

**Modelling of PM_{2.5} Road Dust Emission from On-Road Vehicles:
Developing an Emission Inventory for Resuspended Road Dust in India**

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by

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Abstract

Exposure to particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) from traffic poses significant health risks, as these particles have the ability to deeply penetrate the respiratory tract and reach the lungs. Despite efforts to reduce exhaust emissions, recent studies indicate a projected increase in non-exhaust pollutants, particularly fugitive road dust, due to the expanding vehicle population. Measuring non-exhaust pollutants, especially in developing nations, remains challenging. Therefore, this research study aims to estimate PM_{2.5} resuspended road dust emissions in India at a district level with gridded level of 5km by 5km using the widely accepted USEPA AP-42 methodology. The primary objective of this study is to quantify the contribution of PM_{2.5} resuspended road dust emissions to the total PM_{2.5} levels. The selection of the USEPA AP-42 method is supported by its simplicity, accessibility, and widespread use in the scientific literature for road dust emission estimation. By employing this methodology, the study examines the emissions from different road types and vehicle categories, enabling a comprehensive analysis of their contributions.

The findings reveal that PM_{2.5} resuspended road dust emissions account for approximately 9% of the total PM_{2.5} emissions, with city roads contributing nearly 58% of the emissions. This highlights the substantial role of urban areas in the overall emission landscape, primarily due to the higher vehicle kilometres travelled within cities. The analysis further demonstrates that heavy vehicles play a significant role in emissions due to their increased potential for dust generation compared to lighter vehicles. Moreover, this study identifies Maharashtra as the most polluted state, primarily attributed to its high vehicle kilometres travelled. Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, and Tamil Nadu also exhibit considerable road dust emissions. At the city level, Delhi emerges as the most polluted city, closely followed by Mumbai, Chennai, Kolkata, and Hyderabad, all displaying significant road dust emissions. Comparisons with previous research indicate a strong correlation at the city and state levels, emphasizing the need for updated and comprehensive studies to capture the evolving nature of road dust emissions.

Additionally, the analysis of monthly variations highlights minimum emissions during July and August, and maximum emissions in December and January. This seasonal pattern is attributed to the impact of rainfall, which significantly affects road dust resuspension. Regions with a higher number of wet days experience more effective suppression of road dust emissions, while regions with fewer wet days exhibit relatively lower suppression.

The results of this study have several important implications. First, the estimation of PM_{2.5} resuspended road dust emissions provides crucial input for air quality simulations and modelling. By incorporating this road dust data into air quality models, policymakers and researchers can gain a more accurate understanding of the sources and distribution of PM_{2.5}, enabling them to develop targeted mitigation strategies. Second, the findings offer valuable insights to policymakers and stakeholders in formulating effective measures to mitigate road dust emissions. By identifying highly polluted cities and states, policymakers can prioritize interventions and allocate resources to implement localized strategies for reducing road dust emissions. This can contribute to improving air quality and safeguarding public health in urban environments.

CONTENTS

Chapter 1: Introduction	1
1.1 Background and motivation	1
1.2 Objective	3
1.3 Report Organization and Layout	4
Chapter 2: Literature Review	6
2.1 Non exhaust emission	6
2.1.1 Road dust resuspension	6
2.1.2 Brake wear	7
2.1.3 Tire wear	7
2.1.4 Road wear	7
2.2 Models for non-exhaust emission	8
2.2.1 USEPA AP-42	8
2.2.2 NORTRIP	9
2.2.3 E. Padoan et al. (2018) Method	12
2.2.4 G. Omstedt et al. (2005) Method	13
2.2.5 Moosmuller et al.(1998) Method	14
2.2.6 Comparing Non-Exhaust Emission Modeling Methods	14
Chapter 3: Data and Methodology	18
3.1 Estimation of Total Emissions: Methodology and Workflow	18
3.2 Study Area and Road Network Characterization	19
3.3 Vehicle Categorization and Classification	21
3.4 Emission Factor Estimation	21
3.4.1 Silt load	22
3.4.2 Vehicle weight	24

3.4.3 Precipitation	25
3.5 Vehicle kilometer traveled.....	26
Chapter 4: Results and Discussion.....	28
4.1 District-Level Analysis of Road Dust Emissions: Quantification and Evaluation.....	28
4.2 Quantifying and Mapping Road Dust Emissions on Various Road Types: A Country-wide Study	29
4.3 Identifying Highly Polluted States and Cities: Road Dust Emission Perspective	31
4.4 Comparison of Road Dust Emission Findings: Current Study vs. Previous Research.....	32
4.5 Quantifying the Impact of Precipitation on Road Dust Emission: A Comprehensive Analysis of Monthly, Seasonal, and Spatial Variations.....	34
4.6 Quantifying the Contribution of Different Sectors to Total PM _{2.5} Emissions: Emphasis on Resuspended Road Dust	36
4.7 Limitations of the Road Dust Emission Analysis in this Study.....	38
Chapter 5: Conclusion and Future Work	39
Literature Cited	41
Appendix.....	45

List of Figures

Figure 1: Flowchart Illustrating the Methodology for Estimating Total PM_{2.5} Road Dust Emission from On-Road Vehicles.....	19
Figure 2: Mapping the Study Area Domain: Different Types of Road Networks Illustrated on an India District Map	20
Figure 3: Box Plot Analysis: Silt Load Distribution across different Road Types	23
Figure 4: Spatial Distribution of Wet Days (Based on Precipitation) and Monthly Variation: Impacts on Road Dust Emission	26
Figure 5: District-level Spatial Distribution of Annual Road Dust Emission and Contributions by Road Types and Vehicle Categories.....	29
Figure 6: Mapping Annual PM_{2.5} Road Dust Emission on Different Road Types at a Spatial Resolution of 0.05° × 0.05° on an Indian District Map.....	30
Figure 7: Analysis of Highly Polluted States and Cities Based on PM_{2.5} Road Dust Emission showcasing Contribution from Different Road Types	32
Figure 8: Scatter Plot Comparison: Present Study vs. Previous Study	33
Figure 9: Monthly variation of Total PM_{2.5} road dust emission	34
Figure 10: Seasonal Variation of Annual PM_{2.5} Road Dust Emission at a Spatial Resolution of 0.05° × 0.05°	36
Figure 11: Monthly Variation of Sector-wise PM_{2.5} Emissions.....	37
Figure 12: Sector-wise Contribution to Total PM_{2.5} Emission.....	37

List of Tables

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Non-Exhaust Emission Modelling Methods	15
Table 2: Average vehicle weight of each vehicle categories	24
Table 3: Silt Load Distribution across Road Types in Different Locations	45
Table 4: Monthly wet days of each district (mean value taken for 2011-2021, IMD rainfall)	46
Table 5: Traffic Volume Composition (%) of Each Vehicle Category by Road Types	71
Table 6: District-wise Vehicle Kilometer Travelled (in Billion Vehicle Kilometers) by vehicle categories	72
Table 7: Fraction Weightage of Vehicle Categories on Different Road Types	104
Table 8: State emission comparison dataset	104
Table 9: City emission comparison dataset	106

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background and motivation

Road dust emissions, known as fugitive road dust (FRD), represent a complex and diverse source of atmospheric particles. These particles are released into the surrounding atmosphere as a result of the turbulence generated by moving vehicles on roads (Abu-Allaban et al., 2003; Zhu et al., 2009). These particles originate from various sources, including nearby soils, sediment transported by vehicles, construction and demolition waste, asphalt-derived fly ash, organic matter, natural dust deposition, and other anthropogenic activities (Thorpe et al., 2008; Gunawardana et al., 2018). In recent years, the significance of FRD in contributing to the overall particulate matter (PM) levels has intensified. This can be attributed, in part, to the global rise in the number of vehicles, which has been growing at an approximate rate of 4% annually between 2006 and 2013 (Amato et al., 2014; Han et al., 2014). According to worldwide observations, FRD emissions constituted a significant portion of PM₁₀ levels in different regions. Specifically, in Delhi, India, FRD contributed to 55% of the PM₁₀ concentration in 2010 (Sahu et al., 2011), while in Sao Paulo, Brazil, it accounted for 25.7% of PM₁₀ in 2014 (Pereira et al., 2017). Moreover, in European urban areas between 2000 and 2009, FRD emissions ranged from 14% to 48% of PM₁₀ (Amato et al., 2011).

The substantial impact of road dust emissions on particulate matter (PM) mass is primarily attributed to the coarse size distribution of these particles, typically ranging between 1 and 10µm. This characteristic leads to the frequent exceedance of air quality limit values at urban and traffic sites. Consequently, road dust emissions emerge as a crucial factor that requires comprehensive understanding and effective mitigation strategies to tackle the prevailing air pollution concerns. Amongst the array of pollutants, PM_{2.5} (Particulate matter characterized by a diameter less than 2.5 µm) carries the most significant risk due to its capacity to deeply penetrate the human body. This attribute renders PM_{2.5} particularly hazardous and underscores its heightened potential for adverse health effects (Xing et al., 2016). According to estimations, the exposure to outdoor PM_{2.5} ranks as the third most prominent risk factor in India and the fifth most significant risk factor on a global scale (GBD 2015 Risk Factors Collaborators, 2016). However, road dust raises concerns

due to its substantial content of specific harmful components, such as heavy metals and metalloids (e.g., Cu, Sb, Sn, Fe, Zn, Mo; Amato et al., 2009a), as well as sulfides and carbonaceous aerosols, including elemental and organic carbon (EC and OC), and Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs; Pengchai et al., 2004; Majumdar et al., 2012), among others. These elements contribute significantly to the potential health burden associated with cardiovascular, respiratory, and cancer diseases (Burnett et al., 2014).

In order to gain deeper insights into the interconnections among fugitive road dust (FRD), air quality, economic development, and public health, it becomes crucial to examine the magnitude and spatial as well as temporal variations of FRD emissions. Such a comprehensive study holds the key to enhancing our understanding of these complex relationships and their implications. However, past research has either neglected or substantially underestimated the emissions originating from FRD (Amato et al., 2014). Consequently, this has introduced significant uncertainties in model projections of PM concentrations, specifically for PM_{2.5}. Such uncertainties have a profound impact on our comprehension of the environmental implications, human health effects, and climate consequences associated with these particulate matters (Chen et al., 2018, 2019; Brunekreef et al., 2005; Huang et al., 2014). The calculations of emissions factors can be grouped into three main categories as follows: (i) Emissions factors derived from real-world ambient measurement data, such as comparing traffic emissions to background levels, evaluating upwind and downwind measurements, and analyzing the ratios of NO_x to PM₁₀; (ii) Emission factors based on resuspension fluxes or establishing correlations between emission rates and dust loading, utilizing methodologies like EPA—AP-42, HERMES, NORTRIP, and Empirical Model by Padoan; (iii) Emission factors determined through real-time measurement of emission rates using mobile systems like SCAMPER, TRAKER, EMMA, and SNIFFER. Among the three groupings mentioned above, the second grouping stands out as the most convenient option due to the availability of correlations and easily accessible variables. This approach relies on establishing correlations between emission rates and dust loading, which can be readily obtained. In contrast, the first and third methods involve the use of real-time concentration data, which can be a laborious task and may not be readily accessible. Therefore, the second grouping offers a more practical and efficient means of estimating emission factors for road dust.

1.2 Objective

The primary objective of this study is to develop a comprehensive emission inventory for PM_{2.5} resuspended road dust in India utilizing the AP-42 methodology, with a focus on achieving a grid-level resolution of 5km by 5km. This inventory aims to quantify and analyze the sectoral contribution of resuspended road dust to the total PM_{2.5} emissions. Additionally, the study investigates the contribution of different road types and vehicle categories to road dust emissions, enabling a deeper understanding of the factors influencing emission levels.

Another key objective is to assess the impact of precipitation on road dust emissions and observe the seasonality in emission patterns. By examining the relationship between rainfall and road dust emission levels, the study aims to shed light on the effectiveness of precipitation in mitigating road dust resuspension and its implications for air quality management.

Furthermore, the research focuses on identifying highly polluted cities and states concerning road dust emissions. By evaluating the emission levels across various regions, the study seeks to identify locations with significantly elevated road dust emissions, providing valuable insights for targeted interventions and policy-making.

In summary, the objectives of this study can be summarized as follows:

1. Develop a detailed emission inventory for PM_{2.5} resuspended road dust at a grid level of 5km by 5km in India using the AP-42 methodology.
2. Compare and validate the findings of this study with previous research conducted in the field.
3. Quantify the sectoral contribution of resuspended road dust to the overall PM_{2.5} emissions.
4. Investigate the contribution of different road types and vehicle categories to road dust emissions.
5. Examine the impact of precipitation on road dust emissions and assess the seasonality in emission patterns.
6. Identify highly polluted cities and states based on road dust emissions, facilitating targeted interventions and policy formulation.

By achieving these objectives, this study aims to contribute to a comprehensive understanding of road dust emissions in India and provide valuable insights for air quality management and pollution control strategies.

1.3 Report Organization and Layout

This report is structured into five main chapters and an appendix section. Chapter 2 provides a comprehensive literature review that delves into the fundamental aspects of road dust resuspension and examines various models available in the scientific literature for quantitatively estimating resuspended road dust emissions. A meticulous evaluation and comparison of these models are conducted to determine the most suitable approach to be employed in this study.

Chapter 3 focuses on the data and methodology employed in this research endeavor. It outlines the workflow adopted in this study, providing a detailed description of the methodology used to estimate road dust emissions. The chapter also encompasses the delineation of the study area under consideration and an in-depth analysis of the input parameters, including the selection of pertinent data sources and the underlying assumptions made.

In Chapter 4, the results obtained from the applied model are presented and thoroughly discussed. The analysis encompasses both district-level and gridded-level assessments, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the spatial distribution of emissions. A rigorous comparison of these results with those obtained in previous studies is conducted to validate the findings and elucidate any disparities. Furthermore, this chapter examines the relative contribution of different parameters to the total emissions, with a specific emphasis on quantifying the proportion of PM_{2.5} attributable to resuspended road dust. Additionally, the identification of emission hotspots, areas characterized by higher concentrations of road dust emissions, is undertaken. The chapter also addresses the limitations inherent in this study, including uncertainties and assumptions associated with the data used, which may introduce variations in the results obtained.

Chapter 5 serves as the concluding chapter and offers insights into future research directions. Based on the results and discussions presented in the previous chapter, salient findings and crucial highlights are summarized. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of road dust emissions and offer valuable guidance for developing effective measures to mitigate their adverse impacts. The chapter concludes with a discussion on the implications of the study's outcomes for policymakers and stakeholders, emphasizing the importance of addressing road dust emissions to

improve air quality and foster sustainable urban environments. Furthermore, this chapter outlines future research prospects, such as addressing uncertainties, incorporating localized data, enhancing the mechanistic understanding of road dust dynamics, and adopting more accurate measurement techniques.

The appendix section contains all the input data utilized in this study, accompanied by proper references and supplementary information. This section ensures the transparency and reproducibility of the research, facilitating further analysis and validation by the scientific community.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Non exhaust emission

The emissions of particulate matter (PM) from motor vehicles originate from two primary sources: exhaust emissions produced by combustion engines and the degradation of vehicle components and road surfaces. The latter category is commonly known as non-exhaust PM emissions, encompassing all airborne particle emissions arising from vehicle and road wear, as well as the resuspension of road dust. Non-exhaust PM emissions pertain to the release of airborne particles resulting from the deterioration of vehicle components and road surfaces. This includes particle emissions associated with the wear and tear of brake pads, tires, and other vehicle parts, as well as the resuspension of particulate matter deposited on road surfaces. These emissions contribute significantly to the overall PM pollution and can have implications for air quality, human health, and the environment. In recent years, the significant reduction in exhaust emissions has led to a notable increase in the proportion of particulate matter (PM) emissions originating from non-exhaust sources. Presently, non-exhaust emissions account for nearly 90% of total PM emissions from road traffic (Timmers and Achten, 2016; Rexeis and Hausberger, 2009). Non-exhaust emissions encompass various types, including the resuspension of road dust, brake wear, tire wear, and road wear.

2.1.1 Road dust resuspension

Road dust resuspension refers to the process by which fine particles, consisting of dust and other particulate matter, that have settled on road surfaces are stirred up and reintroduced into the air. This can occur due to vehicle movement, wind, or other disturbances, leading to the suspension of the dust particles in the surrounding atmosphere. Emissions of road dust have a significant impact on the levels of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in the ambient air. The key factors influencing road dust emissions include vehicle speed and size, road dust loading, and weather conditions such as rainfall. Due to the diverse sources and unique chemical composition of road dust at different locations, findings from one specific site cannot be readily applied to another (Amato et al., 2011; Denby, Kupiainen, and Gustafsson, 2018). The relative contributions of various sources and the

overall characteristics of road dust can vary significantly, highlighting the need for site-specific investigations and assessments.

2.1.2 Brake wear

Brake wear particles (PM) are generated when brake pads (linings) and discs (shoes) come into contact and rub against each other. However, it is important to note that not all brake wear debris is released into the air. Based on estimates provided by Garg et al. (2000), Barlow et al. (2007), Sanders et al. (2003), and Kukutschová et al. (2011), approximately 50% of brake wear particles produced by vehicles are released into the air. Sanders et al. (2003) further state that only 50% of brake wear is emitted as airborne particles, with the PM₁₀ component constituting 63% to 85% of the airborne material. Not all worn particles become airborne during the friction process. The emission of particles, including their size and quantity, is influenced by factors such as driving conditions, vehicle characteristics, and brake properties.

2.1.3 Tire wear

Tire wear emissions occur as a result of the abrasion of road surfaces against the tire treads. These emissions consist of particles comprising plasticizers, oils, polymers, carbon blacks, and minerals (Kreider et al., 2010). However, particular attention has been given to the elemental content of tire wear particles, especially zinc and sulfur, due to the adverse effects of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) on ecosystems and human health. Studies by Wang et al. (2017) and Li et al. (2012) have shown that the mass loss from tire wear increases linearly with the vertical load or sprung mass.

2.1.4 Road wear

Road wear is a consequence of the continuous fragmentation and deterioration of road pavement surfaces caused by vehicle traffic. The ballast material used in pavements, typically bonded with bitumen, generates wear particles composed of minerals. These particles contain a significant amount of organic carbon but are predominantly characterized by crustal elements. Particle formation has been found to be influenced by the Nordic abrasion value of the aggregate material and the maximum size of the coarse aggregate, as highlighted by Gustafsson and Johansson (2012).

2.2 Models for non-exhaust emission

The modeling of non-exhaust emissions has been a subject of extensive research, aiming to understand and quantify the contribution of these emissions to air pollution. Various methodologies have been developed to estimate emissions from non-exhaust sources, providing valuable insights into the complex nature of these emissions. These methodologies encompass a range of approaches, including measurements, statistical analysis, and modeling techniques. Researchers have utilized real-world ambient measurement data, established correlations between emission rates and dust loading, and conducted real-time emission rate measurements using mobile systems. Each methodology offers unique advantages and considerations, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of non-exhaust emissions and their impact on air quality. By employing these diverse modeling approaches, researchers have made significant strides in characterizing and quantifying the emissions from non-exhaust sources, thereby contributing to the development of effective mitigation strategies and policies.

2.2.1 USEPA AP-42

The widely adopted approach for quantifying road dust resuspension emissions is the US EPA's AP-42 methodology (USEPA, 2011, AP-42). By employing this methodology, a notable correlation has been observed between vehicle weight and the propensity of silt on a given route to contribute to the generation of re-suspended PM emissions.

In accordance with the modified formula introduced by the USEPA, the emission factors are contingent upon three key variables: vehicular weight (W), silt load (sL), and the frequency of rainy days (P) within a given year. These variables collectively contribute to the quantification of emissions, and their relationship can be expressed through a formula equation (1),

$$EF = k \times (sL)^{0.91} \times (W)^{1.02} \times \left(1 - \frac{P}{4 \times N}\right) \quad (1)$$

In the given equation representing the emission factor, several variables are involved with their respective units and meanings. The emission factor (EF) is expressed in the unit that matches the unit of coefficient k . The coefficient k represents the particle size multiplier, with a value of 0.15 g/VKT for PM_{2.5} and 0.62 g/VKT for PM₁₀. VKT denotes the distance traveled by vehicles in kilometers. The silt load (sL) is measured in grams per square meter (gm^{-2}), while W represents

the average weight of vehicles on the road, measured in tons. P corresponds to the number of days with rainfall, and N represents the total number of days in the average period, typically 365 for an annual period. These notations and their associated values are used to calculate the emission factor.

2.2.2 NORTRIP

The NORTRIP (NON-exhaust Road TRaffic Induced Particle) model, developed by the Norwegian Institute for Air Research, is a predictive tool that integrates surface moisture and road dust to estimate PM10 emissions resulting from traffic activities (Denby et al., 2013a,b). This model incorporates various factors and parameters to simulate the generation and dispersion of particles induced by road traffic, providing valuable insights into the emission patterns and dynamics.

In the initial stage of the model formulation, the PM10 mass balance on the road surface is computed.

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = P - S \quad (2)$$

This involves the calculation of the rate of change of PM10 mass, denoted as dM/dt , which is equal to the difference between the PM10 production rate (P , $g \cdot km^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$) by deposition on the road surface and the PM10 sink rate (S , $g \cdot km^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$) due to resuspension and run-off. The PM10 mass (M) is measured in grams per kilometer ($g \cdot km^{-1}$), while time (t) is measured in hours (h). This equation (2) establishes a fundamental relationship that governs the PM10 dynamics on the road surface, forming the basis for further modeling and analysis.

Within this formulation, the production of PM10 arises from various wear processes, namely brake, tire, and road wear. The PM10 production rate is determined by these wear rates, which are contingent upon the specific vehicle type. Thus, the expression for the PM10 production rate can be defined as follows:

$$P = \sum_{v=1}^2 \sum_{s=1}^3 N_v U_{v,s} f_{PM_s} \quad (3)$$

Within this equation, the index v represents the vehicle type, distinguishing between light-duty vehicles/passenger cars and heavy-duty vehicles. The index s denotes the specific wear type, namely brake, tire, or road wear. N_v represents the traffic flow for each vehicle type (vehicles per

hour). $U_{v,s}$ corresponds to the wear rates resulting from abrasion (grams per kilometer per vehicle). Furthermore, $f_{PM,s}$ represents the fraction of PM10 generated by the respective wear processes, specifically within the particle size range under investigation.

The wear rates are derived from reference emission factors that are specific to each vehicle type. The road wear rate resulting from abrasion can be represented as follows:

$$U_{v,road} = U_{v,road,0} \times h_{pavement} \times \left(\frac{speed}{speed_{ref,road}} \right) \quad (4)$$

The reference wear rate for road wear, denoted as $U_{v,road,0}$, can be determined based on specific values for different vehicle types. For light-duty vehicles and passenger cars, the reference wear rate is $0.15 \text{ g}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}\cdot\text{veh}^{-1}$, while for heavy-duty vehicles, it is $0.75 \text{ g}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}\cdot\text{veh}^{-1}$ (Jacobson and Wagberg, 2007). The parameter $h_{pavement}$ represents the influence of pavement coating, and $speed_{ref,road}$ corresponds to the reference speed for road wear, set at $70 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$.

$$h_{pavement} = 2.49 + 0.144 \times NMB - 0.069 \times MS - 0.0017 \times S \quad (5)$$

The hardness value NMB (Nordic Ball Mill) is set at 12.5, while MS represents the maximal size grain and is defined as 10 mm. The parameter S represents the proportion of grains present in the pavement, which is reported to be 95%. These values are based on a semi coarse asphaltic concrete commonly used in France for road pavements subjected to moderate to high traffic flow conditions (de Bortoli, 2015), resulting in a pavement parameter $h_{pavement}$ of 2.6.

The tire wear rate can be expressed as follows:

$$U_{v,tire} = U_{v,tire,0} \times \left(\frac{speed}{speed_{ref,tire}} \right) \quad (6)$$

The reference wear rate for tire wear, $U_{v,tire,0}$, is determined as $0.1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}\cdot\text{veh}^{-1}$ for light-duty vehicles and passenger cars, and $0.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}\cdot\text{veh}^{-1}$ for heavy-duty vehicles, based on studies by Snilsberg (2008) and Gustafsson et al. (2008). The reference speed for tire wear, $speed_{ref,tire}$, is set at $70 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$.

The brake wear rate, denoted as $U_{v,brake}$, is expressed as follows:

$$U_{v,brake} = U_{v,brake,0} \times h_{traffic} \quad (7)$$

The brake wear rate, denoted as $U_{v,brake,0}$, is determined by the reference wear rate specific to each vehicle type. For light duty vehicles and passenger cars, the reference wear rate is $0.01 \text{ g}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}\cdot\text{veh}^{-1}$ while for heavy-duty vehicles, it is $0.05 \text{ g}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}\cdot\text{veh}^{-1}$, as provided by Boulter in 2005. Additionally, the brake wear rate is adjusted for a standard traffic type using the driving cycle index, $h_{traffic}$, which in this case is set to 1.

The sink rate, denoted as S , is determined for each vehicle type and is influenced by the traffic flow, N_v , and a factor $f_{v,suspension}$, which represents the resuspension of PM10 based on the traffic speed. The sink rate is proportional to the mass of PM10, M , present on the road surface when there is no run-off.

$$S_v = M \times \sum_{v=1}^2 R_v \quad (8)$$

$$R_v = N_v \times f_{v,suspension} \quad (9)$$

The term $f_{v,suspension}$ represents the fraction of PM10 that is resuspended by a vehicle, taking into account its speed and vehicle type in units of veh^{-1} .

$$f_{v,suspension} = f_{v,suspension,0} \times \left(\frac{\text{speed}}{\text{speed}_{ref,resuspension}} \right) \quad (10)$$

The term $f_{v,suspension,0}$ denotes the reference fraction of PM10 resuspension for light-duty and passenger cars ($5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ veh}^{-1}$) and heavy-duty vehicles ($5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ veh}^{-1}$). $\text{speed}_{ref,resuspension}$ represents the reference speed at which traffic resuspension of particles occurs ($50 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$).

As a result, the mass balance equation governing the PM10 concentration on the road surface is represented by the following expression:

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = P - M \times \sum_{v=1}^2 R_v \quad (11)$$

The equation is solved to derive the temporal variation of PM10 mass accumulated on the road surface.

$$M(t) = \frac{P}{\sum_{v=1}^2 R_v} + \left(M(t=0) - \frac{P}{\sum_{v=1}^2 R_v} \right) \times \exp\left(-\sum_{v=1}^2 R_v \times t\right) \quad (12)$$

The rate of resuspension emissions can be determined using the following mathematical expression:

$$E_{resuspension(t)} = M(t) \times \sum_{v=1}^2 R_v(t) \quad (13)$$

2.2.3 E. Padoan et al. (2018) Method

Padoan et al. (2018) proposed a novel approach for estimating road dust emission factors (EFs) by utilizing a power relationship inspired by the work of Amato et al. (2011). This methodology, which shares a comparable theoretical foundation with the USEPA AP-42 model, replaces the conventional silt (<75µm) loading parameter with MF10 in the EF estimation process.

$$EF_i = a \times MF10_i^b \quad (14)$$

In the equation, MF10_i represents the suspendible fraction of road dust at the *i*th location, while the coefficients *a* and *b* are determined empirically.

Instead of relying on external sources, the prediction model aims to estimate the contributions to MF10 loading originating from various traffic-related sources such as construction dust, soil resuspension, or African deposition. Through a multiple linear regression analysis, the maximum MF10 loading from the CAM, traffic intensity (TR), and distance (DIST) from the nearest braking zone were predicted. Several linear regression models with two or three variables, using exponential or potential equations, were tested since each parameter exhibited an inverse association with MF10. Our findings indicate that the equation providing the most accurate prediction of MF10 was:

$$RD10 = e^{2.9 \pm 0.89} \times CAM^{-0.26 \pm 0.12} \times TR^{-0.22 \pm 0.11} \times DIST^{-0.15 \pm 0.08} \quad (15)$$

The CAM (Coarse Aggregate Morphology) of the i -th sample is computed based on the MTD (Mean Texture Depth), the dominant characteristics of aggregates observed through photographic analysis, and the average horizontal size of the aggregates. The calculation of $(CAM)_i$ can be expressed using the following formula:

$$(CAM)_i = MTD_i \times \frac{(aggregate\ mode_i)}{(aggregate\ mean_i)} \quad (16)$$

Here, $(CAM)_i$ represents the CAM value for the i -th sample, MTD is the Mean Texture Depth, Mode(aggregates) refers to the dominant characteristics of aggregates observed, and Mean (horizontal size of aggregates) denotes the average horizontal size of the aggregates. The macro-texture of road pavement refers to the dimensions of the aggregate particles and the void spaces present between them within the asphalt mixture (Henry, 2000).

2.2.4 G. Omstedt et al. (2005) Method

The method proposed by Omstedt et al. provides a valuable approach for estimating particle emission factors. It involves utilizing scaling techniques with NO_x as a tracer and making use of field observations under conditions of high suspension. By considering the concentrations of particles and NO_x in both background and roadside areas, this method enables the estimation of accurate emission factors. The reference emission factor, which serves as the starting point for the model, can be effectively determined using this approach. It offers a practical and reliable means of quantifying emissions and enhancing the predictive capabilities of the model.

$$e_f^{PM} = e_f^{NO_x} \times \left(\frac{C_{PM}^{roadside} - C_{PM}^{background}}{C_{NO_x}^{roadside} - C_{PM}^{background}} \right) \quad (17)$$

$e_f^{NO_x}$: The emission factor for NO_x, which is often more well known and characterized compared to the emission factor for particles. It serves as a reference for scaling and estimating particle emissions.

By utilizing the available information on background and roadside particle concentrations (C_{PM}) and NO_x concentrations (C_{NO_x}), the total emission factor can be calculated. The total emission factor accounts for both direct emissions and emissions from the dust layer, providing a comprehensive measure of particle emissions. The method accounts for the interplay between

particle and NOx emissions and utilizes the relationship between their concentrations to estimate particle emission factors accurately.

2.2.5 Moosmuller et al.(1998) Method

The method proposed by Moosmüller et al. involves calculating the emission factor from a moving vehicle using the following formula:

$$EF_{VKT} = A \times CT_{AV} \times \left(\frac{V_i}{V_{veh}} \right) \quad (18)$$

The emission factor (EF) for particulate matter (PM) emitted per vehicle-kilometer-traveled (VKT) is calculated using the formula proposed by Moosmüller et al. The formula incorporates several variables: A represents the plume area in square meters (the product of plume width, W, and plume height, H), CT_{AV} corresponds to the PM concentration in milligrams per cubic meter (mg/m^3), V_i denotes the wind speed in meters per second (m/s), and V_{veh} represents the vehicle speed in meters per second (m/s).

The plume width in the context of the study was estimated by approximating it as the distance covered by the vehicle during the exposure time ($t_{exp} \times V_{veh}$). Similarly, the plume height was approximated as the height of the vehicle itself. By applying these approximations, the emission rate of particulate matter (PM) per vehicle-kilometer-traveled (EF_{VKT}) can be expressed as follows:

$$EF_{VKT} = H_{veh} \times t_{exp} \times V_i \times CT_{AV} \quad (19)$$

In the given equation, t_{exp} represents the exposure time in seconds (s), while H_{veh} denotes the height of the vehicle in meters (m).

Equation (19) plays a pivotal role in the computation of the PM emission rate for various vehicle classes. Measurable quantities such as H_{veh} (vehicle height) and V_i (wind speed) are utilized, while t_{exp} (exposure time) and CT_{AV} (PM mass concentration) are derived from the observed gradients of vertical PM concentrations generated by the passage of vehicles at the sampling location.

2.2.6 Comparing Non-Exhaust Emission Modeling Methods

In order to comprehensively assess and compare various non-exhaust emission modeling methods, a rigorous analysis of their capabilities in capturing the intricate dynamics of non-exhaust

emissions is imperative. Multiple methodologies have been proposed, each presenting distinct advantages and constraints. Through meticulous scrutiny and comparison of these approaches, valuable insights can be obtained regarding their efficacy and suitability in accurately estimating non-exhaust emissions from diverse sources. Such a comprehensive evaluation is essential for advancing our understanding and enhancing the reliability of non-exhaust emission modeling techniques.

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Non-Exhaust Emission Modelling Methods

Modeling Methods	Input Variables	Comments and Observations
USEPA AP-42	Silt load (particle less than 75µm), Average vehicle weight, Precipitation, Vehicle kilometer traveled	The US EPA AP-42 road dust resuspension model is commonly employed due to its widespread adoption and practicality. It offers a simplified approach by considering a limited set of variables. Nonetheless, the model's scope is restricted as it does not account for important factors such as vehicle speed, leading to potential underestimation of total emissions
NORTRIP	Traffic volume count Vehicle speed, Road dust load in g/km, Pavement related data (grain size, its hardness and its percentage in pavement)	The NORTRIP model demonstrates a comprehensive consideration of various parameters, encompassing both dust resuspension and wear rates. However, its applicability in certain regions, such as India, may be limited due to the requirement of specific and detailed input variables that may not be readily available
E. Padoan (2018)	MF10 (road dust less than 10 µm), Traffic intensity, Distance of closest braking zone,	The proposed model shares similarities with the AP-42 method, yet it incorporates the MF10 parameter instead of silt load to enhance the realism of dust emission estimation. However, the

	Size of aggregate particle	model necessitates extensive sampling across various locations to accurately estimate the emission factor.
Omstedt (2005)	Roadside and Background concentration of PM Roadside concentration of NOx, which is used as tracer	This model adopts an experimental approach, emphasizing the estimation of concentration at each specific location
Moosmuller (1998)	PM concentration, Wind speed, Vehicle speed, Plume area	This model incorporates real-time measurements of input variables using DustTrak instrumentation, enabling a more experimental approach. It considers the plume area, enhancing the accuracy of emission estimations through empirical observations

Among the discussed models, the USEPA AP-42 and NORTRIP models are considered more user-friendly compared to others. However, the use of concentration-related variables in the formulas of other models necessitates continuous monitoring of emissions, making them less preferable. The selection of the USEPA AP-42 method over other non-exhaust emission models is supported by several factors. The AP-42 model offers simplicity and ease of use, making it accessible to researchers and practitioners. It utilizes straightforward variables, enhancing its practicality and applicability. Moreover, the AP-42 model has gained substantial recognition in the scientific community and is widely employed in the literature for road dust emission estimation. Its widespread adoption allows for better comparability and benchmarking of results, facilitating scientific understanding. In contrast, other models may incorporate additional parameters and complexities, requiring extensive monitoring efforts and specialized data, which may not be feasible for large-scale studies or regions with limited resources. By leveraging the standardized

and widely accepted AP-42 methodology, this research aims to estimate emission factors for different road types in various districts across India, ensuring reliable and comparable findings on a national scale. Therefore, the utilization of the USEPA AP-42 method aligns with the objectives of providing practical insights while considering the specific context and constraints of the study area, contributing to the knowledge on non-exhaust emissions.

Chapter 3: Data and Methodology

This chapter encompasses a comprehensive description of the essential components for conducting this research. It begins by outlining the data collection process, highlighting the sources and methods employed to gather relevant information. Subsequently, the methodology section presents the analytical framework adopted to address the research objectives. This framework encompasses the chosen models, algorithms, and statistical techniques utilized to analyze the collected data and derive meaningful insights. Additionally, the study area is delineated, providing a clear definition of the geographic scope and boundaries within which the research is conducted.

3.1 Estimation of Total Emissions: Methodology and Workflow

The estimation of total emissions involves a systematic methodology and workflow that integrates various factors and data sources. This comprehensive approach allows for the accurate assessment of emissions on a broader scale. The process begins with the determination of emission factors, which represent the amounts of pollutants emitted per unit of activity. These factors are derived from extensive research and empirical data, ensuring their scientific validity. Additionally, activity data, such as vehicle counts and travel distances, are collected to quantify the intensity of emissions sources. By combining emission factors with activity data, the total emissions can be calculated, providing valuable insights into the environmental impact of various sectors. This rigorous methodology and workflow enable researchers and policymakers to make informed decisions and develop effective strategies for emission reduction and environmental management.

The total emissions can be determined by multiplying the emission factor with the corresponding activity data, represented by the formula:

$$\text{Total emission} = \text{Emission factor} \times \text{Activity data} \quad (20)$$

In this study, road dust emissions were quantified using the Emission Factor (EF) derived from the USEPA AP-42 Method and activity data represented by vehicle kilometers traveled. The EF was determined based on the silt load, which refers to the smaller-sized particles (<75 micrometers) of road dust deposited on the road surface. Additionally, the EF incorporated factors such as vehicle weight, precipitation, and other relevant parameters. The activity data required for estimating vehicle kilometers traveled included annual vehicle registration data, survival fraction, and annual average distance traveled. By combining these inputs, the study successfully estimated the PM_{2.5} resuspended road dust emissions at a district level. To spatially distribute the emissions, a 5 km by 5 km grid system was employed, taking into account the road length fraction in each district. Furthermore, different road categories and vehicle types were considered to account for variations

in the input parameters. The workflow of this research involved the systematic characterization and quantification of each parameter, leading to the comprehensive assessment of road dust emissions. Subsequent sections will provide detailed analysis and discussion of individual parameters.

Figure 1: Flowchart Illustrating the Methodology for Estimating Total PM2.5 Road Dust Emission from On-Road Vehicles

3.2 Study Area and Road Network Characterization

The study encompassed the entire geographical domain of India, specifically focusing on the road networks present within each district. Emission modeling was conducted at the district level for all states in India, subsequently converting the results into gridded emissions at a spatial resolution of 0.05° x 0.05°. Notably, the road network in India has experienced significant expansion over the past decade, necessitating a comprehensive characterization for effective emission analysis.

The road network in India was categorized into four distinct types based on traffic characteristics, namely Golden-Length, Highway-Length, District-Length, and City-Length roads. These road categories serve as crucial transportation arteries for both interstate and intrastate travel, accommodating various types of vehicles. The differentiation of road types was warranted due to the varying input variables required by the emission modeling method. By considering different road types, the study ensured a more accurate representation of the factors influencing emissions. This approach enables a comprehensive understanding of the emission dynamics within the diverse road network of India.

Figure 2: Mapping the Study Area Domain: Different Types of Road Networks Illustrated on an India District Map

Figure 2 displays the cartographic representation of the road network across various districts in India. The map showcases the intensity of road length within each grid, depicted at a spatial resolution of $0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$. To obtain accurate information regarding road length in each grid, the dataset incorporated data from authoritative sources. Specifically, the road length data for the

Golden Quadrilateral, national and state highways, and district roads were sourced from the Archaeological Survey of India. Additionally, for city roads, the Global Roads Inventory Project (GRIP) database was utilized. By amalgamating these reputable data sources, the study ensured the reliability and precision of the road length information for each grid. By utilizing comprehensive road network data, the estimation of road dust emissions becomes more precise and reliable, enhancing our understanding of the environmental impact of road transportation.

3.3 Vehicle Categorization and Classification

In this study, a comprehensive categorization and classification scheme was employed to classify vehicles into seven distinct categories based on available traffic counts. The vehicle categories included Two-wheelers (2 W), Light motor vehicle-passenger (LMV-P), four-wheelers (4W), Light motor vehicle-goods (LMV-G), Buses, Heavy duty vehicle-Trucks (HDV-T), and others. The 2W category encompassed scooters, motorbikes of varying engine capacities and types, while LMV-P comprised auto-rickshaws and vehicles powered by compressed natural gas (CNG). The 4W category encompassed passenger cars, jeeps, and taxis of different engine capacities, ages, and fuel types (petrol, diesel, and CNG). LMV-G included light commercial vehicles such as pickups and utility vehicles like Bolero and TATA ACE. The BUS category accounted for various types of buses, including those running on CNG and diesel. HDV-T encompassed trucks of different tire configurations such as 4-tyre, 6-tyre, and 10-tyre trucks. The "others" category comprised vehicles like tractors, trailers, JCB machines, road rollers, and multi-axle lorries. This comprehensive categorization scheme enables a detailed analysis of different vehicle types, facilitating a more accurate estimation of road dust emissions associated with specific vehicle categories.

3.4 Emission Factor Estimation

Emission factors (EF) play a pivotal role in the quantification of total emissions generated by vehicles. They represent a specific fraction that indicates the emission rate from a pollution source. Vehicular EFs provide insights into the amount of pollutant emitted per kilometer traveled under mixed driving conditions. In this study, the estimation of particulate matter resuspension emission factors was conducted using the latest formula from the United States Environmental Protection Agency's AP-42 methodology (USEPA, 2011). These emission factors are contingent upon factors

such as the weight of the vehicles (W), silt load (sL), and the number of rainy days (P) within a designated averaging period. By considering these key parameters, a comprehensive understanding of the emission characteristics can be achieved, allowing for accurate estimation of particulate matter resuspension from vehicular sources.

3.4.1 Silt load

The silt load (sL) denotes the quantity of dust particles present on a road surface per square meter, measured in grams per square meter (g/m²). It plays a crucial role in the resuspension process, whereby dust particles are lifted from the road surface into the air. The silt load is influenced by various factors, including its source, seasonal variations, and specific geographical locations. The resuspension emission factor is directly affected by the silt load, which exhibits variability across different roads and within specific road segments, based on local conditions and circumstances (USEPA, 2011; Amato et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2017; Denby et al., 2018; Kuhns et al., 2001; Gustafsson et al., 2019).

Studies have indicated that silt measurements are generally lower in faster lanes compared to slower lanes (Zhang et al., 2017; Kuhns et al., 2001). This suggests that roads with higher Average Daily Traffic (ADT) and faster-moving traffic experience less silt accumulation due to increased resuspension, which lifts the dust particles from the center of the road to the roadside. In contrast, branch roads tend to have higher silt loads due to dust transportation from human activities and less resuspension caused by slower traffic. It is well-established that roads with fast-moving traffic result in more resuspension (Amato et al., 2017), while simultaneously exhibiting lower silt accumulation (Zhang et al., 2017; USEPA, 2011; Kuhns et al., 2001). These findings emphasize the intricate relationship between traffic characteristics, resuspension phenomena, and the distribution of silt load on road surfaces.

Figure 3: Box Plot Analysis: Silt Load Distribution across different Road Types

The variation in silt load distribution across different road types in various regions of India is depicted through box plots (Figure 3), which provide insights into the range and dispersion of silt load values. The silt load data used in this study is taken from multiple sources, including the Central and State Pollution Control Boards, TERI, CSIR-NEERI, and relevant research papers, among others. Table 1 in Appendix section contains a comprehensive compilation of silt load values from these studies and upon careful examination of the dataset, it becomes apparent that the silt load values for Uttar Pradesh (UP) exhibit significantly higher magnitudes compared to other states. This observation is consistent with the findings depicted in the box plot, prompting the classification of data into three distinct categories: UP states, other states (excluding UP), and a collective representation encompassing all states. To ensure accurate estimation and facilitate meaningful comparisons with previous studies, different statistical values are derived from each category.

Notably, the 25th percentile value from other states, encompassing all road types, emerges as an optimal statistical measure for estimation and evaluation purposes. Although having data for every region would be ideal, the study acknowledges the limitations of the dataset and employs meticulous data manipulation techniques to identify statistically robust values that yield superior evaluation results. By adopting this approach, the research endeavors to strike a balance between data availability and reliability, leveraging the available information to generate valuable insights into total emission estimation.

3.4.2 Vehicle weight

The vehicle weight plays a crucial role in influencing non-exhaust emissions, particularly those arising from road wear, tire wear, and brake wear. These emissions are primarily generated due to the frictional forces encountered during vehicle operation. Heavier vehicles tend to create more turbulence, leading to increased resuspension emissions. Additionally, the weight of a vehicle can contribute to the grinding of larger particles into finer ones, resulting in a higher level of resuspended particulate matter (PM) emissions. Furthermore, heavier vehicles induce turbulence, further enhancing the resuspension process.

Table 2: Average vehicle weight of each vehicle categories

Vehicle categories	2-wheelers ^[a]	LMV Passengers ^[a]	4- wheelers ^[a]	LMV Goods ^[a]	HDV Trucks ^[a]	Buses ^[a]	Others ^[b]
Average weight (in Tons)	0.175	0.450	1.425	7.500	20.000	15.800	2.000

[a] *Mumbai CPCB report, 2010*

[b] *ARAI Technical paper no. 2017-26-0156*

The weight of vehicles can vary depending on factors such as the vehicle model, make, engine, and load. In this study, average vehicle weights for each vehicle category, expressed in tons, were obtained from NEERI (2010) [a] and ARAI (2017) [b] reports, as presented in Table 2. These average weights are essential for the emission calculations conducted using the AP-42 method. To

determine the average vehicle weight, the composition of vehicles on a specific road is multiplied by their respective weights. Understanding the relationship between vehicle weight and road dust resuspension emissions provides valuable insights into the emission estimation process. By considering the weight of vehicles as a contributing factor, the study aims to capture the impact of different vehicle types on the overall emissions resulting from road dust resuspension.

3.4.3 Precipitation

Precipitation plays a significant role in influencing road dust resuspension emissions, as it has the ability to effectively suppress emissions for a certain period. The impact of precipitation is accounted for by setting the resuspension rate to zero during periods when the precipitation amount exceeds a threshold of $0.254 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ (Pay et al., 2011). In the AP-42 model, the number of wet days, defined as days with precipitation equal to or exceeding 0.254 mm (0.01 in), is considered using IMD Rainfall data. To incorporate the effect of rainfall, the study considers the average of several years of data to ensure a stable value that does not vary drastically with each passing year. The inclusion of precipitation as a parameter in the road dust resuspension emission estimation enhances the accuracy of the model by accounting for the temporary reduction in emissions caused by rainfall events. Understanding the role of precipitation and its effect on road dust resuspension aids in capturing the seasonal and regional variations in emissions, contributing to a more comprehensive assessment of total emissions.

Figure 4 provides a visual representation of the precipitation effect on road dust resuspension. Part (a) of the figure displays the spatial distribution of annual wet days on a district map of India. It illustrates the geographical variation in the occurrence of wet days across different regions. In part (b), the regions are divided into distinct zones, and the monthly variation of wet days in each zone is depicted. This visualization allows for the identification of specific periods and regions where the effect of precipitation is more pronounced. Part (c) presents the monthly variation in the average number of wet days for the entire country. From these plots, it is evident that the months of June, July, August, and September consistently exhibit a higher frequency of wet days, indicating significant suppression of road dust emissions during these months. Additionally, the analysis reveals that the northeastern region of India experiences a considerable effect of precipitation, with wet days occurring in a larger number of months compared to other regions.

Figure 4: Spatial Distribution of Wet Days (Based on Precipitation) and Monthly Variation: Impacts on Road Dust Emission

3.5 Vehicle kilometer traveled

Vehicle Kilometers Traveled (VKT) is a fundamental metric that quantifies the total distance covered by motor vehicles on the highway system within a specified time frame. It serves as a crucial variable for various analyses related to fuel efficiency, fuel consumption, environmental quality, and highway safety (Rudman L., 1979). VKT, being an activity data, plays a pivotal role in estimating and calculating emissions associated with vehicular activities. In the context of emission estimation, VKT serves as a critical input parameter in the calculation of road dust emissions. It provides valuable information on the extent of vehicle usage, enabling a more accurate assessment of the emission levels attributable to vehicular activities. By incorporating VKT data into the emission estimation framework, the impact of road dust resuspension can be quantified on a spatial and temporal scale, aiding in the development of effective mitigation strategies and policies.

Moreover, VKT data facilitates the evaluation of transportation-related impacts on the environment, allowing for the identification of areas with higher emissions and the exploration of

potential emission reduction measures. Additionally, VKT data can be utilized in assessing the effectiveness of interventions aimed at improving fuel efficiency, reducing emissions, and enhancing overall transportation sustainability. By considering VKT as an essential component in emission modeling, researchers and policymakers can gain valuable insights into the relationship between vehicular activity and emissions, paving the way for evidence-based decision-making and the implementation of targeted measures to mitigate the environmental consequences of road dust emissions.

The Vehicle Kilometers Traveled (VKT) data utilized in this study was obtained from Shahzar Khan (IIT Delhi). The estimation process involved calculating VKT for each vehicle category across all districts in India. VKT was derived by multiplying the on-road vehicle count by the average annual distance traveled (AADT). The AADT values were obtained from survey data specifically collected for this purpose. The on-road vehicle count was determined by multiplying the annual vehicle registration data with the survival fraction. The survival fraction was computed using a log logistic survival function, and the parameter values were obtained from the survey data. The annual vehicle registration data was sourced from MoRTH & MoPNG, 2019, while the city-wise vehicle registration data was derived from state-wise registration data, using population proxies. To allocate the VKT to each road category, assumptions were made regarding the proportion of each vehicle category that operates on specific road types. These assumptions were compiled into a framework provided in the table included in the Table 7 in Appendix section. The final VKT values, expressed in billion kilometers traveled, were obtained for each of the seven vehicle categories across all districts in India. These values can be found in the table presented in the Table 6 in Appendix section, providing comprehensive insights into the magnitude of vehicle travel for emission estimation and related analyses.

Chapter 4: Results and Discussion

In this study, an inventory of resuspended road dust emissions is generated using a model that incorporates refined assumptions for the input parameters, as discussed in the Data and Methodology section. The analysis includes an examination of the spatial and temporal variations in road dust emissions, and a comparison of the results with findings from previous studies. By employing robust methodologies and considering relevant factors, this study aims to provide scientific insights into the magnitude and characteristics of road dust emissions. The following sections delve into the detailed results and discussions, shedding light on the key findings and implications for air quality management and policy development.

4.1 District-Level Analysis of Road Dust Emissions: Quantification and Evaluation

The quantification and evaluation of road dust emissions were carried out using the AP-42 model, which integrates multiple parameters that influence emission levels. The activity data used for this analysis was the vehicle kilometer traveled, providing a comprehensive understanding of the emission patterns at the district level. The results, as depicted in Figure 5, highlight the spatial distribution of annual PM_{2.5} road dust emissions across districts in India.

In Part (a) of the figure, a spatial plot showcases the annual PM_{2.5} road dust emission on a district map of India. The total annual PM_{2.5} road dust emission for the entire country was estimated to be 0.94 Tg/year. Part (b) of the figure displays the percentage contribution of different road types to the overall emissions. Notably, approximately 58% of the emissions originate from city roads, emphasizing the significant role of cities in the emission landscape. This observation can be attributed to the higher vehicle kilometer traveled values observed in the city road network. Following cities, district-level emissions vary, with relatively lower emissions from highways and the golden quadrilateral due to their lower silt load values. Part (c) of the figure provides insight into the percentage contribution of each vehicle category to the overall road dust emissions. The analysis reveals that heavy vehicles make a substantial contribution to the emissions, given their tendency to generate more dust compared to lighter vehicles. The district-level analysis of road dust emissions offers a comprehensive quantification and evaluation of the PM_{2.5} emissions,

shedding light on the spatial distribution and major contributing factors. The findings provide valuable information for policymakers and stakeholders in formulating targeted strategies to mitigate road dust emissions and improve air quality.

Figure 5: District-level Spatial Distribution of Annual Road Dust Emission and Contributions by Road Types and Vehicle Categories

4.2 Quantifying and Mapping Road Dust Emissions on Various Road Types: A Country-wide Study

The quantification and mapping of road dust emissions on different road types were performed at the district level, providing valuable insights into the emission patterns and intensities. To achieve a more detailed understanding of emissions along different road networks, a spatial distribution analysis was conducted on a 5 km by 5 km grid resolution, as depicted in Figure 6. To distribute the district-level emissions onto the grid, proxy data in the form of road length on each road type within the district was utilized. By considering the length fraction, the emission values specific to each road type were allocated to the corresponding grid cells. Consequently, a spatial resolution

of 0.05° by 0.05° was achieved, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of emissions at a finer scale.

Figure 6: Mapping Annual PM_{2.5} Road Dust Emission on Different Road Types at a Spatial Resolution of $0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$ on an Indian District Map

The magnitude of annual PM_{2.5} road dust emissions was determined for different road types. Specifically, the golden quadrilateral, highways, districts, and cities exhibited annual emissions of 12,729 tons/year, 97,030 tons/year, 552,477 tons/year, and 282,280 tons/year, respectively. These figures provide a clear indication of the emission levels associated with each road type. The spatial distribution analysis revealed notable emission hotspots that were consistent across all road networks. This consistency suggests the presence of specific locations where emissions tend to be

consistently higher, regardless of the road type under consideration. This comprehensive country-wide study presents a robust quantification and mapping of road dust emissions, offering valuable insights into the emission patterns across various road types. The findings contribute to a better understanding of the spatial distribution and magnitude of road dust emissions, facilitating targeted strategies for mitigating emissions and improving air quality on a regional scale.

4.3 Identifying Highly Polluted States and Cities: Road Dust Emission Perspective

In order to identify highly polluted states and cities from the perspective of PM_{2.5} resuspended road dust emission, a comprehensive analysis was conducted. The emissions for each state were calculated by summing up the PM_{2.5} resuspended road dust emissions of all districts within that state, utilizing the district emission data. Similarly, for cities, the emission values were extracted using the city emission shape file and gridded emission file. A stacked bar plot, depicted in Figure 7, showcases the analysis of highly polluted states and cities based on their PM_{2.5} road dust emissions, highlighting the contributions from different road types. The plot provides valuable insights into the distribution of emissions among various road types within these highly polluted regions.

From the analysis, it was observed that Maharashtra emerged as the most polluted state, primarily attributed to its high vehicle kilometer traveled. Following Maharashtra, states such as Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, and Tamil Nadu exhibited significant levels of road dust emissions. These findings underline the need for targeted interventions in these regions to mitigate the adverse impact of road dust emissions on air quality. In terms of city-level emissions, Delhi emerged as the most polluted city, demonstrating exceptionally high PM_{2.5} road dust emissions. The city was closely followed by Mumbai, Chennai, Kolkata, and Hyderabad, all of which exhibited significant levels of road dust emissions. These findings shed light on the spatial distribution of pollution hotspots and emphasize the urgent need for effective pollution control measures in these highly polluted cities. The identification of highly polluted states and cities based on PM_{2.5} resuspended road dust emissions provides crucial insights for policymakers and stakeholders, facilitating the development of targeted strategies and interventions to improve air quality and public health in these regions. The findings underscore the importance of comprehensive pollution management

approaches and emphasize the role of road dust emissions in contributing to the overall air pollution burden.

Figure 7: Analysis of Highly Polluted States and Cities Based on PM2.5 Road Dust Emission showcasing Contribution from Different Road Types

4.4 Comparison of Road Dust Emission Findings: Current Study vs. Previous Research

The comparison between the PM2.5 resuspended road dust emissions reported in the present study and previous research is presented in Appendix Table, and the findings are visualized in Figure 8. The scatter plot analysis provides valuable insights into the relationship between the emissions reported in the current study and those reported in the literature. The R-value, correlation coefficient, and Normalized Mean Bias (NMB) are reported to quantify the level of agreement between the two datasets.

In part (a) of the analysis, a comparison is conducted for different cities where emission data are available in the literature. To ensure consistency, the values for the corresponding regions are extracted from the gridded emission dataset. The scatter plot reveals that the data points deviate from the ideal X=Y line, indicating some discrepancies between the two datasets. However, the correlation coefficient of 0.84 suggests a reasonably strong correlation, indicating similarities between the present study and the previous literature. The NMB value of 0.20 indicates a low level

of deviation between the two datasets, further supporting the reliability of the comparison for city-level emissions.

Figure 8: Scatter Plot Comparison: Present Study vs. Previous Study

In part (b) of the analysis, the emissions for states are compared with the previous data obtained from the 2016 TERI report. The scatter plot demonstrates a high correlation coefficient of 0.97, indicating a strong agreement between the current study and the TERI report in terms of state-level emissions. However, it is important to note that the normalized mean bias is relatively high, suggesting a noticeable difference between the emissions reported in the present study and the TERI report. The current study reports emissions that are approximately three times higher than the values reported in the 2016 TERI report. This divergence can be attributed to the increasing number of on-road vehicles over time, which contributes to higher road dust emissions. It is worth mentioning that the absence of specific regulations addressing road dust emissions might also contribute to the observed differences. In the Appendix section, Table 8 and Table 9 present comparison data sets for the purpose of evaluating and benchmarking the obtained results.

Overall, the comparison between the road dust emissions findings of the current study and previous research highlights both similarities and disparities. While a strong correlation is observed at the city and state levels, there are variations in the absolute emission values, underscoring the need for updated and comprehensive studies to capture the evolving nature of road dust emissions. Additionally, the findings emphasize the significance of implementing effective regulations and control measures to mitigate the escalating road dust emissions and their impact on air quality.

4.5 Quantifying the Impact of Precipitation on Road Dust Emission: A Comprehensive Analysis of Monthly, Seasonal, and Spatial Variations

The effect of precipitation on road dust resuspension is a crucial aspect addressed in the AP-42 model. To account for the impact of rainfall, the model considers the number of wet days and sets the resuspension rate to zero when the precipitation amount exceeds 0.254 mm/hr (Pay et al., 2011). However, it should be noted that some input parameters in the model, such as vehicle weight and silt load, are assumed to remain constant throughout the year due to the lack of monthly data for these variables. The only parameter that exhibits monthly variation is the number of wet days, which directly influences the monthly variation in PM_{2.5} resuspended road dust emissions. Figure 9 provides a depiction of the monthly variation in road dust emissions. It reveals that the minimum emissions occur during July and August, while the maximum emissions are observed in December and January. This pattern can be attributed to the impact of rainfall, which has a substantial effect on road dust resuspension.

Figure 9: Monthly variation of Total PM_{2.5} road dust emission

The influence of precipitation is particularly pronounced in the northeastern region of India, where the number of wet days reaches approximately 200 annually. As a result, the annual suppression of road dust emissions in this region is estimated to be around 14%. Conversely, the states of Rajasthan and Punjab exhibit a lesser impact of rainfall due to a lower number of wet days (approximately 40 annually), resulting in a modest annual suppression of road dust emissions at around 3%. To examine the spatial variation of road dust emissions seasonally, a seasonal plot is presented in Figure 10, showcasing the gridded emissions of road dust. It is worth noting that the gridded plot does not exhibit significant variations due to its inherent nature, which emphasizes a more localized perspective. However, when analyzing the total annual emissions for India, as shown in Figure 9, noticeable monthly variations become evident. The findings highlight the substantial influence of precipitation on road dust emissions, with pronounced seasonal and spatial variations. The higher number of wet days in the northeastern region leads to more effective suppression of road dust emissions, while areas with fewer wet days, such as Rajasthan and Punjab, experience relatively lower suppression. These observations underscore the importance of considering the impact of precipitation in road dust emission models and the need for localized strategies to mitigate the adverse effects of road dust on air quality.

Figure 10: Seasonal Variation of Annual PM_{2.5} Road Dust Emission at a Spatial Resolution of 0.05° × 0.05°

4.6 Quantifying the Contribution of Different Sectors to Total PM_{2.5} Emissions: Emphasis on Resuspended Road Dust

The composition of Total PM_{2.5} encompasses various components, including carbonaceous substances, inorganic ions, and mineral dust. Among these, mineral dust consists of three major categories: natural windblown dust originating from arid desert regions (Prospero et al., 2002), anthropogenic wind-blown dust resulting from human-induced changes in land use practices, deforestation, and agriculture (Tegen et al., 1996, 2004), and anthropogenic dust emissions from urban sources, combustion processes, and industrial activities. Figure 11 illustrates the monthly variation of each sector contributing to Total PM_{2.5}, including Thermal Power Plants, Cooking, Resuspended Road Dust, Heavy Industry, Other Industry, Brick Production, Diesel & CNG, Gasoline, Heating & Lighting, Diesel Genset, Residue Burning, and Tractor & Pump. Notably, Figure 12 showcases the sector-wise contribution to the overall PM_{2.5} emission. Specifically, the contribution of resuspended road dust to Total PM_{2.5} is found to be 8.7%. The data for each sector is sourced from the SMOG India emission inventory, obtained through the NCAP-COALESCE project.

This emphasizes the significant role of resuspended road dust in the overall PM_{2.5} emissions. The findings highlight the importance of addressing road dust management strategies to mitigate its adverse impact on air quality. By understanding and quantifying the contribution of different

sectors, particularly resuspended road dust, policymakers and stakeholders can devise targeted measures to reduce PM2.5 levels and improve air quality for sustainable urban environments.

Figure 11: Monthly Variation of Sector-wise PM2.5 Emissions

Figure 12: Sector-wise Contribution to Total PM2.5 Emission

4.7 Limitations of the Road Dust Emission Analysis in this Study

The estimation of emissions in this study may be subject to uncertainties related to emission factors and vehicle kilometer traveled due to the lack of detailed traffic activity data and region-specific emission factors. To achieve more accurate estimations, region-specific input variables are necessary. The resuspension emission estimation, based on the USEPA AP-42 methodology, which was developed for a different region, introduces potential uncertainty when applied to the Indian context due to the inherent differences in data used for model formulation (Venkatram, 2000). Additionally, uncertainties are associated with the estimation of silt load (Teng et al., 2008). Venkatram (2000) highlighted several limitations of this method, including its lack of a mechanistic basis, reliance on silt load measurements that cannot be unambiguously determined, dependence on the dataset used for derivation, and the accuracy of the model being influenced by the methods employed for measuring emissions.

These limitations underscore the need for further research and improvement in the road dust emission analysis methodology, considering the specific characteristics and conditions of the Indian region. Future studies should aim to address these uncertainties and refine the estimation process by incorporating more localized data, enhancing the mechanistic understanding of road dust dynamics, and adopting more accurate measurement techniques. Such advancements will contribute to a more comprehensive and reliable assessment of road dust emissions and facilitate the development of targeted mitigation strategies to improve air quality and public health.

Chapter 5: Conclusion and Future Work

In this study, the estimation of PM_{2.5} resuspended road dust emission was conducted at a district level across India, with a spatial resolution of $0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$, using the AP-42 methodology. The analysis revealed the dependencies of various parameters on emission and explored their seasonal variations. The contribution of different road types and vehicle categories to road dust emissions was investigated. The study identified highly polluted cities and states, and a comparison was made with previous research, demonstrating a strong correlation at the city and state levels, while also highlighting variations in absolute emission values. This indicates the necessity for updated and comprehensive studies to capture the evolving nature of road dust emissions accurately.

The findings revealed that PM_{2.5} resuspended road dust emission accounted for approximately 9% of the total PM_{2.5} emission, with nearly 58% originating from city roads. This emphasizes the significant role of cities in the overall emission landscape, attributed to higher vehicle kilometer traveled values within urban areas. The analysis indicated that heavy vehicles made a substantial contribution to emissions due to their higher dust generation potential compared to lighter vehicles. Spatial distribution analysis identified consistent emission hotspots across all road networks, suggesting specific locations with consistently higher emissions irrespective of road type.

The study identified Maharashtra as the most polluted state, primarily due to its high vehicle kilometer traveled. Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, and Tamil Nadu also exhibited significant road dust emissions. At the city level, Delhi emerged as the most polluted city, followed closely by Mumbai, Chennai, Kolkata, and Hyderabad, all displaying substantial road dust emissions. The analysis of monthly variation highlighted minimum emissions during July and August, and maximum emissions in December and January. This seasonal pattern is attributed to the impact of rainfall, which significantly affects road dust resuspension. Areas with a higher number of wet days, such as the northeastern region, experience more effective suppression of road dust emissions, while regions with fewer wet days, like Rajasthan and Punjab, exhibit relatively lower suppression.

The significant contribution of resuspended road dust to PM_{2.5} emissions underscores the need for targeted road dust management strategies to mitigate its adverse effects on air quality. The findings provide valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders to develop focused measures aimed at reducing PM_{2.5} levels and improving air quality in urban environments. However, the study also acknowledges its limitations, highlighting the necessity for further research and

methodological improvements. Future studies should address uncertainties by incorporating localized data, enhancing the mechanistic understanding of road dust dynamics, and employing more accurate measurement techniques. Advancements in these areas will contribute to a comprehensive and reliable assessment of road dust emissions, enabling the development of effective mitigation strategies to enhance air quality and public health.

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Appendix

Content in this section: Input data used in this study

Table 3 to 9,

Table 3: Silt Load Distribution across Road Types in Different Locations

Road→ City↓	Golden Quadrilateral	(NH + SH) Highway	City road	District road
Ahmedabad ^[A]	9.46	23.62	40	66
Bareilly ^[B]	8.05	10.02	15.76	30.58
Chennai ^[C]	1.96	8.33	14.64	18.22
Delhi ^[D]	0.9	2.2	2.6	4.8
Firozabad ^[B]	12.13	19.98	22.14	29.9
Ghaziabad ^[B]	14.51	17	32.55	61.96
Gorakhpur ^[E]	6.29	6.33	7.43	8.19
Howrah ^[F]	0.37	0.39	0.45	0.51
Jaipur ^[G]	4	8.2	20.5	32
Kolkata ^[F]	0.2	0.24	0.35	0.46
Lucknow ^[B]	4.48	5.76	7.81	10.16
Ludhiana ^[H]	0.64	1.16	4.05	4.05
Noida ^[B]	9.76	15.32	37.79	74.08
Rampur ^[I]	8.869	8.869	60.29	60.29
Surat ^[J]	1.5	2.4	2.6	2.6
Vellore ^[K]	6.14	9.86	21.03	22.03
Vijayawada ^[L]	1.2	2.9	8	12.8

A. Ahmedabad- Source Apportionment Study of Ahmedabad City, GEMI/SAS/243/2020/22

B. Bareilly- Micro plan of non – attainment city, UPPCB (2021)

C. Chennai-Dheeraj Alshetty VI , Shiva Nagendra S MI , Sudheer Kumar Kuppili 2018, “PM EMISSION RATES AND PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF ROAD DUST IN AND AROUND IIT MADRAS CAMPUS”, Indian International Conference on Air Quality Management (IICAQM-2018)

D. Delhi- Dheeraj Alshetty, S.M. Shiva Nagendra, 2022;” Impact of vehicular movement on road dust resuspension and spatiotemporal distribution of particulate matter during construction activities”, Atmospheric Pollution Research 13 (2022) 101256

E. Gorakhpur-CITY CLEAN AIR ACTION PLAN, UPPCB(2020)

- F. Howrah- PM10 and PM2.5 Source Apportionment Study and Development of Emission Inventory of Twin Cities Kolkata and Howrah of West Bengal, CSIR-NEERI (2019)
- G. Jaipur-Air Quality Assessment, Trend Analysis, Emission Inventory and Source Apportionment Study in Jaipur City; Rajasthan State Pollution Control Board, Jaipur (2020)
- H. Ludhiana-Source Apportionment Study to Prepare Action Plan to improve Air Quality of Ludhiana City, TERI (2020)
- I. Rampur- Assessment of Impacts Due to Transportation of Coal for Meja TPP of Meja Urja Nigam (P) Ltd. (2018)
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- L. Vijayawada- Source Apportionment, Emission Inventory and Carrying Capacity Studies for Vijayawada City, Andhra Pradesh Pollution Control Board (2022)

Table 4: Monthly wet days of each district (mean value taken for 2011-2021, IMD rainfall)

District Name	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Nicobars	5	2	4	8	19	19	20	21	20	19	14	8
North & Middle Andaman	15	10	11	15	17	16	17	17	17	2	19	18
South Andaman	14	10	11	15	18	16	17	17	18	20	19	17
Anantapur	0.6	0.6	1.1	3.9	7.4	8.9	10.8	12.2	12.6	11.1	6.4	2
Chittoor	1.3	0.8	1	3.1	6	9.6	12.5	13.3	13.9	13.4	11	5.2
East Godavari	0.7	0.6	2.3	6.2	8	16.3	22.4	21.5	20.3	13.4	4.8	1.1
Guntur	0.9	0.6	0.7	1.9	4.3	12.4	16.8	17.9	15.1	10.7	5.2	0.9
Krishna	0.9	0.6	0.6	1.5	4.3	13	18.4	18.5	15.1	11.2	4.9	0.7
Kurnool	0.8	0.5	1.1	3.8	6.7	10.6	14.3	14.9	13.7	10	5.2	1.1
Prakasam	1.3	0.7	0.9	3	5.3	11	14.7	15.5	14.4	11.6	8.1	2.5
Sri Potti Sriramulu Nell*	2.1	0.9	0.7	2	3.2	9.4	13.2	14.6	13.1	12.7	12	6.2
Srikakulam	0.5	0.8	1.5	3.9	5.3	9.2	13.2	14.3	13.7	7.9	2.3	1
Visakhapatnam	0.7	0.8	2.9	7.6	8.9	14.8	18.6	20	19.9	12	4.1	1.2
Vizianagaram	0.8	0.7	2.1	5.3	7.8	12.7	17.3	19.8	18.5	11.4	3.2	1.2
West Godavari	0.7	0.6	0.8	3.1	5.2	13.6	20.9	20	17.3	12.5	5.1	0.8
Y.S.R.	1	0.5	1	2.6	4.9	9.3	12	12.2	12.5	11.4	8.9	3.5
Anjaw	3.1	5.2	8.3	12.5	14.7	15.3	17.2	15.5	12.7	6.7	2.1	1.3
Changlang	4	6.3	10.9	16.5	19.2	21	23.5	20.4	16.3	8.3	2.6	1.5

East Kameng	4.3	6.5	11.9	19.1	24	26	28.3	24.2	20.7	9.7	3.3	2.4
East Siang	5.7	8	13.4	18.6	21.4	23.9	25.9	22.6	17.6	9.8	4.4	2.9
Kamle	5.7	8.1	15.2	20.6	23.5	25.4	28.6	24.5	20	10.4	4.3	3.5
Kra Daadi	4.9	7.3	14.5	19.1	22.5	25.7	27.7	23.5	19.6	10.7	4.4	3.5
Kurung Kumey	4.6	7	13.7	19.4	23.2	26	28.1	24.9	20.6	11	4.4	3.4
Lepa Rada	5.8	8.8	15	19.8	23.2	24.7	27.6	22.1	19.4	10.2	3.8	3.9
Lohit	3.8	6.5	10.2	14.8	17.1	18.6	20.4	18.4	15	8.1	2.8	1.6
Longding	5	6.6	13.4	19	23.5	25.5	27	24.6	18.2	10.6	3.3	1.5
Lower Dibang Valley	6.1	8.2	13.6	18.7	21	23	24.9	22.2	17.5	9.9	4.4	2.7
Lower Siang	5.7	7.9	14.3	19.6	22.7	24.8	27.2	22.8	19.4	9.8	4.3	3.5
Lower Subansiri	4.8	7.2	13.8	18.3	22.9	25.5	27.4	24.6	18.8	9.2	3.5	2.4
Namsai	5.1	7.2	12.7	18.6	20.7	23	25.3	22.1	17	8.9	3.1	1.7
Pakke Kessang	4.7	5.7	10.3	17.3	23.5	25	27.1	23.2	19.3	9.2	3	2.1
Papum Pare	4.9	6.8	11.9	17.3	22.9	25.1	27.3	23.7	18.5	8.8	3.2	2.2
Shi Yomi	6.9	9.3	17	21	22.3	24.2	26.4	22.4	20.5	12.7	5.3	4.4
Siang	6.1	8.5	15.3	20.2	22.4	24.1	27.1	22.3	19.5	10.7	4.7	3.9
Tawang	2.5	3.2	8.9	18.7	23.2	24.6	26.1	22.9	21	9.5	2.8	1.4
Tirap	5	6.5	13.4	18.3	21.9	24.5	27.4	24.2	18.7	10.2	3	1.6
Upper Dibang Valley	5.2	7.1	11.4	15	16.6	17	18.8	17.4	14.8	8.6	4	3
Upper Siang	6.3	8.8	15.1	18.8	20.3	21.5	23.3	20.4	18.8	11.4	5.3	4.3
Upper Subansiri	6.4	9	16.8	21.4	23.7	25.6	28.3	24.1	20.9	11.8	5	4.6
West Kameng	2.6	3.4	7.4	17.3	22.7	24.5	26.4	22.6	19.3	8.7	2.2	1.2
West Siang	6.4	9.1	16.5	21.5	23.8	25	28.5	23.5	19.5	11	4.8	4.3
Baksa	2.2	3.3	6.9	17.5	21.9	22.3	23.2	19.5	17.2	6.9	1.6	1.1
Barpeta	2	2.7	6.8	16.9	21.6	22.1	23	18.9	17	6.7	1.4	0.7
Biswanath	4.2	5.4	10.7	17.3	23.7	24.7	27	23.1	18.5	9.7	3	1.8
Bongaigaon	1.4	2.9	6.3	16.8	22	24.1	25.7	22.5	20	7.9	1.6	0.5
Cachar	2.5	2.5	7.6	16.8	23.6	25.6	27.7	26.2	20.7	11.4	2.1	1.5
Charaideo	4.8	6.4	13	19	23.5	25.4	26.7	24.3	17.7	10.1	3.1	1.5

Chirang	2.2	3.4	6.4	17.2	22.2	23.1	25.5	21.5	19.6	8.1	1.8	0.9
Darrang	3.2	2.9	6.9	16.5	22	23.3	25.2	22.1	18.4	9.2	2.8	1
Dhemaji	4.8	6.6	12.7	17.9	20.8	23.9	25.8	21.9	17.3	8.7	3.5	1.9
Dhubri	1.4	2	5.8	15.7	23.1	24.7	25.8	23.9	20.1	7.9	1.3	0.7
Dibrugarh	4.3	5.8	12.1	17.4	21.4	23.8	25.5	22.4	16.9	8.8	2.8	1.3
Dima Hasao	2.7	3.5	8.6	17.2	21.9	24.5	27	24.7	19.3	10.4	1.9	1.6
Goalpara	1.8	2.7	6.9	17.3	23.5	24.5	26.1	23.6	19.9	8.2	1.9	0.8
Golaghat	3.8	5	10.6	17.1	23.3	25.2	27.3	23.7	18.5	9.9	3.1	1.6
Hailakandi	2.1	2.5	6.9	16.5	23.5	25.9	28.4	27.1	21.1	11.5	2.1	1.4
Hojai	2.7	3.5	8.7	17.1	21.1	23.5	26	23.5	18.7	9.5	2.1	1.6
Jorhat	4.5	5	11.5	17.5	20.8	25	26.5	22.2	17.3	9.7	2.6	1.7
Kamrup	2.5	2.9	8.1	18.6	24.9	25.7	26.4	24.2	20.8	11.3	2.3	1.5
Kamrup Metropolitan	2.5	2.9	8.1	18.6	24.9	25.7	26.4	24.2	20.8	11.3	2.3	1.5
Karbi Anglong	2.9	3.8	9.2	16.5	21.1	23.4	25.8	23.3	18.3	9.9	2.3	1.7
Karimganj	2	2.5	6.7	16.6	23.5	25.5	28.4	27.1	21.2	11.4	2.1	1.5
Kokrajhar	1.4	2.5	6.2	16.2	21.9	24.1	25.6	22.7	19.8	8.1	1.5	0.8
Lakhimpur	4.9	6.4	12.5	18.4	22.5	25.2	27.7	23.5	18.2	9.2	3.2	1.8
Majuli	4.4	5.2	11.6	16.6	19.5	24.5	25.5	21.1	16.5	8.4	2.5	1.4
Morigaon	2.5	1.9	5.4	14	19.5	21.5	23.1	20.3	16.7	8.1	1.9	1
Nagaon	3.3	3.9	7.7	17.2	22.4	24.5	26	23.4	18.6	9.7	2.6	1.5
Nalbari	1.9	2.7	7.3	17.8	22.6	22.4	23	19.5	16.8	6.6	1.3	0.9
Sivasagar	5.2	5.8	12.9	18.2	22	25.1	27.3	23.5	18.5	9.7	3	1.8
Sonitpur	4	4.8	9.1	18.2	24	25.4	27.2	23.7	20.3	9.9	2.8	1.8
South Salmara Mancachar	1.4	2	5.8	15.7	23.1	24.7	25.8	23.9	20.1	7.9	1.3	0.7
Tinsukia	4.8	7.2	13.3	18.4	21.2	23.5	26	23	17.7	9.4	3.3	1.7
Udalguri	2.7	3.1	7	16.3	20.9	22.8	24.7	20.6	17.3	7.6	2.3	1.2
West Karbi Anglong	2.5	2.6	6.7	14.9	19.5	21.6	23.2	21.6	17.7	9.1	1.8	1.2
Araria	1.2	1.6	2.6	6.9	13.7	19.3	25.3	22.5	17.9	5.3	0.2	0.4
Arwal	2.6	3.1	2.5	4.2	5.8	11.1	19.6	21.4	14.8	5.1	0.1	0.8

Aurangabad	2.1	1.9	2.2	2.1	3.8	10.7	19.1	20.9	14.7	4.2	0.2	0.8
Banka	0.8	1.8	1.9	5.6	9.5	14.8	22.5	20.7	16.8	6.7	0.3	0.7
Begusarai	1.7	1.7	1.6	3.4	6.3	12.7	21.5	20.7	16.3	5.3	0.3	0.6
Bhagalpur	1.2	1.7	2.1	5.2	9.8	14.6	22.1	19.7	16	6.2	0.4	0.6
Bhojpur	2.5	2.6	3.2	3.6	5	11.1	19.4	20	14.6	4.7	0.8	1.4
Buxar	2.3	2.3	2.5	3.1	5.3	11.8	21.4	21.3	15.5	4.9	0.2	0.7
Darbhanga	1.6	1.6	2.1	4.8	9.1	15.6	22.5	20.4	16.1	4.3	0.1	0.5
Gaya	2.1	2.2	2.2	2.8	5.7	12.6	20.7	22.1	15.7	5.7	0.3	0.8
Gopalganj	1.7	1.9	1.8	2.9	6.6	12.3	19.4	18.4	13.8	3.4	0	0.5
Jamui	1.4	1.6	1.9	4.8	8.7	15.2	23.3	21.7	17	7.2	0.3	0.5
Jehanabad	2.4	2.5	2.7	4.7	7.5	15.1	21.5	22.6	17.1	5.6	0	0.7
Kaimur (bhabua)	2.3	2.3	2.2	2.1	3.5	11.1	19.6	20.4	13.9	3.6	0.2	0.8
Katihar	1.3	1.7	2.1	6.8	12.9	17.6	23.5	21.5	17.5	6.4	0.5	0.7
Khagaria	1.6	2	2	5.3	9	14.7	23	20.5	17	6	0.5	0.5
Kishanganj	1	1.4	3.5	9.3	18.5	23.4	26.5	24	19.5	6.2	0.6	0.5
Lakhisarai	1.5	1.6	1.5	3.5	6.3	12.1	20.8	19.7	15.6	4.9	0.4	0.7
Madhepura	1.7	1.8	2.8	6.3	12.3	16.9	24.9	23.5	18.2	5.8	0.5	0.5
Madhubani	1.8	1.7	2.3	5.9	10.9	16.9	23	20.8	15.9	4.3	0.1	0.4
Munger	1.5	1.9	2	4.5	8.2	14.3	22.5	21.5	17.1	6.5	0.4	0.5
Muzaffarpur	1.6	1.7	1.8	3.7	7.9	14.1	20.1	20	14.7	3.8	0.1	0.5
Nalanda	2.5	2.5	2.6	4.2	7.5	13.9	22.8	21.6	17.3	5.5	0.5	0.7
Nawada	1.7	1.9	2	2.7	5.5	11.9	21.7	21.6	15.5	5.3	0.3	0.7
Pashchim Champaran	1.9	2.4	2	3.6	8.3	13.8	20.1	18.2	14.4	3.5	0	0.4
Patna	2.2	2.3	3	4.1	7.6	15.2	23	22.1	17.6	5.9	0.4	0.6
Purba Champaran	1.9	2	1.6	3.5	7.8	11.9	18.3	16.7	12.9	2.6	0.1	0.4
Purnia	1.3	1.6	2.6	7.1	13.9	19.8	24.8	23.5	18.3	6.4	0.4	0.5
Rohtas	2.3	2.3	2.5	2.7	3.9	11.4	19.6	20.7	14.3	4.1	0.5	1.1
Saharsa	1.5	1.5	2.3	5.2	10.3	15.2	22.7	20.5	16.8	4.6	0.3	0.5
Samastipur	1.5	1.8	2.1	4.1	7.9	14.4	21.9	21.3	16.3	4.6	0.1	0.6

Saran	1.7	1.9	2.2	2.6	5.8	11.7	20	20.6	14.6	4.1	0.1	0.6
Sheikhpura	2.5	2.1	1.8	3.2	6.3	12.1	20.9	20.6	15.6	4.9	0.6	0.7
Sheohar	2	1.6	1.7	4.1	8.7	14.1	20	19.2	14.8	3	0.1	0.5
Sitamarhi	1.5	1.6	1.5	4.2	9.9	14.6	20.3	18.7	14.5	3.5	0.1	0.5
Siwan	1.9	1.8	1.8	2.8	6.5	11.6	19.1	19.3	13.2	3.3	0.1	0.4
Supaul	1.6	1.7	2.8	6.7	12.8	18.7	25	22.6	17.3	5.3	0.3	0.5
Vaishali	1.2	1.6	1.8	2.9	6.5	11.9	19.7	19.4	14.5	3.9	0	0.5
Chandigarh	4.1	5.1	5.6	5.4	5	10.5	18.1	19.7	10.5	1.6	1.3	2.1
Balod	1.2	2	3.3	4.4	5.1	15.4	22.9	22.8	18.1	6.8	0.8	0.8
Baloda Bazar	1.3	2.4	2.3	3.3	3.8	15.5	23.1	22.8	17.3	5.3	0.5	0.9
Balrampur	3	3.1	4	4.9	6.7	16.5	24.9	24.6	19.5	7.6	1	1.3
Bametara	1.7	2.2	2.5	3.9	4.7	15.2	21.7	21.2	15.8	4.7	0.5	0.9
Bastar	1.3	1.3	3	9.1	11.1	19	25.7	26.2	21.8	10.4	2.3	1.2
Bijapur	0.9	0.6	2.1	4.7	5.6	17.5	25	26.5	21.4	10.2	1.5	0.5
Bilaspur	2.4	2.9	3.6	4.6	5.2	16.7	24.9	25.3	18.6	6.4	0.6	1.1
Dakshin Bastar Dantewada	1.1	0.7	2.5	7.6	8.2	18.3	25.9	27.6	22.5	11.1	1.8	0.7
Dhamtari	0.7	1.8	2.6	4.4	4.3	14.8	22.7	22.5	17.9	6.4	0.5	0.5
Durg	1.4	2.1	2.9	4.5	5.4	16	23	22.4	17.5	6.1	0.7	1
Gariaband	0.7	1.4	2	4.2	3.7	14.8	22.7	22.9	18.2	6.6	0.4	0.5
Janjgir - Champa	1.5	2.4	2.5	3.2	3.8	15.1	23.8	24.2	18.4	6.3	0.7	1
Jashpur	2.2	2.6	3.6	5.4	7.3	18.7	25.7	25.3	20.6	8.6	0.8	1
Kabeerdham	1.8	2.4	3	4.1	4.6	15.8	22.4	22.5	16.7	5.1	0.5	0.9
Kondagaon	1	0.8	2.8	6.9	7.8	17.6	25.3	25.4	20.8	9.6	1.3	0.7
Korba	1.9	2.7	2.9	3.9	4.4	16.2	24.5	25.9	19.7	7	0.7	1.2
Koriya	2.4	2.6	3.7	2.8	4	15.4	25.3	25.6	18.8	6.4	0.8	1
Mahasamund	1	1.5	1.8	2.7	3.5	15.2	23.3	22.7	18.8	6.6	0.4	0.9
Mungeli	2.7	3.1	4.1	5.5	6.5	18.5	25.8	25.8	19	6.4	0.6	1.3
Narayanpur	1	0.8	2.2	5.4	4.8	16.8	26	26.7	22.3	9.1	1	0.6
Raigarh	1.8	2.3	2.8	3.8	5.2	15.9	24.2	24.5	18.9	7	0.8	1.3

Raipur	0.8	2.2	1.9	2.9	3.6	15.3	22.1	21.6	17.4	5.9	0.6	0.7
Rajnandgaon	1.3	2.1	3	3.1	4.1	15.1	23.2	23	17.6	6.1	0.6	0.7
Sukma	0.6	0.6	1.8	6.1	6.6	16.9	24.4	26.3	21.4	11.5	2.2	0.5
Surajpur	3.2	3.2	4.1	4.9	5.8	15.6	25.6	25.7	19.8	7.1	1.1	1.3
Surguja	2.8	3	4	6	6.4	17.8	26.1	26.5	21	8.2	1.1	1.1
Uttar Bastar Kanker	1	1.3	2.8	4.3	4.2	15.2	24.2	24.2	19.6	7.9	0.7	0.5
Dadra & Nagar Haveli	0.2	0	0.5	0	0.5	17.7	28.5	28.6	20.3	7.3	1	0.5
Daman	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.4	8.8	17.8	16.9	12.5	3.5	0.6	0.2
Diu	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.4	8.8	17.8	16.9	12.5	3.5	0.6	0.2
Central	3.1	2.8	3.8	2.6	4.9	8.2	15.9	16.3	8.1	1.1	0.6	1.3
East	3.1	2.8	3.8	2.6	4.9	8.2	15.9	16.3	8.1	1.1	0.6	1.3
New Delhi	3.4	2.8	4.5	3.5	6.5	8	17.6	17.8	8.9	1.2	1.1	1.3
North	3.4	2.8	4.5	3.5	6.5	8	17.6	17.8	8.9	1.2	1.1	1.3
North East	3.1	2.8	3.8	2.6	4.9	8.2	15.9	16.3	8.1	1.1	0.6	1.3
North West	3.4	2.8	4.5	3.5	6.5	8	17.6	17.8	8.9	1.2	1.1	1.3
Shahdara	3.1	2.8	3.8	2.6	4.9	8.2	15.9	16.3	8.1	1.1	0.6	1.3
South	2.7	2.4	3.6	2.7	5.2	7.3	13.9	16	7.8	1	0.6	1.2
South East	2.7	2.4	3.6	2.7	5.2	7.3	13.9	16	7.8	1	0.6	1.2
South West	3.4	2.8	4.5	3.5	6.5	8	17.6	17.8	8.9	1.2	1.1	1.3
West	3.4	2.8	4.5	3.5	6.5	8	17.6	17.8	8.9	1.2	1.1	1.3
North Goa	0.5	0.6	1.4	4.6	9	26.8	30.4	30.4	23.9	15.4	4.5	1.2
South Goa	0.5	0.5	0.7	2.9	7.1	27	30.6	29.9	23.1	14.2	3.7	1.1
Ahmadabad	0.3	0	0.4	0.5	0.5	7.8	16.1	16.1	11.9	2	0.3	0.5
Amreli	0.1	0	0.4	0.6	0.7	11.1	16.7	15.6	13.6	4.2	0.5	0.4
Anand	0.2	0	0.3	0.2	0.4	6.9	17.4	17.4	12.4	2	0.1	0.5
Aravalli	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.4	7.1	17.2	18	12.1	1.8	0.2	0.6
Banas Kantha	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.5	5.1	12.2	13.5	10.6	1.6	0.4	0.3
Bharuch	0.1	0	0.2	0.1	0.3	9.8	19.5	18.4	14.6	2.9	0.4	0.5
Bhavnagar	0.1	0	0.2	0.4	0.4	8.1	15.2	14.5	11.5	2.8	0.3	0.5

Botad	0.1	0	0.3	0.7	0.7	8.4	14.4	13.3	10.8	2.2	0.4	0.2
Chota Udaipur	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.2	0.4	10.6	22.2	22.7	15.6	3.4	0.5	0.7
Devbhumi Dwarka	0.2	0.1	0.1	0	0.1	5.7	13.1	12.4	9.6	1.9	0.4	0.4
Dohad	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.5	7.7	18	18.5	13.4	2.6	0.2	0.5
Gandhinagar	0.3	0.2	0.5	0.5	0.4	7.3	17.1	17.1	12.6	2	0.3	0.6
Gir Somnath	0.1	0.1	0.4	0.2	0.5	10.9	19.7	18.7	13.5	3.9	0.7	0.6
Jamnagar	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.4	6.8	14	12.6	10.3	1.9	0.5	0.2
Junagadh	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.4	8.8	17.8	16.9	12.5	3.5	0.6	0.2
Kachchh	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.4	4.3	10.6	10.6	8.8	1.7	0.5	0.2
Kheda	0.2	0	0.3	0.3	0.3	7.3	16.9	16.7	11.7	1.7	0.1	0.6
Mahesana	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.4	6.3	14.7	15.4	11.6	1.7	0.3	0.4
Mahisagar	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.5	0.3	7.2	18.2	18.9	13.2	2.4	0.1	0.5
Morbi	0	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.5	8.2	15.7	14.1	11.2	2.5	0.6	0.2
Narmada	0.3	0	0.4	0.1	0.4	13.1	24.5	24.3	17.2	3.9	0.7	0.5
Navsari	0.2	0	0.3	0.1	0.2	14.5	25.4	24.5	17.4	4.7	0.7	0.6
Panch Mahals	0.2	0	0.2	0.3	0.3	7.7	18.2	18.8	13.9	2.4	0.3	0.5
Patan	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.4	0.3	5.4	12.6	13.2	10.5	1.8	0.3	0.2
Porbandar	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	7.3	16.7	15.7	10.9	2.6	0.2	0.4
Rajkot	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.4	0.6	9.7	16.6	14.6	12.6	3.4	0.5	0.2
Sabar Kantha	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.7	0.8	7.7	16.9	17	12.5	1.9	0.4	0.4
Surat	0.2	0	0.4	0.2	0.3	12.9	23.4	21.5	16.1	3.7	0.7	0.5
Surendranagar	0.1	0	0.2	0.5	0.4	8.4	14.3	13.7	11.2	2.2	0.3	0.3
Tapi	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.2	0.3	12.5	24.3	23.6	16.6	4.5	1	0.5
The Dangs	0.4	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.6	14	26	27	18.9	7.1	1.2	0.6
Vadodara	0.2	0	0.2	0.2	0.3	8.5	18.8	18.6	13.6	2.7	0.3	0.7
Valsad	0.2	0.1	0.5	0.2	0.5	17	27.9	27.7	19.4	7.1	0.8	0.6
Ambala	3.6	4.5	4.9	4.3	5	8.7	17.6	17.9	9.2	1.4	0.9	2
Bhiwani	2.2	2.6	3.8	2.9	4.3	7.1	12.9	11.5	6.9	1.3	0.9	0.6
Charki Dadri	2	2.5	3.4	2.7	3.9	6.7	13	12.2	6.9	1.4	0.6	0.5

Faridabad	2.9	2.1	3.1	1.8	4	6	13.7	14.3	8.1	0.9	0.4	0.9
Fatehabad	2	2.3	3.5	2	2.4	6	9.5	8.6	5.2	0.9	0.7	0.8
Gurugram	3	2.1	3.5	3.1	4	7	14.2	15	7.8	1.1	0.6	0.8
Hisar	2.4	2.7	4.3	2.6	4	7.2	11.9	11.1	6.8	1	1.1	0.8
Jhajjar	2.8	2.4	3.6	2.7	4.1	6	13.4	13.6	6.9	1.1	0.5	0.6
Jind	2.5	2.8	3.3	2.3	3.2	6.3	11.1	12	5.7	0.9	0.9	0.7
Kaithal	3	3.5	4	2.9	3.8	7.7	13.4	13.5	6.7	1	0.9	1.5
Karnal	3.2	3.7	4.2	3.1	4.4	7.7	14.7	14.7	7.2	1.3	0.9	1.3
Kurukshetra	3	3.5	3.9	3.2	4	7.1	12.8	13.5	6.4	0.9	0.6	1.5
Mahendragarh	1.6	1.7	3	2.1	3.6	7.5	13.5	12.1	7	1.3	0.2	0.4
Nuh	2.4	1.5	2.9	2.3	4	6.2	13.7	15.3	7.9	1	0.2	0.5
Palwal	2.4	1.7	3.1	2.1	3.2	5.5	13.1	13.7	7.2	0.8	0.3	0.8
Panchkula	4.4	5.2	5.6	5	5.4	11.5	20	20.5	10.3	2	1.1	2.2
Panipat	2.9	2.7	3.9	2.5	5.2	7.5	14.6	14.3	7.1	1.2	0.5	1.1
Rewari	2.4	1.9	4.1	2.5	4	6.5	13.3	13.4	7.4	1.2	0.4	0.4
Rohtak	2.5	2.5	3.4	2.8	3.9	6.4	12.5	12.3	7	1.2	0.8	0.7
Sirsa	1.9	2.1	3.2	2.6	2.6	5.7	8.2	8	5.4	0.8	0.8	0.6
Sonipat	2.9	2.9	3.6	2.8	4.6	7.3	13.9	14.7	7.1	0.9	0.6	1
Yamunanagar	3.5	4.4	4.6	4	4.8	9.8	18.4	18.4	9	1.6	1.1	1.8
Bilaspur	5.4	6.9	7.9	7.6	7.5	13.8	22.6	22.8	12.1	1.8	1.9	2.5
Chamba	8.7	9.6	11.5	11.3	11.9	14.3	22.8	23.2	13.6	4.2	3.2	3.3
Hamirpur	5.8	6.8	7.4	6.7	7.1	13	23	23.3	13	2.5	1.6	2.5
Kangra	6.8	8.4	9.7	8.8	8.9	13.4	21.9	22.6	12.7	3.7	2.5	2.8
Kinnaur	9.1	9.8	11.2	11.2	11.5	12.3	20.8	19.5	12.5	3.1	3.3	4
Kullu	8.6	9.6	12.1	11.9	12.2	15.5	23.2	22.8	12.8	3.9	3.7	4
Lahul & Spiti	9.5	10.3	12	11.2	12.2	13.5	21.2	20.7	12.3	4.2	4	4.4
Mandi	6.5	7.5	9.7	9.3	10.4	15.1	24.1	24.5	13.4	2.9	2.5	2.8
Shimla	8	8.7	11.1	10.8	11.7	14.5	22.6	21.3	13	3	3	3.7
Sirmaur	4.8	6.4	6.7	6.6	7.9	14.5	23.9	23.5	13.2	2.6	1.5	2.5

Solan	6.3	7	8.8	8.6	9.3	15.5	23.7	23.4	12.3	2.7	2.5	3.2
Una	5.3	6.6	6.7	6.5	6.3	11.1	19.4	20.8	10.7	2.8	1.3	2.1
Anantnag	11.2	12.8	14.3	15.8	14.8	13.9	16.1	14.7	10	5.7	5.1	4.5
Badgam	10.4	11.5	14.1	16	14.5	14.4	14.7	13.4	8.7	5.9	5.2	4.5
Bandipore	10.4	11.7	13.9	15.1	13.7	12.6	13.9	13.3	8.7	5.9	5	4.3
Baramula	11.3	12	14.7	16.3	15.6	15.9	15.2	14.6	9.7	6.7	5.5	4.7
Doda	9.6	10.4	13	14	14	14.8	20.6	20.7	11.6	4.7	3.9	4.1
Ganderbal	10.2	11.3	13.2	14.9	13	11.6	14	12.8	8.6	5.3	5	4.1
Jammu	5.9	8.1	9.5	9.4	7.7	11.4	21.1	21.1	11.2	4.1	2.8	2.5
Kathua	7.7	8.8	10.8	10.5	10.3	13.6	21.5	23.1	11.6	4.2	2.7	3.1
Kishtwar	10.5	11.7	13.8	14.8	14.3	15.1	20.6	20.3	12.7	5.5	4.7	4.3
Kulgam	9.7	11.4	12.8	14.3	12.1	12.4	15.5	14.8	8.8	4.5	4.3	3.9
Kupwara	10.8	11.8	13.9	15.3	13.8	13.6	13.7	12.9	8	6.3	5.1	4.4
Mirpur	8	10.4	12.4	13.5	12.1	14.4	20.9	20.4	12.1	5.3	4.2	3.7
Muzaffarabad	11.1	11.9	14.5	16	15.2	15.3	14.8	14	9.1	6.6	5.3	4.7
Pulwama	11.4	12.7	14.1	15.6	14.6	13.6	16	14.4	10.2	6.2	5.2	4.4
Punch	10.2	11.6	14.9	16.2	16	16.6	16.8	15.6	11.1	6.4	5.3	4.6
Rajouri	8.2	10.2	12	13.5	11.3	13.8	20.9	21	11.7	5.1	4.1	3.3
Ramban	9.8	11.5	14.6	14.9	14.5	15.2	19	18.7	9.7	5.1	4.3	4.3
Reasi	9.3	10.6	12.6	13.6	12.1	13.9	20	20.2	10.9	5.1	4	3.8
Samba	5.7	7.6	8.4	7.6	6.9	11.1	19.7	20.3	10.5	3.8	2.1	2.4
Shupiyan	10.8	11.8	13.4	14.8	12.6	12.3	13.6	13	7.8	4.5	4.7	4.2
Srinagar	10.2	11.3	13.2	14.9	13	11.6	14	12.8	8.6	5.3	5	4.1
Udhampur	9.6	10.7	13.6	13.7	13.6	15.6	22.2	23	11.7	5.2	4	4.1
Bokaro	2.1	2.3	4.3	6.3	11.3	17.6	24.2	24.3	18.2	8.9	1	0.9
Chatra	2.5	2.5	2.6	3.8	7.2	15.2	22.8	23	18.6	7.2	0.6	0.9
Deoghar	1.6	2.1	2.3	6	10.2	16.8	23.6	22.2	17.4	7.4	0.5	0.5
Dhanbad	1.9	1.9	3	5.4	10.1	16.8	23.1	22.6	17.3	8.5	0.8	0.8
Dumka	1.8	1.9	2.9	7.2	12.3	17.3	24	22.3	17.4	8.2	0.8	0.6

Garhwa	2.6	3.1	3.4	3.1	4.7	13.4	21.9	22.4	16.3	5.9	0.7	1.3
Giridih	1.5	1.6	2.4	4.8	8.5	14.9	22.5	21.3	16.7	7.1	0.5	0.5
Godda	1.3	2	2.1	7.4	12.3	17.2	24.2	22	17.5	7.7	0.5	0.7
Gumla	3.1	3.3	4.4	6.1	9.3	18	26	26.1	19.9	9.5	1	1.2
Hazaribagh	1.8	2	3	4.7	8.7	15.9	22.2	23	18.1	7.4	0.6	0.8
Jamtara	2	2.1	3.4	6	11.8	18.7	24.9	23.7	18.3	8.3	0.8	0.8
Khunti	2.5	2.9	3.9	7.1	11	16.5	22.5	23.2	19.1	8.5	1.1	1.2
Kodarma	1.6	2	2.2	4.1	8.1	14.1	22.4	22.1	17.7	6.9	0.5	0.7
Latehar	2.6	2.6	2.9	4	6.9	15.3	22.2	21.5	16.7	7.2	0.8	1
Lohardaga	2.8	2.7	3.3	4.6	8.1	16.2	24	23.5	17.6	7.7	1	1.2
Pakur	1.8	1.7	2.7	7.7	12.7	16.9	23.7	22.1	17.4	7.6	0.7	0.6
Palamu	2.6	2.7	2.8	3	4.6	13.2	21.2	21.7	16.8	6.4	0.6	1.2
Pashchimi Singhbhum	2	2.5	3.6	7.6	12.8	17.4	22.8	24.3	19.2	8.7	1	1.5
Purbi Singhbhum	1.9	2.8	4.1	9	13.8	18.2	24.9	24.7	19.6	9.9	1.7	1.9
Ramgarh	1.9	2.2	3.8	5	8.5	15.1	21.7	21.5	15.8	7.3	0.8	0.8
Ranchi	2.3	2.9	4	6.3	10.3	16.9	24	23.9	18.9	8.6	1	1.1
Sahibganj	1.2	1.8	1.7	6.3	11.5	15.7	23	20.5	17.5	6.7	0.4	0.8
Saraikela-kharsawan	2.2	2.6	3.5	7.9	13.9	17.7	23.7	23.8	19.8	10	1.1	1.3
Simdega	2.6	2.8	3.6	6.2	9.6	18.1	25.7	26.1	20.2	8.9	0.9	1.1
Bagalkote	0.3	0.6	1.5	4.8	7.8	12.6	17.1	15.7	14.2	10.3	2.2	0.7
Ballari	0.4	0.6	1.6	5.3	9.3	11.4	15.1	16.1	14.1	10.4	3.9	1.1
Bangalore	0.7	0.9	2	6.6	12.8	11.1	13.7	15.6	13.8	13.8	8.4	3.7
Belagavi	0.3	0.6	2	5.4	8.9	17.6	23.6	21.5	17.5	11.7	2.9	1
Bengaluru Rural	0.6	1	2.2	7.2	12.8	13.5	16.7	18.4	15.8	14	8.2	3.5
Bidar	0.8	1	2.7	5.5	6.6	16.4	20	20.1	16.5	8.8	2.1	0.4
Chamarajanagara	0.9	0.8	2.8	9.2	13.7	13.5	14.3	16.4	14.9	15.4	9.8	4.2
Chikkaballapura	0.7	1	1.8	5.5	9.8	11.6	14.2	14.4	14	12.9	8.3	3
Chikkamagaluru	0.6	1.1	2.6	8.8	13.6	20.5	26.1	25.4	19.1	14.9	6.7	2.4
Chitradurga	0.5	0.7	1.2	5.3	9.3	10.4	13.6	14.2	12	10.5	4.8	1.5

Dakshina Kannada	1	1.2	3.1	10.5	16.5	28.1	30.4	29.8	24.6	19.8	9.5	3.4
Davanagere	0.4	0.7	1.5	5.9	10.4	14.3	20.1	20.4	16.1	11.8	4.1	1.5
Dharwad	0.4	0.7	2.2	8	11.6	19	23.9	23	18.3	11.9	3.9	1
Gadag	0.4	0.6	1.9	6.7	10.3	13.9	19.3	19.9	16.6	11.1	3	1
Hassan	0.6	1.1	2.4	9.4	14.8	17.9	21.1	20.6	16.8	15.4	7	2.7
Haveri	0.3	0.5	1.6	6.1	10.6	17.5	24.6	23.8	18.2	12.3	3.3	1
Kalaburagi	0.3	0.7	2.2	6	8.4	15.2	18.7	19.2	17.1	9.4	2.4	0.6
Kodagu	0.7	1.6	3.3	12.3	16.9	25.4	28	26.6	21.9	17.4	8.1	3.3
Kolar	1.1	0.7	1.8	5.6	10.4	9.7	12.1	12.8	13.3	14.1	9	3.6
Koppal	0.4	0.5	1.3	4.6	8.6	11	14.5	16.3	14.2	9.6	2.9	0.8
Mandya	0.7	1.1	2.6	9	15	15.4	18.6	20.4	16.8	15.8	7.8	3
Mysuru	0.6	1.2	2.9	9.9	14.1	18.2	21.1	19.6	16.3	14.9	7.7	2.8
Raichur	0.5	0.5	0.9	3.9	7.1	11.9	15.6	16.2	15.7	8.7	2.7	0.5
Ramanagara	0.7	0.7	2.1	7.6	13.5	11.4	14.1	17	14.4	14.6	7.8	3.3
Shivamogga	0.7	0.8	1.8	6.3	10.1	22.5	27.9	27.1	20.6	13.8	5.1	1.7
Tumakuru	0.5	0.8	1.7	6.3	11	11.5	14	15.7	13.9	13.4	6.8	2.3
Udupi	0.9	0.9	2	8	13.4	28	30.8	30.4	24.5	18.4	7.9	2.7
Uttara Kannada	0.6	0.7	1.7	5.5	10.1	24.5	29.3	28.8	21.7	14.2	4.3	1.1
Vijayapura	0.3	0.6	1.8	5.6	8.3	13.7	16.3	16.1	15.3	10	2.2	0.7
Yadgir	0.3	0.5	1.1	4.1	6.2	13.4	17.4	17.4	15.9	8.5	2	0.4
Alappuzha	3.3	3.3	9.1	16.5	20.4	27	27.2	24.8	22.2	21.9	16.7	7.6
Ernakulam	2.2	2.9	7.9	15	19.9	27.9	28.4	27.5	23.3	22.2	14.9	6.3
Idukki	3.1	2.9	7.4	12.7	16.1	19.8	20.4	21.2	18.6	19.9	15.9	8.4
Kannur	1.1	1.3	3.2	10.8	16.8	28.2	29.9	28.7	23	18.9	10.1	3.5
Kasaragod	1.3	1.4	3.7	11.6	17	28.7	30.6	29.8	24.5	20.4	10.2	4.3
Kollam	2.4	2.4	6.9	11.9	15	23.5	23.4	20.3	18.2	18	15.9	7.1
Kottayam	3.4	3.4	9.3	17.5	20.9	28.2	28	27.1	23.5	23.2	17.9	7.4
Kozhikode	1.4	1.3	5	13.8	17.3	27.5	29.1	28.5	22.5	19.8	11.6	4.3
Malappuram	1.1	1.3	3	9.1	15.3	26.3	27.6	26	20.7	19.9	11.6	4.4

Palakkad	0.8	1.2	3.5	7.7	12.4	24.5	26.5	24.9	20	17.3	10.5	4.1
Pathanamthitta	3.4	3.5	8.9	13.8	15.1	19.7	18.9	18.4	16.5	19	17.9	9.7
Thiruvananthapuram	3.4	3.3	8.7	15.5	18.7	24.3	21.6	20	19.1	20.5	19	9.9
Thrissur	1.2	1.5	4.6	10.2	16.8	27.2	28	25.1	21.4	19.6	11.3	3.7
Wayanad	1.5	1.6	6	15.3	18.5	24.9	27.5	26.3	20.6	18.9	11.8	4.8
Kargil	9.3	10.4	11.2	11.3	10.9	11.4	17.4	17.3	10.9	4.3	3.6	3.6
Leh	7.5	8.2	8	8.8	7.2	7.4	9.8	10.1	6.5	3.1	2.6	2.7
Lakshadweep	2	1	1	3	10	18	17	15	14	13	9	5
Agar Malwa	1	0.8	1	0.7	1.2	11.7	19.1	20.7	12.3	1.9	0.2	0.7
Alirajpur	0.5	0.1	0.7	0.5	0.6	10.6	21.3	21.9	15.3	3.8	0.5	0.7
Anuppur	3	2.9	4.4	4.9	6.3	17.2	25.3	25	18.1	6.1	0.6	1.1
Ashoknagar	1.8	1.8	1.7	0.9	1.6	12.6	20.9	20.8	12.5	2	0.3	0.6
Balaghat	2.3	2.9	4.1	3.2	3.6	16.1	24.7	25.2	18	5.8	0.9	1.1
Barwani	0.5	0.5	1	0.5	0.7	11.6	20.6	19.6	15.9	4.7	0.5	0.7
Betul	2	2	2.5	1.3	1.7	15.8	22.6	22.7	16.7	5.9	0.7	0.8
Bhind	2.1	1.8	1.6	1.3	2.7	7.9	17.4	18.6	9.9	1.8	0.3	0.8
Bhopal	1.7	1.5	2.3	1.2	2.4	15.1	22	23.4	14.1	3.4	0.3	0.9
Burhanpur	0.8	0.9	1.6	0.7	0.9	13.4	21.4	21.2	16	4.9	0.7	0.6
Chhatarpur	2.7	2.2	2.2	1.3	2.2	11.6	20.6	20.7	12.9	1.9	0.3	0.7
Chhindwara	2.5	2.6	3.6	2.3	3	16.9	24.2	24	17.7	5.3	0.6	1
Damoh	2.4	1.8	2	1.4	1.7	14.2	22.1	22.6	15.1	3.1	0.5	0.7
Datia	1.8	2	1.6	1	2.7	8.3	17.5	16.9	10	1.7	0.2	0.7
Dewas	0.9	1	1.1	0.3	0.9	13.5	20.2	21.2	14.8	3.1	0.2	0.6
Dhar	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.5	0.6	11	20.3	20.2	15.5	4.1	0.4	0.7
Dindori	3	3.2	4.4	5.1	6.6	18.5	25.7	26	19.2	6.1	0.6	1.3
East Nimar	0.9	1.2	1.4	0.6	0.7	13.1	21.4	21.6	15	4.2	0.4	0.8
Guna	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.2	1.8	12.6	21.8	22.4	12.9	2.3	0.3	0.8
Gwalior	2.4	2	2.3	2.1	4.2	10	19.6	19.9	11.1	1.8	0.5	0.9
Harda	1.5	1.9	1.8	0.8	1.2	14.6	22.1	23.1	16.2	4.5	0.5	0.8

Hoshangabad	2.5	2	2.4	1.3	2.1	15.4	23.5	25.1	17	4.5	0.6	0.9
Indore	0.8	0.8	0.9	0.6	1.1	12.9	20.3	19.9	15.1	4.3	0.3	0.8
Jabalpur	2.9	2.4	3.5	2.1	2.6	15	23.6	23.6	16.7	3.6	0.4	1
Jhabua	0.6	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.6	9.5	19.3	20	14.7	3.5	0.4	0.7
Katni	2.8	2.2	2.9	1.9	2.4	14.7	23.3	23.4	15.6	3.3	0.4	0.7
Mandla	3.1	3.2	4.7	3.7	4.7	17.4	26	25.9	18.9	5.8	0.8	1.2
Mandsaur	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.5	1.4	11	19.4	20.2	12.5	2.2	0.3	0.6
Morena	2.1	1.6	2.3	1.4	3.1	8.5	16.8	18.3	10.1	1.4	0.4	0.9
Narsimhapur	2.5	2	2.6	1.7	2.3	14.5	21.9	22.7	15.8	3.3	0.3	0.9
Neemuch	0.9	0.6	0.8	0.6	1.5	10.1	18.2	19.7	12.4	1.9	0.4	0.6
Niwari	1.9	2	2	1.2	2.5	10.2	20.1	19.7	10	1.8	0.4	0.7
Panna	2.5	2	2.2	1.2	2	13	21.8	21.6	13.7	2.4	0.4	0.6
Raisen	1.9	1.4	1.9	1.1	2.2	15.1	22.2	23.4	15.1	3.3	0.3	0.8
Rajgarh	1.4	1.2	1.5	0.9	1.6	13.3	21.4	21.6	13.1	2.6	0.3	0.8
Ratlam	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.5	1.5	10.9	19.4	20.9	14.5	3.4	0.4	0.9
Rewa	2.3	1.9	2.6	1.6	2.6	10.7	21.8	20.1	13.1	3.1	0.2	0.6
Sagar	2.2	1.8	2	1.6	1.9	14.7	21.9	22.6	14.4	2.7	0.3	0.8
Satna	2.4	2.3	2.7	1.6	2.5	13.2	22.5	21.9	13.5	2.8	0.4	0.7
Sehore	1.3	1.2	1.7	0.8	1.9	14.3	21	23.1	14.1	3.1	0.2	0.8
Seoni	2.6	2.6	3.5	2.6	2.6	15.9	24.7	24.6	17.1	4.7	0.5	0.9
Shahdol	2.2	2.5	3.5	2.6	3.4	15.1	24.8	24.2	17.1	5.1	0.4	0.8
Shajapur	1	0.7	1.4	0.7	1.6	13.5	20.7	21.3	13.5	2.6	0.3	0.8
Sheopur	2	1.2	1.8	1.2	2.7	10.6	19.8	21.3	11.7	1.6	0.5	1.1
Shivpuri	2.1	2	1.9	1.5	2.8	10.9	20.2	19.8	11.1	1.8	0.4	0.8
Sidhi	2.2	2.4	3	1.8	2.9	13.5	24	22.8	15.9	4.7	0.4	0.8
Singrauli	2.7	2.6	3.4	2	4.4	14	23.4	22.3	16.6	4.6	0.7	1.3
Tikamgarh	2.3	2.4	2.4	1.5	2.6	11.4	20.8	20.8	11.9	2	0.4	1.1
Ujjain	0.9	0.7	0.8	0.8	1.7	11.5	18.4	19.4	12.6	2.7	0.4	0.9
Umari	2.7	2.8	3.6	2.7	3.6	16.1	25.1	25.1	18.3	4.9	0.4	1

Vidisha	1.7	1.6	2	0.9	1.6	15.1	22	23	14.3	2.8	0.3	0.7
West Nimar	0.6	0.7	1.3	0.4	0.7	11.4	20.9	19.6	15.2	4.4	0.3	0.6
Ahmadnagar	0.5	0.3	2.1	1.6	2.8	13.1	16.2	13.6	14.1	8.6	2.1	0.8
Akola	0.8	1.2	2.4	1	1.4	15.2	21.2	17.9	15.3	5.3	0.6	0.4
Amravati	1	1.3	2.7	1.1	1.6	16.3	22	20.8	17.3	5.9	0.7	0.5
Aurangabad	0.7	0.7	2.4	1.3	2	13.6	18.8	15.6	14.9	7.5	1.6	0.8
Bhandara	1.2	1.8	3.2	2.1	2.3	14.9	23.3	23.5	16.6	4.7	0.7	0.6
Bid	0.5	0.8	2.4	3.1	2.6	15.1	16.7	16	14.6	8.7	1.8	0.5
Buldana	0.6	0.9	2.6	0.8	1.4	14.4	20.1	17.8	15.2	6.2	1	0.4
Chandrapur	1.1	1.2	2.9	2.5	2.7	15	22.8	22.1	17	5.5	0.7	0.5
Dhule	0.6	0.7	1.9	0.7	1	11.6	19.9	16.9	14.2	5.3	1.1	0.9
Gadchiroli	0.8	0.8	2.2	2.3	2.7	16.2	24.9	25.2	20.2	7.7	1.1	0.5
Gondiya	1.3	1.8	2.9	2	2.6	14.5	23.3	23.7	17.1	5.2	0.6	0.7
Hingoli	1	1.3	3.3	2.3	2	16.4	21.3	19	15.9	6.4	0.7	0.2
Jalgaon	0.6	0.8	2.2	0.7	1.2	12	20.6	18.5	15.2	5.3	1.1	0.7
Jalna	0.4	0.9	2.6	1.7	1.6	14.9	18.2	16	14.9	7.6	1.4	0.4
Kolhapur	0.3	0.4	1.8	4.1	7	20.5	26.6	25.5	18.9	11.5	2.7	1
Latur	0.7	1.3	2.8	4.3	3.8	16.5	18.5	19.8	15.3	8.3	2.2	0.6
Mumbai	0.2	0.2	0.7	0.4	1.2	20.1	29.4	29.6	21.6	8.7	1.5	0.7
Mumbai Suburban	0.2	0.2	0.7	0.4	1.2	20.1	29.4	29.6	21.6	8.7	1.5	0.7
Nagpur	1.2	1.7	3.4	1.9	2.5	15.2	22.2	21.2	16.1	4.8	0.8	0.6
Nanded	0.7	1	2.5	3	3	15.4	19.1	18.9	14.8	6.4	1.3	0.3
Nandurbar	0.6	0.5	1.2	0.5	0.5	11.4	21.6	20	15.6	4.9	1	0.6
Nashik	0.6	0.5	2	1.1	2	13.8	21.8	20.9	16.5	8.2	1.6	0.9
Osmanabad	0.4	0.7	2.2	4.8	4.5	15.3	18.3	18.1	15.8	9.7	2.1	0.7
Palghar	0.2	0.2	0.7	0.4	1.2	20.1	29.4	29.6	21.6	8.7	1.5	0.7
Parbhani	0.7	1.4	2.5	2.7	2.7	15.3	18.9	17.1	15.4	6.9	1.3	0.4
Pune	0.3	0.2	1.8	1.7	3.5	15.5	21.5	19.6	16.1	10.2	2.3	0.8
Raigarh	0.2	0.2	1.2	1.1	3	23.1	30.3	30.1	23.1	11.9	2.1	1.1

Ratnagiri	0.2	0.3	1.2	3	5	26.1	30.5	30.5	24.3	13.2	2.8	0.9
Sangli	0.3	0.4	1.4	4.3	7.1	15.2	20.4	19.5	15.7	10.9	2.7	0.7
Satara	0.3	0.3	1.8	3.4	5.7	16.8	21.7	20.2	16.9	10.9	3.3	1
Sindhudurg	0.3	0.5	1.2	2.3	6	26.4	30.4	30.3	23.8	14	3.3	1.2
Solapur	0.3	0.4	1.8	4.2	5.2	13.4	15.1	15.3	14.9	10	2.7	0.8
Thane	0.3	0.4	1.3	0.7	2.5	20.1	29.2	29.4	21.3	9	2.2	1
Wardha	1	1.4	3.4	1.9	2.6	16.3	22.6	20.9	16.5	5.7	0.6	0.4
Washim	0.9	1.2	3.3	1.7	1.9	17.3	22.2	18.9	16	6.4	0.7	0.2
Yavatmal	0.8	1.2	3.6	2.3	2.4	16.8	22	20.2	16.2	5.8	0.7	0.3
Bishnupur	2.5	2.5	6.4	16.2	22.2	23.1	26.5	24.3	17.5	10.6	1.6	1.7
Chandel	1.7	2.1	5.2	12.2	17.4	16.7	20.2	16.9	12.8	8.7	1.5	1.5
Churachandpur	2.4	2.4	6.7	16.7	22.9	24.6	27.2	25.8	18.2	11	1.8	1.7
Imphal East	2.6	3.2	7.9	17	22.4	23.3	26.9	23.2	17.9	11	1.6	1.5
Imphal West	2.6	3.2	7.9	17	22.4	23.3	26.9	23.2	17.9	11	1.6	1.5
Jiribam	2.6	2.5	7.5	17.5	24.5	26.3	28	27.1	21	12.5	2.1	1.8
Kakching	2.5	2.4	5.7	15.7	20.7	21.4	25.2	21.9	16	10	1.5	1.5
Kamjong	1.9	2.7	6.2	13.9	17.7	18.7	21.9	19.6	16.5	10.9	1.8	1.5
Kangpokpi	2.8	3.7	8	17.5	21.5	23.4	26.8	24.9	19.2	11.4	2	1.7
Noney	2.7	2.8	6.9	15.5	19.8	20.5	22.9	20.5	14.2	8.9	1.5	1.5
Pherzawl	2.6	2.5	7.5	17.5	24.5	26.3	28	27.1	21	12.5	2.1	1.8
Senapati	2.8	3.7	8.2	17.1	20.3	23.2	26.1	23.2	20.3	11.8	2.1	1.6
Tamenglong	2.8	3.7	8.5	18.2	22.8	24.8	28.3	25.9	19.8	11.6	2	1.7
Tengnoupal	1.5	2.1	5.1	12	15.9	16	18.7	16.7	12.7	8.6	1.5	1.5
Thoubal	1.5	2.1	5.1	12	15.9	16	18.7	16.7	12.7	8.6	1.5	1.5
Ukhrul	2.7	3.6	8.2	16.2	20	23	25.4	21.5	18.9	11.5	2.1	1.6
East Garo Hills	1.9	2.9	7.7	18.5	25.3	25.9	27.4	25	21.6	8.9	2	1.1
East Jaintia Hills	2.5	2.9	7.8	17.7	23.4	25.6	27.6	26	21.1	11.3	2.1	1.7
East Khasi Hills	3	3.3	8.9	20.7	27.4	28	29.4	28.1	24.6	15.5	3	1.8
North Garo Hills	1.6	2.4	6.6	16.7	23.9	25.1	26.5	25.4	21.2	8.6	1.9	0.7

Ribhoi	2.9	2.4	7.4	16.7	23.5	25.1	26.6	24.4	21.5	13.2	2.5	1.6
South Garo Hills	1.6	2.8	7.7	19.2	25.8	26.6	28.3	25.6	22.8	10.5	2.1	1.1
South West Garo Hills	0.9	1.8	4.9	13.8	23	23.8	23.8	23.3	19.8	7.3	1.2	0.6
South West Khasi Hills	2.2	3.2	8.4	21	27.6	28.1	29.5	27.6	23.4	12.8	2.5	1.4
West Garo Hills	1.3	2.1	5.8	15.5	23.8	24.6	25.8	24.5	20.4	8	1.4	0.7
West Jaintia Hills	2.8	3.1	8.3	18.6	24	25.6	27.4	25.9	22.6	13.5	2.5	1.9
West Khasi Hills	2.8	3.2	8.9	20	26.9	27.6	29	27.1	23.9	15.3	3.2	2
Aizawl	2.3	2.5	6.7	16.1	23.2	26.4	29.1	27.6	22.6	14.1	2.8	1.7
Champhai	2.2	2.3	6.1	15.1	22.3	25.9	29.1	27.3	22.1	14.2	2.8	1.7
Kolasib	2.3	2.6	7.1	16.7	23.6	25.7	28.6	27.8	21.7	12.8	2.6	1.6
Lawngtlai	0.9	1	2.3	7	12.2	20.7	23.4	23	20.5	13.7	2.7	1.4
Lunglei	1.2	1.3	3.7	10.4	17.6	24.7	27.2	26.4	23.3	15.1	2.7	1.5
Mamit	2.2	2.4	6.1	15.4	22.6	26.2	29.3	27.6	23.2	14.4	2.8	1.8
Saiha	0.7	0.9	1.8	6.2	10.6	19.9	22.9	22.3	19.6	12.8	2.5	1.2
Serchhip	2.2	2	4.7	13.4	20.6	27.2	29.9	28.2	23.6	15.2	3.1	1.5
Dimapur	2.8	3.1	8.4	15.7	19.7	22.9	27.3	24	20.1	10.8	2.1	1.7
Kiphire	3.6	4.2	10.3	16.7	20.3	23.8	25.4	21.8	18.9	11.6	2.6	2
Kohima	3.3	4	10	17.3	21.2	24.9	27.3	24.7	20.7	12.3	2.6	2.2
Longleng	4.9	5.4	12.5	17.9	22.4	25.5	27.3	23.6	19	10.2	2.9	1.8
Mokokchung	4.6	5.2	11.9	17.6	21.8	25.6	27.5	23.9	19.4	10.7	3.2	1.7
Mon	5	6.3	13	18.9	23.9	25.7	27.6	25.2	19.5	11.3	3.4	2
Peren	2.7	3.5	8.6	16.6	20.1	23.5	27.4	24.3	20.2	11.7	2	1.8
Phek	2.3	3	7.2	12.6	15.4	18.3	20.2	17.5	15.2	9.2	1.9	1.5
Tuensang	4.5	5.6	11.6	17.8	22.3	25.3	27.1	23.8	19.7	11	3	1.8
Wokha	4	4.8	11.4	17.9	22.5	25.8	27.7	25.2	20.1	11.2	3.2	2
Zunheboto	4.2	5	11.5	18	21.9	25.8	27.8	24.4	20	11.9	3.2	2.1
Anugul	1.6	2.1	2.6	6.1	8.8	16.7	24.4	24.4	20.2	10.1	1.5	1.5
Balangir	1.3	1.6	2.1	4.5	5.5	16	23.7	24	19.2	8.1	0.9	1.2
Baleshwar	1.5	2	3.1	8.5	10.5	15.7	21.4	23.1	19.4	10.9	1.6	1.6

Bargarh	1.4	2	2.2	3.9	5	14.7	22.9	23.2	17.7	7.1	0.8	1.4
Baudh	1.3	1.8	2.1	4	6	15.6	23.3	23.2	18.6	8.9	1.2	1.3
Bhadrak	1.7	2.3	3.8	8.2	10.1	17.5	22.6	24.3	19.4	12	1.9	1.8
Cuttack	1.3	1.6	2.6	5.8	8.2	15.3	23.5	23.5	19.4	10.8	1.9	1.2
Debagarh	1.5	2.2	2.2	5.7	8.1	16.4	24.7	24.7	19.5	8.4	1.3	1.4
Dhenkanal	1.3	1.8	2.6	6.3	9.2	15.7	23.5	23.2	19.3	9.9	1.7	1.3
Gajapati	1	1.4	3.3	8.5	10	15.1	21.1	21.8	20.6	11.7	3.4	1.5
Ganjam	1.1	1.2	2.4	5.8	6.6	13.7	20.2	21.6	19.2	10.8	3	1.4
Jagatsinghapur	1.5	1.7	2.5	6	9	16.3	23.4	24.3	19.7	12.5	2.7	1.7
Jajapur	1.4	1.9	2.8	7	10.4	16.2	22.1	23.3	18.5	10.3	1.7	1.5
Jharsuguda	1.7	2.3	3	4.1	5.4	15.9	22.9	23.7	17.8	6.7	0.7	1.8
Kalahandi	0.9	1.5	2.2	5.6	6.1	16	23.1	24.8	20	8.8	1.5	1
Kandhamal	1.3	1.8	2.7	6.8	8.9	16.3	23.7	23.9	21.5	10.6	2.3	1.5
Kendrapara	1.9	2.1	3.6	7.8	11.2	17.9	25	24.2	19.5	12.2	2.4	2.1
Kendujhar	1.8	2.3	3.7	8.6	12.9	17.5	24.2	24.3	20.3	10.6	1.6	1.7
Khordha	0.9	1.2	2.2	4	6.3	14.3	21.4	22	19.5	11.2	2.3	1.2
Koraput	1.2	1.3	3.6	8.4	11.2	17.9	22.8	25	21.8	12.2	3.3	1.5
Malkangiri	0.8	1	4	11	11.4	19.5	24.9	26.4	23.3	14	4	1.2
Mayurbhanj	1.6	2.2	3.5	9	12.4	17.2	23	23.6	19.6	10.2	1.5	1.7
Nabarangapur	0.8	1	2.5	6.5	7.4	17.1	23.3	24.7	19.9	8.4	1.3	0.8
Nayagarh	1	1.6	2.5	5	6.6	15.7	23.5	24.1	20.2	10.4	1.8	1.1
Nuapada	0.6	1.3	1.6	4.6	3.7	13.8	20.9	21.1	17.2	6.2	0.5	0.5
Puri	0.8	0.8	1.5	2.8	5	12.3	19.1	19.8	18.2	10.7	2.2	1.1
Rayagada	1.2	1.6	3.2	8.8	9.6	16.6	22.2	23.8	20.8	11.5	2.9	1.3
Sambalpur	1.5	1.9	2.2	4.1	6.2	16.1	24.2	24.6	18.9	7.7	1.1	1.4
Subarnapur	1.4	1.7	1.4	3.3	4.4	14	23.4	24.1	17.3	7.8	1.1	1.1
Sundargarh	1.8	2.3	3.1	5.3	8.3	17.2	24.8	25.4	19.9	8.4	1	1.4
Karaikal	4.9	1.9	2.5	4.8	5.9	9.5	9.8	13.2	10.8	15.1	18.4	12.5
Mahe	4.9	1.9	2.5	4.8	5.9	9.5	9.8	13.2	10.8	15.1	18.4	12.5

Puducherry	2.7	1.5	0.9	1.6	3.5	7.2	12	14.1	12	14.1	14.7	8.4
Yanam	2.7	1.5	0.9	1.6	3.5	7.2	12	14.1	12	14.1	14.7	8.4
Amritsar	3.5	5.2	5.1	4.6	3.5	8.3	13.3	13.3	6.5	2.1	1.1	1.3
Barnala	3.2	3	3.9	3.2	3.5	6.2	11.4	11.8	7.5	1.3	1	1.5
Bathinda	2.3	2.8	3.6	3	3.1	5.7	8.8	8.9	5.5	0.9	0.9	0.8
Faridkot	2.5	3.2	3.7	2.9	3.5	6.1	9.2	9	5.5	1.1	1	0.8
Fatehgarh Sahib	3.9	4.9	5.5	4.5	5.2	9.3	15.9	17.2	9.2	1.5	1.3	1.8
Fazilka	1.7	2.3	2.9	2.6	2.9	5.5	7.3	7.1	5.5	0.8	0.9	0.6
Firozpur	3.1	3.7	4.5	3.5	3.7	7	11.5	11.2	7	1.4	0.8	1
Gurdaspur	4.3	6.3	6.2	6.2	5	9.5	15.6	15.3	7.8	2.3	1.1	1.7
Hoshiarpur	4.6	6	6.3	5.7	5.4	10.2	17.6	17.9	9.4	2	1.1	1.8
Jalandhar	4.2	4.9	4.9	4.5	4.5	8.7	16.4	16.4	10	1.7	0.8	1.5
Kapurthala	4.1	5.4	5	4.6	4.2	9.5	15.2	16	9.4	1.9	1.2	1.5
Ludhiana	3.8	4.7	4.7	4	4.9	9	15.5	15.5	8.9	1.8	1.1	1.6
Mansa	2.4	2.7	4.2	2.9	3.5	6.8	9.5	8.9	5.8	1	1	1
Moga	3.1	3.7	4.3	3.5	3.9	6.5	11.7	10.7	6.4	1.3	1	1
Pathankot	5.5	7	7.1	6.2	6.3	9.8	17.7	19.3	9.7	3	1.4	1.9
Patiala	3.9	4.9	5.5	4.5	5.2	9.3	15.9	17.2	9.2	1.5	1.3	1.8
Rupnagar	4.1	5.5	6.1	5.4	5.1	10.2	17.6	18.4	10.4	1.8	1.3	2.2
Sahibzada Ajit Singh Nag*	4.1	5.5	6.1	5.4	5.1	10.2	17.6	18.4	10.4	1.8	1.3	2.2
Sangrur	2.9	3.6	4.2	3	3.9	7.2	12.1	12.4	6.4	1.1	1	1.6
Shahid Bhagat Singh Nagar	4.3	5.4	5.8	4.9	5.5	10	18.5	19.7	11.1	1.3	1.2	2
Sri Muktsar Sahib	2	2.4	3.2	2.6	2.8	5.2	8.2	8.5	5.5	0.8	1	0.7
Tarn Taran	3.7	5.1	5.3	4.7	3.8	8.5	14.9	14.1	7.5	2.2	1.2	1.2
Ajmer	0.8	0.7	1.1	1.6	2.5	6.4	14.1	15.4	8.3	1.1	0.3	0.2
Alwar	1.4	1.4	2.5	1.9	3.4	7.6	15.4	15.9	8.8	1.2	0.3	0.4
Banswara	0.4	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.8	7.3	17.2	18.7	12.4	2.2	0.1	0.5
Baran	1.2	0.9	1.2	0.9	1.7	10.4	20.1	20.8	12	1.7	0.3	0.8

Barmer	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.9	2	3.9	7.7	8.7	6.4	0.9	0.3	0.2
Bharatpur	1.8	1.5	2.3	1.9	3.4	7.4	15.7	17.2	8.4	1.2	0.3	0.5
Bhilwara	0.8	0.5	1	1.3	2.5	8.2	16.4	17.7	10.3	1.2	0.4	0.3
Bikaner	0.8	1.1	2	2	3.7	5.7	9.3	10.6	5.7	1.2	0.7	0.3
Bundi	1.4	0.7	1.5	1.6	2.7	9.4	19.1	19.6	10.9	1.4	0.5	0.7
Chittaurgarh	1.1	0.5	1	1.1	2.1	9.6	17.7	19	12.2	1.9	0.7	0.5
Churu	1.3	1.7	3	2.7	4.9	8.4	13.9	11.9	7.5	1.2	0.8	0.3
Dausa	1.2	1.1	2	1.6	3	8.9	18.1	18.8	9.9	1.7	0.4	0.4
Dhaulpur	1.7	1.5	2.2	1.6	2.9	8.4	16	17.3	9.9	1.3	0.3	0.6
Dungarpur	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.8	6.8	17.2	18.3	12.6	1.7	0.2	0.5
Ganganagar	1.3	2	2.5	2.3	2.9	5	7.3	6.7	5.3	0.6	0.7	0.4
Hanumangarh	1.5	1.8	2.9	2.6	3.1	6.4	9.4	7.9	6	1.1	0.8	0.4
Jaipur	1.1	1.3	1.8	1.8	2.9	8	16.5	17.3	9.2	1.4	0.4	0.4
Jaisalmer	0.7	0.6	1.4	1.5	2.2	3.6	7.1	6.7	4.5	0.6	0.4	0.3
Jalor	0.5	0.3	0.4	0.6	1.5	5	10.6	11.6	9.2	1.3	0.3	0.2
Jhalawar	0.8	0.8	1	0.6	1	10.1	19.2	19.9	12	1.7	0.2	0.5
Jhunjhunun	1.2	1.5	2.7	2.5	3.8	8.5	14.5	12.9	7.8	1.1	0.7	0.3
Jodhpur	0.7	0.5	1.1	1.4	3.2	5.4	10.5	11	6.5	1	0.2	0.4
Karauli	1.6	1.2	1.8	1.5	2.9	9.4	18.8	19.2	10.5	1.4	0.5	0.4
Kota	1.3	0.8	1.3	1.5	2	9.8	19	20.1	11	1.5	0.5	0.7
Nagaur	0.8	0.7	1.1	2	3.7	7	13.4	13.8	7.7	1.2	0.3	0.3
Pali	0.6	0.3	0.7	1.2	2.5	6.5	13.3	13.7	9	1.4	0.3	0.2
Pratapgarh	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.7	1.5	10.5	19.3	20.4	14.4	2.8	0.3	0.6
Rajsamand	0.6	0.3	0.8	1.2	2.6	8.3	16.1	16.8	11.6	1.9	0.4	0.2
Sawai Madhopur	1.4	0.9	1.2	1.8	2.3	8.8	17.7	19.2	9.8	1.3	0.5	0.7
Sikar	1.1	1.4	2.5	2.3	3.8	9.5	16.1	14.7	9.1	1.5	0.6	0.3
Sirohi	0.3	0.2	0.6	0.5	1.4	6.5	14.6	16.4	11.4	1.7	0.2	0.3
Tonk	1.2	0.8	1.4	1.9	2.9	8	17.3	18.2	9.9	1.4	0.3	0.4
Udaipur	0.6	0.3	0.7	1	2.2	8.9	16.8	18.4	13.2	2.2	0.5	0.3

East District	4	5	13.8	20.3	26.9	27.8	30.6	29.7	26.7	12.9	3.1	2.4
North District	5.5	6.8	17.3	22.9	26.6	28.3	30.5	30.3	27.2	14	4.5	2.3
South District	4	5	13.8	20.3	26.9	27.8	30.6	29.7	26.7	12.9	3.1	2.4
West District	5	5.9	15.7	21.5	26.2	27.5	30.4	29.4	26.4	12.7	3.5	2.3
Ariyalur	3.7	1.7	2.4	5	7	9	10.5	13.2	10.9	13.6	15.3	9.4
Chengalpattu	1.5	0.7	0.3	1.5	2.7	6.5	12.2	13	10.7	13.6	13.4	7
Chennai	2	1	0.3	1.6	3	7.7	13.4	14.5	12.4	13.7	13.7	7
Coimbatore	1.8	1.3	3.6	8	12	15.8	17	17	15.4	15.9	12.5	5.9
Cuddalore	3.5	1.5	1.7	3.6	5.3	9.2	11.9	15.2	12.2	15.4	16.4	9.4
Dharmapuri	1.3	0.7	1.2	5.3	10.6	7.8	9.7	12.5	12.6	14.5	11	5.1
Dindigul	2.6	1.3	2.8	6.4	10.3	10	10	12.2	13.2	14.5	13	7
Erode	1.2	0.8	1.8	6.9	10.8	10.1	9.5	12.8	12.8	15.3	10.6	4.5
Kallakurichi	1.4	0.7	0.6	2.6	5.7	5.9	8.9	11	10.5	13.7	12.4	6.2
Kancheepuram	2	1	0.3	1.6	3	7.7	13.4	14.5	12.4	13.7	13.7	7
Kanniyakumari	4.7	3.9	8.3	14	15.5	18.9	14.8	14.3	16.6	18.5	19.7	12.9
Karur	2.4	1.1	2.5	5.3	8.1	8.5	8.4	11.4	11.6	13.5	12.6	6.7
Krishnagiri	1.3	0.9	1.5	6	12.1	8.6	10.6	13	13.3	15.2	10.6	4.6
Madurai	2.9	1.4	3.1	6.3	9.7	8.4	8.9	11.8	11.6	13.6	12.4	7.2
Nagapattinam	4.6	1.7	2.5	5	6.3	9.4	10.6	13.1	11.5	15.5	18.3	11.7
Namakkal	1.4	0.8	1.1	5.6	9.6	8.6	9	13.1	13	14	11	5
Perambalur	2.8	1.1	1.8	4.9	7.1	9.3	10	12.9	10.7	13.9	13.2	7.3
Pudukkottai	3	1.4	2.5	5.3	7	9.5	10	12.2	11	13.8	14.6	8.8
Ramanathapuram	3	1.6	2.5	5.5	6.2	5.3	6	7.5	7.7	12.1	13.3	8.3
Ranipet	2	1	0.5	2.5	4.7	9.9	13.5	15.1	14.7	12.5	12.2	6.2
Salem	1.8	0.7	1.2	5.5	10	7.9	10.1	13.3	12.9	15.4	12	5.9
Sivaganga	3.3	1.6	2.9	6.1	9.3	9.8	11	13.2	12.3	15.1	15.4	10.1
Tenkasi	3.2	2	5.4	9.3	10.7	8.5	8.4	9.5	10.6	14.7	15.8	9.6
Thanjavur	3.6	1.5	2.3	5.6	6.9	8.5	9.6	12	10.8	13.5	16.4	10
The Nilgiris	2.6	1.9	5	12.2	16.2	21.6	24.4	23.7	19.5	19.4	15.3	7.8

Theni	2.8	1.8	4.8	8.6	11.8	11.5	12.2	13.3	12.2	15.5	13.1	7.3
Thiruvallur	1.6	0.9	0.4	1.9	2.9	8.9	13.5	14	12.8	14.2	13.1	7.2
Thiruvarur	4.1	1.5	2.3	5	6.5	8	9.2	11.5	10.7	14	17.5	10.7
Thoothukkudi	2.7	1.5	2.9	4.9	6	5	4.9	6.3	7.2	11.2	13.1	7.5
Tiruchirappalli	2.6	1.1	2.1	5.3	8	8.7	8.8	11.6	12.1	14.2	13.6	7.1
Tirunelveli	3.6	2.2	5.1	7.4	7.8	7.3	5.8	7.2	7.3	12.6	16.2	10.3
Tirupathur	1.2	0.9	0.9	4.1	8.8	8.4	11	13.2	13.9	14.7	11	5.1
Tiruppur	1.7	0.9	2	5.8	8.8	9.2	10.1	11.3	11.4	13.1	11.9	5.4
Tiruvannamalai	1.7	0.9	0.5	2.3	5.7	8.5	12.2	14	14.5	15.1	13	6.2
Vellore	1.7	0.8	0.6	3.2	7	9.5	12.9	14.7	15.3	14.2	11.3	5.6
Viluppuram	1.4	0.7	0.4	1.2	3.1	5.7	8.3	10	9	10.8	10.6	5.4
Virudhunagar	2.8	1.6	3.4	6.3	9.6	7.2	7.7	10.6	10.7	14	13.6	8.1
Adilabad	1	1.1	3.1	3.3	3.9	16.4	21.7	21	16.7	7.1	1.2	0.4
Bhadradi Kothagudem	0.5	0.2	1.4	4.3	5.3	14.1	22.2	22.9	18.5	10.6	2.6	0.4
Hyderabad	0.8	0.7	1.2	5.3	5.6	12.8	16.9	17	15.2	9	2.6	0.5
Jagitial	0.9	1	1.6	2.4	3.8	13.6	19.4	19.2	16.2	7.4	1	0.4
Jangoan	0.7	0.6	1	3.7	3.9	13.8	18.1	18.1	16.2	8.4	2.8	0.5
Jayashankar	0.7	0.7	2.1	3.4	4.6	16.1	22.7	22.7	18.3	8.8	1.7	0.4
Jogulamba Gadwal	0.7	0.5	0.7	3.4	5.8	12.1	17.1	16.4	14.6	7.9	3.5	0.4
Kamareddy	0.8	0.7	1.9	3.3	3.9	15.1	19	17.5	14.5	7.2	1.5	0.3
Karimnagar	0.8	0.6	1.8	2.7	3.6	14.1	19.4	18.3	15.5	6.7	1.4	0.5
Khammam	0.8	0.3	1.3	3.2	5.1	13.9	20.3	20.8	16.6	9.4	3	0.5
Kumuram Bheem Asifabad	0.9	1.1	2.7	3.4	3.8	16.4	23.1	22.8	17.7	7.1	1.2	0.7
Mahabubabad	0.6	0.6	1.5	3.3	5	14.5	20.7	20.9	16.8	9.2	2.6	0.5
Mahabubnagar	0.4	0.3	0.9	4.7	6.9	12.2	17.2	16.9	14.3	8.4	2.6	0.3
Mancherial	0.8	0.7	2.3	2.4	3.5	14.7	21.8	22.7	18.1	8.1	1.1	0.5
Medak	1	0.7	2	4.4	4.9	14.1	18.5	17.8	14.7	7.8	1.8	0.4
Medchal Malkajgiri	1.1	1.1	1.8	5.7	6.1	13.5	18.1	18.5	15.4	8.5	2.1	0.5
Mulugu	0.8	0.5	1.8	4.1	5.8	16.1	22.7	23.2	19	10	2	0.4

Nagarkurnool	0.6	0.5	1.1	4.5	6.5	12.2	16	16.8	14.8	9.2	4	0.8
Nalgonda	0.8	0.5	1	2.8	5	12.4	16.4	17.5	15.1	8.8	3.4	0.5
Narayanpet	0.5	0.4	1.3	4.1	6.6	13.5	18.2	18.2	15.7	8.7	2.5	0.4
Nirmal	0.9	1.2	2.1	2.7	4.1	16.1	21.2	21.6	16.9	7.5	1.3	0.5
Nizamabad	0.9	1	1.8	3	4	15.5	20.7	19.3	15.9	7.2	1.6	0.4
Peddapalli	0.8	0.6	2	2.6	3.5	14.6	21.1	20.2	16.1	7.3	1.2	0.6
Rajanna Sircilla	1	0.7	2	3.5	4.5	13.3	18.9	17.6	14.9	7.5	1.5	0.3
Ranga Reddy	0.8	0.7	1.2	5.3	5.6	12.8	16.9	17	15.2	9	2.6	0.5
Sangareddy	0.9	0.6	2.1	5.5	5.7	14.8	19.1	19.3	15.3	8.2	2.2	0.3
Siddipet	0.9	0.7	1.9	4.3	4.1	14.2	18	17.4	15.4	8.2	2.1	0.4
Suryapet	0.9	0.5	0.7	2.1	4.9	13.2	18	18.8	14.2	9.1	3.5	0.5
Vikarabad	0.5	0.5	1.6	5.3	6	12.9	17.5	18.5	15.2	8.4	1.8	0.3
Wanaparthy	0.5	0.5	1	4	6.8	12.4	17.9	17.7	14.9	9	3.6	0.7
Warangal Rural	1	0.5	1.6	3.3	4.6	15.2	19.6	19.8	16.5	8.9	2.4	0.5
Warangal Urban	0.7	0.6	1.4	2.9	3.8	13.4	18.4	18.1	14.9	7.4	1.8	0.4
Yadadri Bhuvanagiri	0.7	0.8	1.2	3.9	4.3	12.4	15.6	15.9	14.8	8.6	2.6	0.3
Dhalai	1.9	2.6	6.4	16.4	24.2	26.9	28.8	27.5	22.4	13.8	2.7	1.8
Gomati	1.2	2.1	4.6	12.2	20.5	25.1	27	26.2	22.8	13.9	2.5	1.4
Khowai	2	2.5	6.9	15.8	24.6	27.3	29.1	28	24	15.5	2.8	1.9
North Tripura	2	2.6	5.8	14.9	23	25.6	29.1	27.5	22.4	14.1	2.9	1.8
Sipahijala	1.1	2	4.5	12.6	19.9	23.9	26.1	24.4	20.6	12.1	2	1.4
South Tripura	0.8	1.8	4	10.7	19.3	24.2	26.9	25.4	22.6	13	2.1	1.2
Unokoti	1.6	2.3	6	16.9	24.6	25.8	28.1	27.2	21.6	11.8	2	1.5
West Tripura	1.4	1.9	5.3	14.1	21.8	25	27.5	25.9	21.7	12.5	2	1.5
Agra	2.2	2	2.7	2	3.4	7.3	17.2	18.6	10.1	1.5	0.3	0.9
Aligarh	2.9	2.5	3.2	2.1	3.9	7.1	16.7	16.6	8.6	1.6	0.3	0.9
Ambedkar Nagar	2.4	2.6	2.4	2.4	5	11.7	21.2	20.8	14.5	3.3	0.2	0.8
Amethi	2.3	2.7	2.1	1.6	3.4	9.7	18.9	17.8	11.1	2.8	0.2	0.7
Amroha	3.1	3.2	3.5	2.7	4.1	7.3	18.1	17.4	9.2	1.4	0.6	1.2

Auraiya	2.7	2.2	2.1	1.4	3	8	18.2	17.6	9.6	2	0.3	0.7
Azamgarh	2.4	2.2	1.9	1.9	4.2	11.1	20.4	20	12.7	3.1	0	0.6
Baghpat	3.4	3	3.5	2.6	4.6	7.3	14.2	15	7.3	1	0.8	1.2
Bahraich	3.2	3.2	2.3	2	4.8	12.1	21.3	19.7	11.4	2.4	0.1	0.8
Ballia	1.8	1.9	1.6	2.1	4.9	10.2	18.6	17.8	13.3	3.6	0	0.4
Balrampur	2.1	2.7	1.6	1.9	4.7	11.9	19.6	18.6	11.4	2.2	0.1	0.6
Banda	2.5	2.1	1.9	1.4	2.8	9.6	18.6	18.1	10.1	2	0.2	0.6
Bara Banki	2.9	3	2.5	2.1	3.9	10.4	20.7	19.9	12.1	2.2	0.2	0.6
Bareilly	3.5	3.1	3.6	2.5	3.9	9.5	20.3	18.6	10.1	1.6	0.3	0.9
Basti	2.4	2.6	2.1	1.8	5.1	11.8	20.5	19.6	14.1	3.2	0.1	0.5
Bhadohi	2.6	2.3	2.5	2	2.8	9.7	19.6	18.5	12.4	3.2	0.2	0.6
Bijnor	3.1	3.7	3.6	2.3	4.1	8.3	19.1	18.7	9.9	1.4	0.5	1.6
Budaun	2.9	2.2	2.4	2	2.8	6.5	17.2	15.8	7.8	1.4	0.2	0.6
Bulandshahr	2.8	2.5	3.2	1.9	3.9	6.1	15.5	15.3	7.7	1.3	0.4	0.9
Chandauli	2.2	2.1	2.4	2	3.6	10.8	19.8	19.8	13.8	3.4	0.3	0.9
Chitrakoot	2.5	2	2.2	1.4	2.9	10.1	19.6	19.3	11.8	2.3	0.2	0.7
Deoria	1.8	2.1	1.8	2.4	5.5	12.2	19.6	20	13.5	3.4	0.1	0.5
Etah	2.5	2	2.3	1.8	3	6.1	15.7	15.2	7.9	1.3	0.3	0.6
Etawah	2	1.5	1.7	1.3	2.5	6.9	15.1	15.7	7.5	1.4	0.3	0.6
Faizabad	2.3	2.4	1.8	1.8	3.9	10.1	18.5	18.8	12.1	2.5	0.1	0.6
Farrukhabad	2	1.9	2.1	1.5	2.1	6.9	16.7	14.8	9.4	1.7	0.4	0.6
Fatehpur	2.5	2.5	2	1.5	3.4	9.2	18.6	18.1	10.6	2.2	0.1	0.6
Firozabad	2.3	2	2.3	1.5	2.7	6.6	15.1	16.4	7.8	1	0.2	0.7
Gautam Buddha Nagar	2.7	2.1	2.5	1.5	3.4	5.6	13	13.9	6.8	0.8	0.4	0.8
Ghaziabad	3.4	2.8	3.7	2.8	5.4	7.5	15.5	15.7	7.5	1.3	0.6	1.5
Ghaziipur	2	2	1.9	2	4.1	10.9	20.2	19.2	13.4	3.8	0	0.3
Gonda	2.3	2.5	1.7	1.8	4.5	11.3	19.1	19	12	2.2	0.1	0.6
Gorakhpur	2.1	2.5	2.1	2.2	5.4	11.1	18.7	17.2	12	2.5	0.1	0.5
Hamirpur	2.7	2.4	2.2	1.9	3.6	8.6	18.7	18.5	9.8	2.2	0.2	0.8

Hapur	3.3	2.9	3.1	2.1	3.8	6	15.6	16.1	8.4	1.2	0.4	0.9
Hardoi	2.6	2.8	2.3	2	3.4	9.7	19.9	18.5	10.9	1.8	0.3	0.7
Hathras	2.4	2	3	2.1	2.9	6.3	15.9	15.7	7.7	1.4	0.4	0.5
Jalaun	2.5	1.9	1.7	1.3	3.1	7.5	16.5	15.6	8.5	2.1	0.2	0.7
Jaunpur	2.3	2.2	2.3	2	2.9	8.9	18	17.9	12.6	2.9	0	0.6
Jhansi	2.2	2.4	2	1.8	3.2	9.8	19.1	18.6	10.1	2	0.3	0.7
Kannauj	2.8	2.7	2.5	1.8	2.9	8.1	19.5	17.8	10.9	1.9	0.3	0.6
Kanpur Dehat	2.8	2.2	2.6	1.6	3.1	8.4	19.3	17.8	10.5	2.1	0.3	0.7
Kanpur Nagar	2.9	2.5	2.5	1.6	3.5	8.5	19.1	17.9	11.7	2.3	0.3	0.7
Kasganj	3	2.6	2.8	2.2	3.5	6.9	17.6	17.1	8.6	1.5	0.3	0.8
Kaushambi	2.6	2.2	1.9	1.3	2.7	8.9	17.6	17.2	11.1	2.2	0.1	0.7
Kheri	2.7	2.8	2	1.5	4.5	11.3	20.1	18.4	9.9	2.1	0.3	0.8
Kushinagar	1.8	1.9	2.2	2.9	6.8	11.9	19.2	19	13.9	3.1	0.2	0.5
Lalitpur	1.9	2.1	1.6	1	1.8	11.9	20.5	20.7	11.9	1.9	0.1	1
Lucknow	3.1	3.1	2.8	2	3.8	10.8	21.1	20.3	12.8	2.7	0.2	0.7
Mahoba	2.6	2.4	2.1	1.7	2.9	9.9	19.4	19.5	11.1	1.8	0.3	0.9
Mahrajganj	1.7	2.2	2.3	3.2	7.6	13.4	19.7	19.5	14	2.9	0.1	0.5
Mainpuri	2.2	1.9	2	1.4	2.7	6.4	16.5	15.7	8.9	1.6	0.2	0.6
Mathura	2.3	2	2.6	2.3	3.4	6.6	15.8	15.9	8.1	1.4	0.2	0.6
Mau	2.3	2.1	1.9	2.3	5	12.1	20.7	20.6	14.7	3.6	0	0.6
Meerut	3.4	3.1	3.6	2.7	4.9	7.1	16.5	15.9	8.1	1.3	0.6	1.5
Mirzapur	2.6	2.1	2.9	2.1	3.3	10.9	20.9	20.6	13.9	3.4	0.5	0.9
Moradabad	2.9	3.6	3.7	2.8	3.8	8.2	18.3	17.1	9.5	1.4	0.3	1
Muzaffarnagar	3.5	3.8	4.1	3.4	4.8	7.9	16.2	16.5	8.7	1.5	0.8	1.7
Pilibhit	3.5	3.3	2.9	2.6	4.5	12.7	22.3	21.3	11.5	2.5	0.4	0.9
Pratapgarh	2.5	2.2	2.2	1.8	3.2	10.2	19.7	19.3	13.2	2.7	0.1	0.7
Prayagraj	2.3	2	2.4	1.3	2.4	9.5	19.4	19.1	12.4	2.7	0.1	0.5
Rae Bareli	2.4	2.4	2.2	1.7	3.2	9.1	17.8	16.3	10	2.3	0.1	0.6
Rampur	3.9	3.4	3.6	2.9	4.7	9.6	21.4	19.5	10.4	1.7	0.4	1

Saharanpur	4	4.8	4.6	4.5	5.6	11	20.8	20.6	11.2	2.2	0.7	1.9
Sambhal	3.1	3.1	3.2	2.2	3.6	6.7	17.7	16.2	8.3	1.4	0.4	0.8
Sant Kabir Nagar	2.3	2.9	2.5	1.9	5.9	12.8	20.9	20	14.6	3.1	0.2	0.6
Shahjahanpur	2.7	2.3	2.5	1.7	3.4	8.4	18.5	16.8	9	1.6	0.4	0.6
Shamli	3.5	3.8	3.8	3	4.1	7.2	14.4	15.8	8.3	1.3	0.8	1.5
Shrawasti	2.9	3	1.8	1.7	4.9	11.5	19.2	17.8	10.4	2.2	0.1	0.8
Siddharthnagar	2.1	2.6	2.1	2	5.9	12.5	20.7	20.3	13.4	2.8	0.2	0.5
Sitapur	3	3.1	2.3	2.2	4.2	9.7	19.6	18.6	10.5	1.8	0.2	0.6
Sonbhadra	2.6	2.4	3.4	2.4	4	12.2	21.3	20.9	15.1	4.2	0.6	1.2
Sultanpur	2.5	2.6	2.3	2.5	3.8	10.4	20.6	19.8	13.4	2.8	0.2	0.7
Unnao	2.9	2.6	2.1	1.5	2.8	8.2	18.3	16.9	10	2.1	0.2	0.6
Varanasi	2.9	2.6	2.6	2.3	3.1	9.8	19.9	20.2	13.6	3.4	0.2	0.6
Almora	5.4	5.5	7.2	8.8	10.7	15.8	24.3	23.2	13.9	2.7	0.6	1.7
Bageshwar	6	6.4	8.1	10.2	13	18.8	27.1	26.8	18	4.2	0.9	2.1
Chamoli	7	7.9	9	12.1	14.2	19.6	27.6	27.5	18.3	4.6	1.8	2.6
Champawat	5.3	5.6	7.6	9.5	12	17.6	25.6	25.3	14.5	3.3	0.4	1.8
Dehradun	6.3	7.6	8.3	9.1	10.3	15.6	26	25.7	15.3	3.3	1.5	2.7
Garhwal	5.1	5.8	6.2	6.5	8.2	13.4	24.5	24.1	13.7	2.1	0.7	2
Hardwar	4.6	5	5.1	4.4	7.1	13	24.6	24.2	13.5	1.9	0.8	2.2
Nainital	5.5	5.2	6.4	7.8	9.7	16.6	25.9	25	15.5	3.3	0.5	1.7
Pithoragarh	6.6	7.5	9.3	11.8	15	20.7	28.8	28.4	20.2	5.3	1.2	2.2
Rudraprayag	5.9	7.1	7.9	10.5	13.4	17.9	26.3	26.9	16.4	3.5	1.1	2.2
Tehri Garhwal	6.1	7.6	8.2	9.9	11.7	15.8	25.4	25	14.8	3.2	1.6	2.6
Udham Singh Nagar	4.8	4.5	4.8	4.9	7.7	14.7	25.3	24	13.5	2.9	0.5	1.3
Uttarkashi	7	8.9	10	11.3	13	17.2	26.4	26.2	16.6	3.7	2	3.1
Alipurduar	1.2	2	5.8	13.7	22.6	24.8	25.6	23.9	19.9	8.5	1.2	0.6
Bankura	2.2	2	4.2	7.5	12.2	18.6	24.5	23.4	19	9.6	1.7	1.5
Birbhum	2.1	2	3.9	6.9	12.6	17.6	24.1	22	16.6	8.5	1.3	1
Cooch Behar	1.2	2	5.8	13.7	23	24.9	26.4	24.2	20.4	8.3	1.5	0.7

Dakshin Dinajpur	0.8	1.2	2.6	8.4	15.6	17.7	23.3	19.1	16.2	6.4	0.6	0.4
Darjiling	2.2	2.7	7	13.3	22.9	25.9	28.6	26.3	23.1	9.7	1.8	1.1
Hooghly	1.8	2	4	6.6	10.9	19.6	26.2	24.2	19.6	10.7	2.1	1.5
Howrah	2.3	2	4.1	6.9	11.5	19.9	26	25.5	20.5	12	2.3	1.8
Jalpaiguri	1.7	2.5	6.1	13.2	23.1	25.8	28.1	26.6	22.4	9.3	2.3	0.9
Jhargram	1.9	2.5	3.6	8.2	10.9	16.5	22.3	24	19	10.1	2	2
Kalimpong	1.9	2.6	6.1	12.4	22.3	26.4	29.3	27.3	23.4	10.6	2.8	1
Kolkata	1.9	1.7	3.6	6.4	10.6	19.6	25.4	24.9	19.7	11.8	2.6	1.8
Maldah	1.3	1.5	2.3	7.2	12.7	17	24.1	21.7	17.9	7.1	0.6	0.7
Medinipur West	2.1	2.3	4.1	8	12.2	17.5	24.6	24.5	20.5	11.3	2.2	1.8
Murshidabad	2.1	2.2	4.1	6.9	11.8	17.1	23.8	21.5	16.6	8.5	1.5	1.1
Nadia	1.5	1.9	3.2	5.7	9.6	15.4	21.2	18.8	14.7	8.3	1.6	1.1
North Twenty Four Pargan*	1.5	1.6	3.5	6	10.3	19	25.7	23.5	17.9	10.7	1.8	1.4
Paschim Bardhaman	2.1	1.8	4	7	13.3	19.4	25.5	24.2	18.1	9.7	1	1.3
Purba Bardhaman	1.8	2.1	3.9	7	11.4	18.1	24.3	22.1	16.7	9.5	1.9	1.4
Purba Medinipur	1.8	2.1	3.6	7.3	11.7	17.4	23.4	24.1	20.8	12.1	2.1	1.8
Puruliya	2.2	2.4	4.3	7.8	13	17.9	24.4	23.7	18.6	9.8	1.5	1.5
South Twenty Four Pargan*	1.9	1.7	3.6	6.4	10.6	19.6	25.4	24.9	19.7	11.8	2.6	1.8
Uttar Dinajpur	1	1.6	3.7	9.4	18.1	21.6	26.1	23.1	19.2	6.7	0.8	0.6

Table 5: Traffic Volume Composition (%) of Each Vehicle Category by Road Types

	2W	LMV-P	4W	LMV-G	HDV-T	Buses	Others
Golden Quadrilateral	30	11	46	5	3.5	2.5	2
(State+National) Highway	31	12	44	4	2.5	2.5	4
District Road	40	18	30	3.5	1	1.5	6
City road	42.5	17.5	35	1.5	1	1.5	2

References: *CLASSIFIED TRAFFIC VOLUME AND SPEED STUDY DELHI (2018)*, *TRIPP*

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Table 6: District-wise Vehicle Kilometer Travelled (in Billion Vehicle Kilometers) by vehicle categories

District	2-W	LMV-P	4-W	LMV-G	HDV-T	Buses	Others
Nicobars	0.0671	0.0166	0.0507	0.0024	0.0096	0.0049	0.0014
North & Middle Andaman	0.008	0.002	0.0071	0.0003	0.0014	0.0005	0.0002
South Andaman	0.3625	0.0896	0.2737	0.0128	0.0519	0.0267	0.0074
Anantapur	4.9227	1.2149	1.1504	0.758	0.702	0.4859	0.5359
Chittoor	5.5668	1.2601	1.2027	0.7445	0.7971	0.5147	0.5626
East Godavari	5.838	1.3619	1.3428	0.8194	0.8285	0.5503	0.6053
Guntur	7.1698	1.8084	1.5893	1.0776	1.0079	0.6274	0.7767
Krishna	8.4394	2.091	1.6881	1.1487	1.2174	0.7232	0.7686
Kurnool	4.8695	1.2371	1.1405	0.7735	0.6739	0.475	0.5427
Prakasam	3.1969	0.6457	0.6447	0.3584	0.4695	0.2848	0.2912
Sri Potti Sriramulu Nell*	3.7436	0.9177	0.8376	0.5525	0.5371	0.3417	0.4012
Srikakulam	2.062	0.4063	0.4387	0.2411	0.2969	0.2083	0.192
Visakhapatnam	9.4224	2.3325	1.7415	1.259	1.3533	0.7388	0.8232
Vizianagaram	2.1865	0.5004	0.4894	0.3034	0.3286	0.2092	0.228
West Godavari	3.591	0.8475	0.7816	0.503	0.5092	0.3252	0.3753
Y.S.R.	4.3844	1.0165	0.9511	0.6006	0.6392	0.3973	0.4533
Anjaw	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Changlang	0.0207	0.0028	0.0209	0.0042	0.006	0.0171	0.0018
East Kameng	0.0162	0.0021	0.0136	0.0029	0.0053	0.0074	0.0009
East Siang	0.014	0.002	0.0107	0.0023	0.0038	0.0118	0.0008
Kamle	0.0054	0.0007	0.0046	0.001	0.0018	0.0025	0.0003

Kra Daadi	0.001	0.0002	0.001	0.0003	0.0003	0.0006	0.0001
Kurung Kumey	0.0022	0.0004	0.0022	0.0006	0.0006	0.0013	0.0002
Lepa Rada	0.0027	0.0004	0.0021	0.0005	0.0007	0.0023	0.0002
Lohit	0.0231	0.003	0.0194	0.0042	0.0076	0.0106	0.0013
Longding	0.0109	0.0015	0.0109	0.0024	0.0031	0.0083	0.0009
Lower Dibang Valley	0.0183	0.0024	0.0153	0.0033	0.006	0.0084	0.001
Lower Siang	0.0118	0.0017	0.0091	0.002	0.0032	0.0098	0.0007
Lower Subansiri	0.0151	0.002	0.0127	0.0027	0.005	0.0069	0.0008
Namsai	0.0289	0.0038	0.0242	0.0053	0.0095	0.0132	0.0016
Pakke Kessang	0.0132	0.0017	0.0111	0.0024	0.0043	0.0061	0.0007
Papum Pare	0.1467	0.0205	0.0947	0.0188	0.0437	0.086	0.0076
Shi Yomi	0.0035	0.0005	0.0027	0.0006	0.0009	0.0028	0.0002
Siang	0.0116	0.0016	0.009	0.0019	0.0032	0.0097	0.0007
Tawang	0.018	0.0024	0.0151	0.0033	0.0059	0.0082	0.001
Tirap	0.0127	0.0018	0.0127	0.0028	0.0036	0.0097	0.0011
Upper Dibang Valley	0.0033	0.0005	0.0032	0.0009	0.0009	0.0019	0.0003
Upper Siang	0.007	0.001	0.0071	0.0014	0.002	0.0058	0.0006
Upper Subansiri	0.0215	0.0028	0.018	0.0039	0.0071	0.0099	0.0012
West Kameng	0.0193	0.0028	0.0191	0.0046	0.0055	0.0134	0.0017
West Siang	0.0052	0.0007	0.0041	0.0009	0.0014	0.0043	0.0003
Baksa	0.0335	0.0054	0.0195	0.0089	0.0125	0.0029	0.0028
Barpeta	0.51	0.0703	0.2617	0.1005	0.1962	0.0394	0.027
Biswanath	0.2037	0.0303	0.0958	0.0375	0.0821	0.0119	0.0104

Bongaigaon	0.3311	0.0527	0.1904	0.0829	0.1354	0.0258	0.0238
Cachar	0.953	0.171	0.5656	0.2867	0.3199	0.0743	0.0743
Charaideo	0.1364	0.021	0.0654	0.0266	0.055	0.0078	0.0076
Chirang	0.1174	0.0188	0.0706	0.0295	0.0547	0.0086	0.0072
Darrang	0.1998	0.0282	0.1059	0.0405	0.0831	0.0148	0.0099
Dhemaji	0.1682	0.0236	0.0876	0.0341	0.065	0.0127	0.0089
Dhubri	0.5512	0.0743	0.2424	0.0889	0.1973	0.0361	0.0261
Dibrugarh	0.7707	0.1339	0.4425	0.219	0.2567	0.0592	0.0553
Dima Hasao	0.2222	0.0294	0.1093	0.0407	0.0816	0.0171	0.011
Goalpara	0.4738	0.0738	0.2356	0.0979	0.1912	0.0283	0.0276
Golaghat	0.3364	0.0451	0.1669	0.0634	0.1218	0.0264	0.0178
Hailakandi	0.1525	0.0267	0.0976	0.0456	0.0641	0.0098	0.0109
Hojai	0.3951	0.0612	0.213	0.0939	0.1407	0.0304	0.0242
Jorhat	0.5505	0.0964	0.3191	0.1587	0.1841	0.0422	0.0403
Kamrup	0.4532	0.07	0.2588	0.1101	0.1834	0.0345	0.0296
Kamrup Metropolitan	3.1697	0.6042	1.8773	1.0271	0.9149	0.244	0.2541
Karbi Anglong	0.2711	0.0413	0.1232	0.0499	0.1051	0.0149	0.015
Karimganj	0.3865	0.0589	0.1781	0.0719	0.1519	0.0217	0.0213
Kokrajhar	0.185	0.0251	0.0923	0.0359	0.065	0.0145	0.0103
Lakhimpur	0.3405	0.0514	0.1488	0.0581	0.1351	0.0172	0.0169
Majuli	0.1393	0.0244	0.0808	0.0402	0.0466	0.0107	0.0102
Morigaon	0.2436	0.0351	0.1301	0.0523	0.0946	0.0188	0.0142
Nagaon	0.8379	0.1298	0.4518	0.1992	0.2983	0.0644	0.0513

Nalbari	0.2585	0.0388	0.1419	0.0608	0.0943	0.0201	0.0173
Sivasagar	0.2517	0.0388	0.1207	0.0492	0.1015	0.0144	0.014
Sonitpur	0.4292	0.0639	0.2019	0.0791	0.1729	0.0251	0.0219
South Salmara Mancachar	0.1979	0.0267	0.087	0.0319	0.0708	0.013	0.0094
Tinsukia	0.8722	0.1413	0.4817	0.2222	0.3044	0.0666	0.0562
Udalguri	0.1276	0.0204	0.0769	0.0319	0.0607	0.0092	0.0075
West Karbi Anglong	0.1274	0.0194	0.0579	0.0234	0.0494	0.007	0.007
Araria	0.6327	0.1126	0.0828	0.0327	0.0813	0.0206	0.0775
Arwal	0.1972	0.0364	0.0244	0.0098	0.0258	0.0053	0.0244
Aurangabad	0.7962	0.1516	0.1344	0.0658	0.0989	0.0359	0.1273
Banka	0.2547	0.0393	0.0394	0.0151	0.0305	0.0134	0.03
Begusarai	1.9277	0.3732	0.3146	0.1553	0.2393	0.0808	0.3097
Bhagalpur	1.9439	0.3897	0.3553	0.1887	0.2355	0.0941	0.3474
Bhojpur	1.2524	0.2493	0.2354	0.1245	0.1525	0.0635	0.2237
Buxar	0.5388	0.1103	0.0922	0.0491	0.0662	0.0226	0.0959
Darbhanga	1.2218	0.2571	0.2226	0.124	0.1475	0.0553	0.2318
Gaya	1.8225	0.3753	0.3481	0.1933	0.2146	0.0934	0.349
Gopalganj	0.5907	0.0996	0.0844	0.0332	0.0738	0.0245	0.0733
Jamui	0.5239	0.0924	0.0729	0.0295	0.0669	0.0192	0.069
Jehanabad	0.4287	0.0864	0.0805	0.0438	0.0505	0.022	0.0793
Kaimur (bhabua)	0.2322	0.043	0.0318	0.0134	0.0303	0.0074	0.0332
Katihar	0.8458	0.1784	0.1647	0.0936	0.0995	0.0433	0.1688
Khagaria	0.3113	0.048	0.0482	0.0184	0.0373	0.0164	0.0366

Kishanganj	0.5185	0.1032	0.0977	0.0515	0.0636	0.0262	0.0923
Lakhisarai	0.5339	0.094	0.0709	0.0279	0.0682	0.0183	0.0652
Madhepura	0.3238	0.0567	0.0444	0.0177	0.0412	0.0118	0.041
Madhubani	0.5795	0.1019	0.0855	0.0349	0.0754	0.0227	0.0763
Munger	1.1743	0.2476	0.2299	0.1298	0.1401	0.0597	0.2339
Muzaffarpur	1.4885	0.3047	0.2854	0.1561	0.1791	0.0757	0.2818
Nalanda	1.4851	0.2941	0.2654	0.1397	0.1778	0.0716	0.2611
Nawada	0.7926	0.1337	0.1112	0.0433	0.0991	0.0321	0.0956
Pashchim Champaran	1.2549	0.2438	0.2305	0.1202	0.1489	0.0649	0.2232
Patna	8.8211	1.7397	1.3134	0.7682	1.1492	0.3409	1.242
Purba Champaran	1.3772	0.2485	0.2299	0.1058	0.171	0.0653	0.202
Purnia	1.0768	0.2217	0.2054	0.1141	0.1266	0.0552	0.2056
Rohtas	1.3564	0.2704	0.2553	0.1358	0.1634	0.0693	0.2483
Saharsa	0.4769	0.1044	0.0953	0.0562	0.0558	0.0243	0.0999
Samastipur	0.5215	0.0905	0.0757	0.0308	0.066	0.021	0.0705
Saran	1.1543	0.2194	0.2083	0.1056	0.1381	0.0593	0.1934
Sheikhpura	0.4038	0.0696	0.0551	0.0216	0.051	0.0151	0.049
Sheohar	0.1004	0.0155	0.0155	0.0059	0.012	0.0053	0.0118
Sitamarhi	0.6804	0.12	0.1063	0.0439	0.0907	0.028	0.0901
Siwan	0.5823	0.1164	0.1087	0.0586	0.0686	0.0299	0.1063
Supaul	0.3906	0.0705	0.056	0.0228	0.0522	0.0136	0.0494
Vaishali	0.7549	0.1455	0.1371	0.071	0.0892	0.0389	0.1301
Chandigarh	2.6154	0.1996	2.7273	0.558	0.1145	0.1776	0.0022

Balod	1.367	0.0547	0.2272	0.1394	0.262	0.2179	0.1914
Baloda Bazar	2.289	0.0887	0.3103	0.1994	0.4851	0.289	0.247
Balrampur	0.3206	0.0129	0.0569	0.0344	0.0665	0.0532	0.0477
Bametara	1.3541	0.0542	0.2251	0.1381	0.2595	0.2158	0.1896
Bastar	0.5105	0.0203	0.0878	0.0531	0.1015	0.0851	0.0718
Bijapur	0.1268	0.0049	0.0235	0.0129	0.032	0.0205	0.018
Bilaspur	2.1385	0.0834	0.3688	0.2155	0.451	0.3527	0.2872
Dakshin Bastar Dantewada	0.1923	0.0067	0.0325	0.0167	0.0456	0.032	0.0242
Dhamtari	0.6222	0.0262	0.113	0.0708	0.1296	0.1041	0.0943
Durg	2.8722	0.115	0.4774	0.293	0.5505	0.4577	0.4021
Gariaband	1.3365	0.0518	0.1812	0.1164	0.2832	0.1687	0.1442
Janjgir - Champa	1.0504	0.0324	0.1556	0.0745	0.209	0.1779	0.1209
Jashpur	0.3624	0.0122	0.0591	0.0288	0.0855	0.0588	0.0399
Kabeerdham	0.4099	0.013	0.0626	0.0303	0.0849	0.0679	0.0469
Kondagaon	0.3254	0.013	0.056	0.0339	0.0647	0.0542	0.0457
Korba	1.8925	0.0787	0.3305	0.2094	0.3596	0.3161	0.2781
Koriya	1.0498	0.0333	0.1346	0.0617	0.2147	0.1365	0.1036
Mahasamund	0.5967	0.0202	0.0814	0.0396	0.1321	0.0753	0.0639
Mungeli	0.8587	0.0335	0.1481	0.0865	0.1811	0.1416	0.1153
Narayanpur	0.1144	0.0031	0.015	0.0062	0.021	0.0188	0.0101
Raigarh	1.0369	0.0432	0.1892	0.1164	0.2235	0.1718	0.1541
Raipur	3.5009	0.1356	0.4746	0.305	0.742	0.442	0.3778
Rajnandgaon	1.1952	0.0464	0.202	0.1197	0.2366	0.1981	0.1625

Sukma	0.241	0.0084	0.0408	0.0209	0.0571	0.0401	0.0303
Surajpur	0.3471	0.0139	0.0617	0.0373	0.072	0.0576	0.0516
Surguja	0.3533	0.0142	0.0628	0.038	0.0733	0.0587	0.0525
Uttar Bastar Kanker	0.3513	0.0113	0.0541	0.0268	0.0718	0.0589	0.0425
Dadra & Nagar Haveli	0.446	0.0053	0.3148	0.0722	0.3942	0.0217	0.007
Daman	0.307	0.0064	0.22	0.0385	0.1539	0.0152	0.0046
Diu	0.0512	0.0008	0.0322	0.0046	0.0199	0.0026	0.0006
Central	2.8971	0.7338	2.754	0.3695	0.3064	0.1584	0.0022
East	1.7346	0.4394	1.6489	0.2212	0.1834	0.0948	0.0013
New Delhi	3.4286	0.8684	3.2593	0.4373	0.3626	0.1875	0.0026
North	4.4586	1.1294	4.2384	0.5686	0.4715	0.2438	0.0034
North East	1.7875	0.4528	1.6992	0.228	0.189	0.0977	0.0014
North West	3.613	0.9152	3.4346	0.4608	0.3821	0.1975	0.0027
Shahdara	2.008	0.5086	1.9089	0.2561	0.2124	0.1098	0.0015
South	1.8993	0.4811	1.8055	0.2422	0.2009	0.1038	0.0014
South East	3.1771	0.8047	3.0202	0.4052	0.336	0.1737	0.0024
South West	2.719	0.6887	2.5847	0.3468	0.2875	0.1487	0.0021
West	4.3942	1.113	4.1772	0.5604	0.4647	0.2403	0.0033
North Goa	2.2604	0.0285	1.6055	0.1969	0.5896	0.2684	0.0549
South Goa	2.1061	0.0241	1.2714	0.1452	0.5193	0.2036	0.0426
Ahmadabad	18.7015	3.3323	6.2752	2.9577	3.7563	0.5483	1.5004
Amreli	1.3836	0.2002	0.5008	0.1779	0.2609	0.0477	0.1182
Anand	2.2698	0.3409	0.8055	0.2949	0.4364	0.0721	0.1981

Aravalli	0.5783	0.0778	0.193	0.0624	0.1152	0.0175	0.0475
Banas Kantha	1.3235	0.2268	0.5731	0.2346	0.2573	0.0523	0.1366
Bharuch	1.8081	0.939	1.081	0.2579	0.3726	0.0658	0.1748
Bhavnagar	3.8473	0.6629	1.5601	0.6474	0.7375	0.1372	0.3897
Botad	2.3177	0.413	0.7777	0.3665	0.4655	0.0679	0.1859
Chota Udaipur	1.7521	1.9556	0.7164	0.2774	0.3523	0.1159	0.1449
Devbhumi Dwarka	1.0833	0.1793	0.4405	0.1775	0.2009	0.0413	0.1053
Dohad	0.6165	0.1034	0.2594	0.1056	0.1145	0.0244	0.0623
Gandhinagar	1.8828	0.3331	0.8217	0.3472	0.3561	0.0752	0.1988
Gir Somnath	1.2468	0.2037	0.4805	0.1908	0.2368	0.043	0.118
Jamnagar	2.1103	0.3493	0.8581	0.3457	0.3914	0.0804	0.2052
Junagadh	1.818	0.297	0.7006	0.2783	0.3453	0.0627	0.1721
Kachchh	2.4455	0.4014	0.9589	0.3817	0.4671	0.0861	0.234
Kheda	0.7031	0.1054	0.2765	0.1023	0.1305	0.0273	0.0633
Mahesana	1.8404	0.2799	0.635	0.2369	0.3466	0.0561	0.1611
Mahisagar	0.6385	0.0977	0.2493	0.0937	0.1202	0.0239	0.0587
Morbi	1.862	0.317	0.668	0.2881	0.3669	0.059	0.1621
Narmada	0.2097	0.0273	0.0781	0.0265	0.0376	0.0083	0.0204
Navsari	1.3829	0.2288	0.5366	0.2122	0.2823	0.0443	0.1354
Panch Mahals	0.4437	0.0701	0.1712	0.066	0.0854	0.0156	0.0421
Patan	0.9597	0.1518	0.3627	0.1407	0.1804	0.0332	0.0895
Porbandar	0.9449	0.1514	0.388	0.1517	0.1777	0.0371	0.0909
Rajkot	3.8978	0.6833	1.4031	0.6265	0.7769	0.1226	0.34

Sabar Kantha	0.7874	0.1059	0.2628	0.085	0.1569	0.0238	0.0647
Surat	16.7037	10.765	9.0178	2.6843	3.3696	0.5095	1.3558
Surendranagar	0.5009	0.0745	0.1772	0.0647	0.0939	0.0164	0.0432
Tapi	0.2937	0.0345	0.0995	0.03	0.0504	0.0114	0.0234
The Dangs	0.0769	0.0126	0.0366	0.0139	0.0187	0.0029	0.009
Vadodara	5.3562	5.9782	2.1901	0.8481	1.077	0.3544	0.4429
Valsad	2.0218	0.3397	0.8825	0.3543	0.4055	0.0795	0.2135
Ambala	1.8883	0.3458	1.1382	0.2625	1.2977	0.1962	0.2524
Bhiwani	0.8606	0.1603	0.5183	0.1193	0.6169	0.0855	0.1129
Charki Dadri	0.3688	0.0687	0.2221	0.0511	0.2644	0.0366	0.0484
Faridabad	5.8252	1.2148	3.0567	0.7828	4.2477	0.4816	0.5995
Fatehabad	0.8233	0.1269	0.3492	0.0598	0.5538	0.0575	0.0848
Gurugram	3.7552	0.7994	2.5656	0.6009	2.5759	0.4248	0.5207
Hisar	2.1501	0.3859	1.2556	0.2809	1.4854	0.2165	0.2733
Jhajjar	0.9026	0.1676	0.565	0.1328	0.6128	0.1	0.1207
Jind	1.189	0.2154	0.692	0.1554	0.8353	0.1163	0.1521
Kaithal	0.9049	0.1612	0.5478	0.1228	0.6062	0.0997	0.1142
Karnal	1.6987	0.3139	1.067	0.2471	1.1734	0.1881	0.226
Kurukshetra	1.0923	0.1882	0.6412	0.1393	0.7137	0.1201	0.1327
Mahendragarh	0.5832	0.0911	0.273	0.0486	0.4012	0.0464	0.0654
Nuh	0.5202	0.0792	0.2955	0.0521	0.3607	0.0574	0.0606
Palwal	0.918	0.167	0.5341	0.1207	0.6452	0.0893	0.118
Panchkula	1.157	0.2133	0.7187	0.1689	0.7664	0.1278	0.1562

Panipat	2.1527	0.3776	1.2399	0.275	1.4353	0.2224	0.2731
Rewari	0.8393	0.1555	0.5347	0.1264	0.5756	0.0951	0.1221
Rohtak	1.6193	0.3106	1.0253	0.2524	1.0834	0.1798	0.2208
Sirsa	1.2623	0.221	0.7067	0.1564	0.8319	0.1261	0.1527
Sonipat	1.7397	0.315	1.0774	0.2327	1.1614	0.1768	0.2221
Yamunanagar	1.6978	0.3301	1.125	0.2718	1.2269	0.1897	0.2446
Bilaspur	0.148	0.0029	0.1907	0.0768	0.1333	0.0455	0.0203
Chamba	0.2163	0.0043	0.2868	0.1157	0.1975	0.0624	0.0281
Hamirpur	0.1864	0.0037	0.2419	0.0973	0.1692	0.0564	0.025
Kangra	0.5197	0.0089	0.5935	0.2257	0.3871	0.1677	0.0686
Kinnaur	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kullu	0.2385	0.0047	0.3064	0.1251	0.2083	0.0744	0.0343
Lahul & Spiti	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mandi	0.4179	0.0059	0.4148	0.135	0.2806	0.1367	0.0441
Shimla	1.1335	0.0266	1.4634	0.6674	0.6442	0.383	0.1453
Sirmaur	0.3947	0.0052	0.3755	0.1148	0.2614	0.13	0.0384
Solan	0.6714	0.01	0.6994	0.2375	0.4775	0.216	0.073
Una	0.2574	0.0051	0.3317	0.136	0.2229	0.0801	0.0373
Anantnag	0.3716	0.0365	0.5249	0.146	0.1607	0.0974	0.0255
Badgam	0.1019	0.0093	0.153	0.0387	0.0563	0.0298	0.008
Bandipore	0.0996	0.0073	0.1262	0.0273	0.0492	0.027	0.0052
Baramula	0.2903	0.0231	0.2885	0.0649	0.1379	0.0477	0.0159
Doda	0.0503	0.0036	0.0617	0.0131	0.0239	0.0136	0.0025

Ganderbal	0.0694	0.005	0.0856	0.0187	0.0319	0.0191	0.0039
Jammu	0.9966	0.1057	1.4538	0.4276	0.4172	0.2457	0.0666
Kathua	0.135	0.0111	0.1414	0.0335	0.0623	0.0237	0.0083
Kishtwar	0.0214	0.0019	0.0326	0.0078	0.0133	0.006	0.0013
Kulgam	0.1129	0.0092	0.1541	0.0361	0.0582	0.0319	0.0073
Kupwara	0.1422	0.012	0.1996	0.0484	0.0733	0.0405	0.01
Mirpur	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Muzaffarabad	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pulwama	0.1162	0.0095	0.1612	0.0374	0.0629	0.0324	0.0071
Punch	0.056	0.0039	0.0659	0.0143	0.0234	0.0155	0.0033
Rajouri	0.0759	0.0056	0.0944	0.0209	0.0348	0.0211	0.0045
Ramban	0.0147	0.0015	0.0247	0.0071	0.0073	0.0031	0.0012
Reasi	0.0313	0.003	0.047	0.0129	0.0145	0.0092	0.0031
Samba	0.0701	0.0064	0.1061	0.0269	0.0389	0.0201	0.0054
Shupiyan	0.0236	0.0021	0.0359	0.0086	0.0146	0.0066	0.0015
Srinagar	1.815	0.1883	1.9875	0.6654	0.7881	0.327	0.0918
Udhampur	0.1685	0.0135	0.1658	0.0379	0.0774	0.0277	0.0097
Bokaro	2.5138	0.4481	0.8908	0.6169	0.7189	0.1522	0.1865
Chatra	0.184	0.023	0.0577	0.0285	0.0585	0.0121	0.0088
Deoghar	0.6503	0.1276	0.2279	0.1714	0.1726	0.0356	0.0524
Dhanbad	4.1405	0.7595	1.2577	0.9859	1.3153	0.2198	0.2617
Dumka	0.2475	0.0344	0.0839	0.0462	0.0835	0.0167	0.0138
Garhwa	0.1978	0.0261	0.0646	0.0337	0.0649	0.0132	0.0102

Giridih	0.4776	0.0936	0.1875	0.1413	0.142	0.032	0.0426
Godda	0.1856	0.0238	0.0594	0.0302	0.0591	0.012	0.0093
Gumla	0.1899	0.0295	0.049	0.0284	0.0591	0.0072	0.0105
Hazaribagh	0.6521	0.1268	0.2597	0.1897	0.2059	0.0431	0.0548
Jamtara	0.2212	0.026	0.0656	0.0313	0.0653	0.0145	0.0106
Khunti	0.1269	0.0156	0.0387	0.0196	0.038	0.0084	0.0066
Kodarma	0.4187	0.0623	0.1141	0.0627	0.1331	0.0184	0.0217
Latehar	0.1409	0.0199	0.0483	0.0271	0.0471	0.0092	0.0081
Lohardaga	0.1799	0.0273	0.0422	0.0227	0.0551	0.0057	0.0087
Pakur	0.1829	0.0237	0.0576	0.0311	0.0555	0.0122	0.0105
Palamu	0.6584	0.0958	0.2013	0.1094	0.2208	0.0356	0.0338
Pashchimi Singhbhum	0.6219	0.0995	0.1849	0.1091	0.211	0.0282	0.035
Purbi Singhbhum	3.2173	0.5952	1.1595	0.8307	0.8795	0.1978	0.2491
Ramgarh	1.1939	0.1779	0.3579	0.2019	0.3916	0.0613	0.0656
Ranchi	3.4109	0.6274	0.9951	0.7941	1.0689	0.1762	0.2058
Sahibganj	0.4553	0.0693	0.1291	0.0744	0.1452	0.0208	0.0256
Saraikele-kharsawan	0.6348	0.1187	0.2371	0.1717	0.1765	0.0408	0.0513
Simdega	0.1283	0.0146	0.0373	0.0171	0.0376	0.0083	0.0058
Bagalkote	2.0911	0.2505	0.6397	0.227	0.3319	0.2232	0.173
Ballari	31.4702	3.0405	9.4989	2.7861	4.4729	4.3031	2.2491
Bangalore	3.1183	0.397	1.2596	0.4549	0.6339	0.4414	0.2897
Belagavi	4.3986	0.4678	1.4452	0.465	0.6942	0.6019	0.3535
Bengaluru Rural	0.7159	0.0809	0.2138	0.0712	0.1155	0.0786	0.0588

Bidar	1.3805	0.1822	0.4749	0.1915	0.2037	0.1685	0.132
Chamarajanagara	0.6402	0.0729	0.1727	0.0563	0.1026	0.0579	0.0492
Chikkaballapura	1.0218	0.1145	0.2737	0.0887	0.1591	0.0957	0.0793
Chikkamagaluru	0.7521	0.098	0.2702	0.1093	0.1061	0.1011	0.0756
Chitradurga	1.0776	0.1441	0.3584	0.1449	0.1658	0.1192	0.1032
Dakshina Kannada	3.0185	0.4224	1.1195	0.4767	0.4604	0.3923	0.3315
Davanagere	1.9468	0.2807	0.711	0.3111	0.2823	0.2382	0.2053
Dharwad	3.0765	0.4803	1.2173	0.5699	0.43	0.4039	0.3578
Gadag	1.2243	0.1566	0.4394	0.1718	0.1834	0.1651	0.1157
Hassan	2.9136	0.2995	0.9264	0.2909	0.4344	0.3971	0.2293
Haveri	1.1439	0.1365	0.4033	0.1503	0.1804	0.1624	0.1196
Kalaburagi	1.2383	0.1371	0.4099	0.1394	0.1848	0.1692	0.1018
Kodagu	0.2656	0.0307	0.0968	0.0335	0.0465	0.0379	0.0242
Kolar	1.5188	0.2082	0.5354	0.2256	0.2158	0.1885	0.1523
Koppal	0.7573	0.1022	0.254	0.1042	0.114	0.0853	0.0737
Mandya	0.9913	0.1247	0.3486	0.136	0.143	0.1344	0.0944
Mysuru	3.749	0.557	1.419	0.6374	0.5436	0.4765	0.4166
Raichur	1.5948	0.2086	0.5501	0.2193	0.2383	0.1963	0.1511
Ramanagara	0.9846	0.1125	0.2547	0.0832	0.1556	0.0829	0.0757
Shivamogga	1.8875	0.2818	0.7153	0.3216	0.2752	0.2375	0.2077
Tumakuru	1.9363	0.2595	0.6712	0.273	0.2922	0.2319	0.1871
Udupi	0.9993	0.1375	0.3851	0.161	0.1552	0.1393	0.1114
Uttara Kannada	1.4974	0.1691	0.4472	0.1467	0.2433	0.1595	0.118

Vijayapura	1.573	0.2131	0.5671	0.2381	0.2165	0.209	0.1587
Yadgir	0.8056	0.0924	0.2101	0.0692	0.1274	0.0687	0.063
Alappuzha	3.7139	0.7508	2.1302	0.5756	0.1947	0.7758	0.1364
Ernakulam	7.1989	1.4896	4.0152	1.1094	0.361	1.4148	0.2697
Idukki	0.1863	0.0382	0.0777	0.0199	0.01	0.0243	0.0062
Kannur	5.482	1.0554	3.0587	0.7798	0.3109	1.162	0.1898
Kasaragod	1.5489	0.3634	0.9755	0.2972	0.0881	0.3384	0.0675
Kollam	3.8139	0.7578	2.1371	0.5764	0.1832	0.7776	0.1401
Kottayam	1.9335	0.3231	0.9851	0.2231	0.0973	0.4038	0.0606
Kozhikode	6.7156	1.3791	3.7236	1.0197	0.3389	1.3154	0.2486
Malappuram	6.2033	1.1021	3.0956	0.7343	0.3108	1.2035	0.2013
Palakkad	2.2107	0.4341	1.2308	0.3247	0.1134	0.4544	0.0792
Pathanamthitta	0.4544	0.0842	0.2228	0.0539	0.024	0.0835	0.0149
Thiruvananthapuram	5.5391	1.2539	3.2238	0.9613	0.2718	1.0499	0.2239
Thrissur	6.3536	1.4562	4.0901	1.2251	0.3754	1.489	0.2773
Wayanad	0.1077	0.0173	0.0554	0.0122	0.0053	0.0233	0.0033
Kargil	0.0236	0.0021	0.0359	0.0086	0.0146	0.0066	0.0015
Leh	0.0695	0.005	0.0854	0.0184	0.032	0.0184	0.0036
Lakshadweep	0.0853	0.0218	2.5491	0.037	0	0.0024	0.0893
Agar Malwa	0.3989	0.0223	0.0843	0.0242	0.0673	0.0323	0.0513
Alirajpur	0.1768	0.0094	0.0416	0.0118	0.0291	0.0184	0.0238
Anuppur	0.6945	0.0348	0.151	0.0428	0.101	0.0761	0.0944
Ashoknagar	0.5267	0.0272	0.0956	0.0255	0.0792	0.042	0.06

Balaghat	0.7713	0.0422	0.1616	0.0472	0.1241	0.0671	0.1042
Barwani	0.6817	0.0369	0.1301	0.0363	0.1082	0.0524	0.0829
Betul	0.9349	0.0556	0.2045	0.0674	0.1441	0.0912	0.1376
Bhind	1.275	0.0785	0.2998	0.102	0.1984	0.1365	0.1954
Bhopal	5.8124	0.3918	1.1256	0.4844	0.9434	0.5375	0.7535
Burhanpur	0.7032	0.0487	0.1833	0.0707	0.1062	0.0878	0.1265
Chhatarpur	1.1702	0.0701	0.2883	0.0944	0.1876	0.1309	0.1778
Chhindwara	1.4421	0.0857	0.3499	0.1173	0.2204	0.1659	0.231
Damoh	0.6953	0.0445	0.1749	0.0629	0.1063	0.083	0.1182
Datia	0.5323	0.0321	0.1258	0.0431	0.0773	0.0634	0.0813
Dewas	1.2165	0.0857	0.3307	0.1223	0.1994	0.1446	0.2201
Dhar	1.2666	0.0724	0.2715	0.0869	0.1887	0.1279	0.1796
Dindori	0.1044	0.0053	0.0233	0.0063	0.0165	0.0109	0.0127
East Nimar	0.6998	0.0487	0.1854	0.071	0.1092	0.086	0.1263
Guna	0.9136	0.058	0.2106	0.0749	0.1378	0.0977	0.1436
Gwalior	3.864	0.2842	0.7785	0.3163	0.6316	0.3602	0.506
Harda	0.4154	0.0212	0.0714	0.0187	0.061	0.0319	0.0461
Hoshangabad	1.1943	0.0695	0.2593	0.0833	0.1822	0.1174	0.1706
Indore	7.3382	0.5623	1.4789	0.6057	1.2096	0.6777	0.9712
Jabalpur	4.328	0.2844	0.8876	0.3565	0.7156	0.4052	0.5833
Jhabua	0.2843	0.0159	0.0709	0.0204	0.0507	0.0284	0.0386
Katni	0.6895	0.05	0.1879	0.0745	0.1083	0.0864	0.1319
Mandla	0.4147	0.0231	0.0863	0.0252	0.0676	0.0339	0.0554

Mandsaur	0.7711	0.05	0.1998	0.0709	0.1247	0.0895	0.131
Morena	1.4283	0.0797	0.3177	0.1019	0.1991	0.1678	0.201
Narsimhapur	0.6683	0.0337	0.1297	0.0353	0.098	0.0621	0.0814
Neemuch	0.6673	0.0441	0.1759	0.0637	0.1088	0.078	0.118
Niwari	0.2369	0.0133	0.0518	0.0153	0.0397	0.0205	0.0326
Panna	0.3953	0.0233	0.0869	0.0261	0.0705	0.0298	0.0545
Raisen	0.9807	0.052	0.212	0.0589	0.1584	0.0917	0.1229
Rajgarh	0.8872	0.0437	0.1905	0.0514	0.1317	0.0952	0.1096
Ratlam	1.2137	0.0802	0.2925	0.1088	0.1857	0.1335	0.2085
Rewa	1.0837	0.0742	0.2943	0.1071	0.1831	0.1253	0.1901
Sagar	2.1428	0.1248	0.4728	0.155	0.3164	0.2274	0.3109
Satna	1.309	0.0854	0.3339	0.1215	0.2023	0.1567	0.2253
Sehore	0.7265	0.0461	0.1722	0.0595	0.1176	0.0734	0.1142
Seoni	0.4338	0.0304	0.1193	0.0449	0.0726	0.0514	0.0811
Shahdol	0.66	0.0349	0.1286	0.0355	0.1022	0.0549	0.0803
Shajapur	0.5521	0.0309	0.1167	0.0335	0.0932	0.0447	0.071
Sheopur	0.3558	0.0205	0.0702	0.0203	0.0607	0.024	0.045
Shivpuri	0.8136	0.0551	0.2174	0.0791	0.1349	0.0949	0.141
Sidhi	0.3035	0.0177	0.0631	0.0185	0.0532	0.0214	0.0394
Singrauli	0.5848	0.0432	0.1576	0.065	0.0866	0.0764	0.115
Tikamgarh	0.5434	0.0305	0.1189	0.0351	0.0912	0.047	0.0748
Ujjain	2.1274	0.1618	0.5444	0.2069	0.3136	0.2661	0.3746
Umaria	0.3519	0.0177	0.0773	0.0211	0.0521	0.0376	0.0445

Vidisha	1.0129	0.0647	0.2249	0.0787	0.1612	0.0935	0.156
West Nimar	0.8837	0.0524	0.2132	0.0697	0.1374	0.1002	0.132
Ahmadnagar	2.37	0.3388	0.8633	0.3527	0.4157	0.1635	0.1599
Akola	1.7607	0.2713	0.6985	0.3124	0.305	0.1306	0.1318
Amravati	2.4476	0.3962	1.0254	0.4818	0.4199	0.1903	0.1939
Aurangabad	4.2568	0.656	1.4023	0.6796	0.7778	0.2634	0.2596
Bhandara	0.6288	0.0827	0.2139	0.0779	0.1164	0.0396	0.0414
Bid	1.392	0.1928	0.4643	0.1813	0.2437	0.0853	0.0885
Buldana	1.5929	0.2032	0.4751	0.1597	0.2868	0.0862	0.0899
Chandrapur	1.9528	0.2867	0.741	0.3134	0.3427	0.1383	0.1403
Dhule	1.3774	0.2164	0.5485	0.2523	0.2328	0.1019	0.106
Gadchiroli	0.3201	0.042	0.1061	0.0385	0.0595	0.0195	0.0209
Gondiya	0.5185	0.0835	0.228	0.1057	0.0949	0.0421	0.0437
Hingoli	0.5272	0.0684	0.1467	0.0498	0.0953	0.0242	0.0297
Jalgaon	3.4293	0.5042	1.2616	0.5368	0.5889	0.2366	0.239
Jalna	0.8912	0.1424	0.3717	0.1739	0.1471	0.0716	0.0698
Kolhapur	2.9106	0.4595	1.2182	0.5605	0.4932	0.2338	0.2282
Latur	1.4548	0.2372	0.6194	0.2945	0.2439	0.1172	0.1173
Mumbai	7.8876	2.1354	2.8048	1.4197	1.4548	0.4714	0.4931
Mumbai Suburban	23.9202	6.4759	8.506	4.3055	4.4118	1.4297	1.4955
Nagpur	8.228	1.2968	2.7697	1.3762	1.5343	0.5092	0.5179
Nanded	2.2138	0.3417	0.8997	0.4026	0.3831	0.1712	0.1673
Nandurbar	0.6938	0.1018	0.2614	0.1107	0.1227	0.0485	0.0501

Nashik	6.6273	1.0454	2.3003	1.1273	1.1955	0.424	0.4365
Osmanabad	0.7008	0.1032	0.2891	0.1198	0.1311	0.0556	0.0499
Palghar	7.3956	1.6962	2.7768	1.4142	1.3397	0.4902	0.517
Parbhani	1.4193	0.2073	0.5576	0.2371	0.2361	0.1131	0.1002
Pune	16.1507	5.0671	5.5456	1.969	2.9836	0.8969	0.9534
Raigarh	2.3639	0.434	0.9445	0.4057	0.4297	0.1733	0.1824
Ratnagiri	0.6955	0.0978	0.2496	0.0961	0.1424	0.0407	0.0487
Sangli	1.7235	0.2745	0.703	0.3258	0.2942	0.1306	0.1332
Satara	1.5014	0.2063	0.5552	0.2132	0.2761	0.1068	0.0985
Sindhudurg	0.2646	0.0375	0.1154	0.0446	0.0579	0.0212	0.0198
Solapur	3.2866	0.5373	1.3748	0.6543	0.5588	0.2533	0.263
Thane	13.5275	3.1025	5.0791	2.5867	2.4505	0.8966	0.9457
Wardha	1.0295	0.1557	0.4289	0.1854	0.1869	0.0823	0.077
Washim	0.6194	0.0785	0.1784	0.0593	0.1097	0.0322	0.0345
Yavatmal	1.6078	0.2124	0.559	0.2076	0.2794	0.1126	0.101
Bishnupur	0.1729	0.0412	0.0968	0.0197	0.0475	0.0197	0.0054
Chandel	0.0243	0.006	0.0143	0.0028	0.0074	0.0028	0.0006
Churachandpur	0.0322	0.0074	0.0168	0.0038	0.0072	0.0036	0.0013
Imphal East	0.1995	0.0476	0.1094	0.0237	0.0494	0.0219	0.0073
Imphal West	1.0186	0.2592	0.5409	0.125	0.2275	0.1012	0.0254
Jiribam	0.0271	0.0065	0.0149	0.0032	0.0067	0.003	0.001
Kakching	0.2375	0.0429	0.1061	0.0185	0.0529	0.025	0.0055
Kamjong	0.03	0.0046	0.0119	0.0018	0.0061	0.003	0.0005

Kangpokpi	0.0095	0.0021	0.0048	0.0011	0.0021	0.0011	0.0004
Noney	0.0141	0.0035	0.0083	0.0016	0.0043	0.0016	0.0004
Pherzawl	0.0095	0.0022	0.0049	0.0011	0.0021	0.0011	0.0004
Senapati	0.0076	0.0017	0.0038	0.0008	0.0016	0.0009	0.0003
Tamenglong	0.0353	0.0087	0.0208	0.004	0.0107	0.004	0.0009
Tengnoupal	0.0187	0.0046	0.011	0.0021	0.0057	0.0021	0.0005
Thoubal	0.216	0.039	0.0964	0.0168	0.0481	0.0227	0.005
Ukhrul	0.051	0.0079	0.0202	0.0031	0.0104	0.0052	0.0009
East Garo Hills	0.0258	0.0084	0.0483	0.0113	0.0374	0.0074	0.002
East Jaintia Hills	0.0137	0.0039	0.0221	0.0046	0.0168	0.0039	0.0009
East Khasi Hills	0.4664	0.1625	0.8827	0.2221	0.6934	0.1235	0.0408
North Garo Hills	0.032	0.0104	0.0598	0.014	0.0463	0.0091	0.0025
Ribhoi	0.0293	0.011	0.0642	0.0175	0.0483	0.0088	0.0032
South Garo Hills	0.0164	0.0062	0.0363	0.0095	0.0286	0.0047	0.0015
South West Garo Hills	0.0715	0.0242	0.0934	0.0218	0.0934	0.0106	0.0052
South West Khasi Hills	0.0176	0.0056	0.0318	0.0072	0.0245	0.005	0.0014
West Garo Hills	0.0354	0.012	0.0462	0.0108	0.0462	0.0052	0.0026
West Jaintia Hills	0.0248	0.0071	0.0401	0.0083	0.0305	0.007	0.0017
West Khasi Hills	0.0393	0.0124	0.0709	0.0161	0.0547	0.0112	0.003
Aizawl	0.4091	0.0689	0.2766	0.1822	0.1043	0.028	0.0098
Champhai	0.0733	0.0085	0.0444	0.0194	0.021	0.0052	0.0021
Kolasib	0.0678	0.0083	0.0424	0.0194	0.0196	0.0049	0.0022
Lawngtlai	0.0325	0.0033	0.0176	0.007	0.0084	0.0024	0.0008

Lunglei	0.1032	0.0113	0.0585	0.0248	0.0272	0.0075	0.0028
Mamit	0.018	0.0028	0.0137	0.0075	0.0054	0.0013	0.0008
Saiha	0.0392	0.004	0.0212	0.0084	0.0102	0.0029	0.001
Serchhip	0.0461	0.0054	0.0274	0.0123	0.0124	0.0034	0.0014
Dimapur	0.3663	0.0989	0.3655	0.1583	2.3071	0.0904	0.1011
Kiphire	0.0285	0.0079	0.0378	0.0133	0.2645	0.0086	0.0085
Kohima	0.2924	0.0574	0.202	0.0638	1.7731	0.0429	0.0518
Longleng	0.0129	0.003	0.0127	0.0054	0.0743	0.0038	0.0045
Mokokchung	0.1336	0.0222	0.1024	0.0326	0.6379	0.0293	0.028
Mon	0.0873	0.0135	0.0617	0.0187	0.3982	0.0187	0.0168
Peren	0.0233	0.0054	0.0231	0.0098	0.1346	0.0068	0.0081
Phek	0.0425	0.0118	0.0564	0.0198	0.3942	0.0128	0.0127
Tuensang	0.1028	0.0143	0.0673	0.0181	0.4455	0.0205	0.0169
Wokha	0.0979	0.0136	0.064	0.0172	0.4241	0.0195	0.0161
Zunheboto	0.0713	0.0112	0.0537	0.0156	0.3332	0.0144	0.0132
Anugul	0.9924	0.0988	0.1928	0.1191	0.257	0.0375	0.1207
Balangir	1.0849	0.0957	0.1518	0.0789	0.25	0.0324	0.0993
Baleshwar	1.2417	0.126	0.2257	0.1443	0.2766	0.0476	0.1602
Bargarh	0.8002	0.0745	0.1185	0.067	0.1961	0.0231	0.08
Baudh	0.1122	0.0089	0.0169	0.0078	0.0238	0.0044	0.0093
Bhadrak	0.8887	0.0925	0.1639	0.1087	0.1929	0.0342	0.1228
Cuttack	3.39	0.3895	0.6633	0.4811	0.7691	0.1224	0.5328
Debagarh	0.123	0.0097	0.0186	0.0085	0.0261	0.0049	0.0102

Dhenkanal	0.6464	0.0597	0.0934	0.0509	0.159	0.018	0.0605
Gajapati	0.356	0.0309	0.0596	0.0325	0.0787	0.0141	0.0374
Ganjam	3.628	0.3826	0.7058	0.4687	0.8825	0.1401	0.496
Jagatsinghapur	0.6406	0.0576	0.0882	0.0467	0.1498	0.0179	0.0591
Jajapur	0.7139	0.0649	0.1073	0.0595	0.17	0.0224	0.0712
Jharsuguda	1.3078	0.119	0.1703	0.0896	0.3106	0.0323	0.117
Kalahandi	0.6573	0.063	0.1009	0.058	0.1724	0.0184	0.0647
Kandhamal	0.3766	0.0335	0.0659	0.0357	0.0946	0.0148	0.0364
Kendrapara	0.4589	0.0363	0.0692	0.0318	0.0975	0.0181	0.038
Kendujhar	1.3984	0.1249	0.1994	0.1044	0.3323	0.0414	0.1268
Khordha	5.0219	0.5698	0.9755	0.6998	1.1318	0.1835	0.7764
Koraput	1.2398	0.1127	0.1738	0.0939	0.2975	0.0347	0.1162
Malkangiri	0.2579	0.0223	0.0435	0.023	0.0613	0.0102	0.0248
Mayurbhanj	0.9312	0.0964	0.1723	0.1129	0.2082	0.0357	0.1251
Nabarangapur	0.4495	0.0372	0.072	0.0372	0.0973	0.0183	0.0441
Nayagarh	0.3621	0.0362	0.0731	0.0471	0.0992	0.015	0.0474
Nuapada	0.1747	0.0177	0.0358	0.0214	0.0542	0.0066	0.0181
Puri	1.2225	0.14	0.2487	0.1773	0.2939	0.046	0.1876
Rayagada	0.7835	0.0723	0.1173	0.0656	0.1911	0.0234	0.0776
Sambalpur	1.489	0.1564	0.2803	0.1848	0.3428	0.0567	0.2006
Subarnapur	0.2489	0.0225	0.0445	0.0253	0.0619	0.01	0.0266
Sundargarh	3.4522	0.3796	0.6531	0.4572	0.7711	0.1267	0.5131
Karaikal	0.5875	0.0184	0.1138	0.0215	0.0174	0.0258	0.0043

Mahe	0.2486	0.0068	0.0539	0.0084	0.0063	0.0188	0.0016
Puducherry	3.0525	0.1166	0.8693	0.227	0.0527	0.2541	0.0205
Yanam	0.3411	0.0105	0.0613	0.0113	0.0095	0.0139	0.0023
Amritsar	1.8755	0.091	0.659	0.0591	0.5505	0.0882	0.1721
Barnala	0.2555	0.012	0.1123	0.0095	0.0766	0.0149	0.033
Bathinda	0.7038	0.0311	0.2791	0.0229	0.1931	0.0386	0.0798
Faridkot	0.3982	0.0134	0.1054	0.0063	0.1022	0.013	0.037
Fatehgarh Sahib	0.331	0.0115	0.0944	0.0059	0.0896	0.0111	0.0338
Fazilka	0.4355	0.0185	0.1639	0.0131	0.1219	0.0217	0.0499
Firozpur	0.3747	0.016	0.141	0.0113	0.1048	0.0187	0.043
Gurdaspur	0.6382	0.028	0.2565	0.021	0.1788	0.035	0.0782
Hoshiarpur	0.4548	0.0202	0.191	0.0156	0.1281	0.0268	0.0572
Jalandhar	1.5058	0.0732	0.6544	0.0584	0.4206	0.0916	0.179
Kapurthala	0.4898	0.0175	0.1474	0.0096	0.1365	0.0171	0.0534
Ludhiana	2.9216	0.14	1.025	0.0913	0.8457	0.1382	0.2696
Mansa	0.2775	0.01	0.0906	0.0058	0.08	0.0108	0.0323
Moga	0.296	0.0144	0.1301	0.0115	0.0854	0.0178	0.0365
Pathankot	0.2768	0.0122	0.1113	0.0091	0.0776	0.0152	0.0339
Patiala	1.0949	0.0486	0.4097	0.0347	0.3006	0.0544	0.1201
Rupnagar	0.2962	0.0103	0.0982	0.006	0.0792	0.0132	0.0331
Sahibzada Ajit Singh Nag*	0.8501	0.0335	0.2884	0.0216	0.231	0.0377	0.0928
Sangrur	0.8283	0.0318	0.2758	0.0197	0.2246	0.036	0.0886
Shahid Bhagat Singh Nagar	0.2018	0.0068	0.0716	0.0042	0.0512	0.0108	0.0228

Sri Muktsar Sahib	0.3816	0.0157	0.1329	0.0104	0.1005	0.0182	0.0395
Tarn Taran	0.2508	0.0083	0.0744	0.0043	0.0643	0.0102	0.0247
Ajmer	3.9056	0.2317	1.1677	0.2298	1.3259	0.2681	0.5373
Alwar	2.496	0.1413	0.751	0.1416	0.8676	0.1777	0.3374
Banswara	0.469	0.0289	0.1506	0.03	0.1706	0.0333	0.0683
Baran	1.0132	0.0522	0.2886	0.0504	0.3466	0.0722	0.1256
Barmer	0.8532	0.0395	0.1676	0.0244	0.2998	0.0328	0.0853
Bharatpur	1.9948	0.1023	0.56	0.0973	0.6704	0.1411	0.24
Bhilwara	1.9614	0.1132	0.5986	0.1136	0.6939	0.1384	0.263
Bikaner	3.0374	0.1832	0.8986	0.1782	1.0615	0.196	0.4196
Bundi	0.879	0.0457	0.2517	0.0444	0.2991	0.0626	0.1113
Chittaurgarh	1.1917	0.0603	0.3119	0.0528	0.4106	0.0742	0.1375
Churu	2.4524	0.1246	0.6065	0.1026	0.8489	0.1368	0.2786
Dausa	0.9348	0.0394	0.2046	0.0278	0.3122	0.0523	0.0883
Dhaulpur	1.0077	0.0543	0.2703	0.0486	0.3507	0.0611	0.1231
Dungarpur	0.3924	0.0156	0.0952	0.013	0.1231	0.0278	0.0387
Ganganagar	2.1546	0.114	0.6063	0.1069	0.768	0.1417	0.2681
Hanumangarh	1.4588	0.0696	0.3861	0.0633	0.4688	0.1031	0.1626
Jaipur	14.6627	0.8306	3.4155	0.7048	5.4879	0.7877	1.5039
Jaisalmer	0.4206	0.0184	0.0845	0.0116	0.1429	0.0192	0.0398
Jalor	0.6968	0.0295	0.1578	0.0217	0.2353	0.0406	0.0667
Jhalawar	1.0198	0.0443	0.2434	0.035	0.3518	0.062	0.1052
Jhunjhunun	2.0629	0.1	0.5574	0.0899	0.7389	0.1357	0.2334

Jodhpur	5.3769	0.2969	1.2484	0.2509	1.9785	0.2972	0.5419
Karauli	0.9046	0.0478	0.2281	0.0404	0.31	0.0508	0.1081
Kota	4.9494	0.2855	1.1843	0.2401	1.8606	0.2717	0.5131
Nagaur	2.8162	0.1324	0.6655	0.1029	0.983	0.155	0.2986
Pali	1.8453	0.0964	0.5311	0.0929	0.6412	0.1303	0.2253
Pratapgarh	0.3134	0.0137	0.0849	0.0123	0.1136	0.0222	0.0326
Rajsamand	0.8067	0.0377	0.2034	0.0309	0.2994	0.0459	0.088
Sawai Madhopur	0.9746	0.0614	0.3122	0.0635	0.3465	0.0687	0.142
Sikar	2.6431	0.1321	0.6806	0.1149	0.8968	0.1642	0.3069
Sirohi	0.9288	0.0393	0.2165	0.0306	0.309	0.0575	0.0948
Tonk	1.2722	0.0658	0.3595	0.063	0.4288	0.0901	0.1552
Udaipur	2.2314	0.1354	0.7082	0.1404	0.7956	0.1583	0.3268
East District	0.0324	0	0.4233	0.0332	0.1204	0.3601	0.0027
North District	0.0012	0	0.0177	0.0013	0.0057	0.0097	0.0001
South District	0.0058	0	0.0777	0.005	0.03	0.049	0.0004
West District	0.0014	0	0.02	0.0015	0.0064	0.0109	0.0001
Ariyalur	0.3014	0.0158	0.0703	0.011	0.0442	0.0234	0.0125
Chengalpattu	4.2092	0.2614	1.015	0.1894	0.6085	0.2938	0.1995
Chennai	15.6109	1.2053	3.3317	0.8232	2.202	0.8454	0.7115
Coimbatore	9.0643	0.6027	2.0556	0.4174	1.3659	0.5662	0.4111
Cuddalore	2.9808	0.1936	0.7292	0.1442	0.4384	0.2023	0.15
Dharmapuri	0.9324	0.0553	0.2235	0.0384	0.1543	0.0634	0.0408
Dindigul	2.6857	0.1756	0.7114	0.1381	0.4315	0.2007	0.1358

Erode	3.8273	0.2437	0.9738	0.1906	0.6118	0.2768	0.198
Kallakurichi	0.9042	0.0507	0.1904	0.0311	0.1357	0.0551	0.037
Kancheepuram	4.5402	0.282	1.0948	0.2042	0.6564	0.3169	0.2152
Kanniyakumari	4.9659	0.3263	1.4036	0.2743	0.8623	0.4018	0.2633
Karur	1.5803	0.0934	0.3508	0.0608	0.2527	0.0965	0.0682
Krishnagiri	1.4648	0.0924	0.3603	0.0681	0.219	0.1027	0.0706
Madurai	6.4182	0.4351	1.4046	0.2939	0.9475	0.3832	0.2845
Nagapattinam	1.2317	0.0789	0.2974	0.0583	0.1798	0.0829	0.0617
Namakkal	2.4762	0.1501	0.5765	0.1032	0.4103	0.1576	0.1115
Perambalur	0.3418	0.0198	0.089	0.0149	0.0584	0.027	0.0149
Pudukkottai	0.9888	0.0681	0.2753	0.0579	0.1519	0.0783	0.0565
Ramanathapuram	1.4681	0.089	0.3439	0.0609	0.2448	0.0935	0.0653
Ranipet	2.1929	0.1385	0.52	0.0995	0.3366	0.1421	0.1065
Salem	5.5703	0.3985	1.5212	0.3297	0.8351	0.4096	0.3202
Sivaganga	1.4124	0.0863	0.3409	0.0634	0.2025	0.1013	0.0677
Tenkasi	2.2098	0.1434	0.5486	0.1078	0.3286	0.1532	0.1111
Thanjavur	2.685	0.1923	0.7474	0.1598	0.4234	0.2002	0.1523
The Nilgiris	1.5831	0.0871	0.3575	0.0578	0.2386	0.1102	0.0662
Theni	2.4184	0.1437	0.5604	0.0969	0.3965	0.1559	0.105
Thiruvallur	7.9697	0.5442	2.016	0.4187	1.1136	0.5504	0.4226
Thiruvarur	0.9493	0.0549	0.2014	0.0343	0.1459	0.056	0.0401
Thoothukkudi	2.9134	0.1897	0.7575	0.1477	0.4532	0.2135	0.1482
Tiruchirappalli	4.1407	0.3051	1.161	0.2567	0.5833	0.315	0.2433

Tirunelveli	2.9007	0.1883	0.7202	0.1415	0.4313	0.2012	0.1458
Tirupathur	1.4822	0.0936	0.3514	0.0672	0.2275	0.096	0.072
Tiruppur	5.1781	0.3294	1.2545	0.2417	0.7572	0.3533	0.254
Tiruvannamalai	1.6331	0.1072	0.4215	0.0836	0.2489	0.118	0.0847
Vellore	2.176	0.1374	0.5159	0.0987	0.334	0.141	0.1057
Viluppuram	1.0266	0.0576	0.2162	0.0353	0.1541	0.0625	0.042
Virudhunagar	3.3361	0.2141	0.8188	0.1565	0.5275	0.2153	0.1656
Adilabad	0.3692	0.0621	0.1044	0.0542	0.0619	0.0258	0.0318
Bhadradi Kothagudem	0.7562	0.1291	0.223	0.1223	0.1282	0.0553	0.0723
Hyderabad	18.9171	3.4622	5.5534	4.079	3.4243	1.3867	1.8142
Jagitial	0.7329	0.1296	0.2472	0.1527	0.1264	0.0619	0.092
Jangoan	0.1742	0.0298	0.0441	0.0217	0.0306	0.0087	0.0129
Jayashankar	0.104	0.0161	0.0304	0.0143	0.0155	0.0102	0.0076
Jogulamba Gadwal	0.028	0.0045	0.0089	0.0044	0.0045	0.0023	0.0021
Kamareddy	0.5803	0.1021	0.182	0.1082	0.1007	0.0437	0.0658
Karimnagar	0.5979	0.1057	0.2017	0.1246	0.1031	0.0505	0.0751
Khammam	0.8877	0.1515	0.2617	0.1436	0.1504	0.0649	0.0849
Kumuram Bheem Asifabad	0.3058	0.0514	0.0864	0.0449	0.0513	0.0214	0.0264
Mahabubabad	0.1948	0.0309	0.0615	0.0306	0.0315	0.0161	0.0144
Mahabubnagar	0.3314	0.0558	0.1041	0.0575	0.055	0.027	0.0327
Mancherial	0.8583	0.1444	0.2427	0.1261	0.144	0.06	0.074
Medak	0.3752	0.0613	0.1064	0.052	0.0612	0.0272	0.0293
Medchal Malkajgiri	0.4587	0.0738	0.135	0.066	0.0739	0.0361	0.0347

Mulugu	0.0307	0.005	0.0106	0.0055	0.0054	0.002	0.0023
Nagarkurnool	0.4727	0.0795	0.1484	0.0821	0.0785	0.0386	0.0466
Nalgonda	0.7208	0.1256	0.2429	0.1456	0.1243	0.0588	0.0839
Narayanpet	0.2431	0.0409	0.0763	0.0422	0.0404	0.0198	0.024
Nirmal	0.3892	0.0655	0.11	0.0572	0.0653	0.0272	0.0336
Nizamabad	0.8611	0.1515	0.2701	0.1606	0.1495	0.0648	0.0977
Peddapalli	0.6106	0.108	0.206	0.1273	0.1053	0.0516	0.0767
Rajanna Sircilla	0.3271	0.0578	0.1103	0.0682	0.0564	0.0276	0.0411
Ranga Reddy	1.47	0.2366	0.4326	0.2116	0.2367	0.1158	0.1113
Sangareddy	0.6503	0.1063	0.1845	0.0902	0.1061	0.0472	0.0507
Siddipet	0.4552	0.0744	0.1291	0.0631	0.0743	0.033	0.0355
Suryapet	0.4724	0.0823	0.1592	0.0954	0.0815	0.0386	0.055
Vikarabad	1.0113	0.1627	0.2976	0.1456	0.1629	0.0797	0.0766
Wanaparthy	0.2303	0.0387	0.0723	0.04	0.0382	0.0188	0.0227
Warangal Rural	0.0495	0.0078	0.0153	0.0075	0.0078	0.0043	0.0037
Warangal Urban	0.9605	0.1733	0.3636	0.2394	0.1677	0.0918	0.1425
Yadadri Bhuvanagiri	0.4131	0.072	0.1392	0.0834	0.0712	0.0337	0.0481
Dhalai	0.0743	0.0285	0.0261	0.0173	0.0219	0.0057	0.0029
Gomati	0.1171	0.0415	0.0379	0.0237	0.0313	0.0099	0.0044
Khowai	0.3115	0.1374	0.1092	0.0775	0.076	0.0262	0.0092
North Tripura	0.1382	0.0461	0.0418	0.0242	0.0351	0.0117	0.0045
Sipahijala	0.3266	0.1441	0.1145	0.0812	0.0797	0.0275	0.0096
South Tripura	0.11	0.039	0.0356	0.0222	0.0294	0.0093	0.0041

Unokoti	0.0961	0.0321	0.0291	0.0168	0.0244	0.0081	0.0031
West Tripura	0.5826	0.2571	0.2043	0.145	0.1421	0.0491	0.0172
Agra	6.6544	0.6854	1.3522	0.577	0.8329	0.3757	0.4664
Aligarh	3.581	0.3367	0.9106	0.373	0.424	0.2487	0.3334
Ambedkar Nagar	0.9056	0.0771	0.1957	0.0718	0.1079	0.0515	0.0735
Amethi	0.3065	0.0288	0.0815	0.0331	0.0378	0.0217	0.0316
Amroha	1.4844	0.1233	0.3198	0.1158	0.1703	0.0901	0.1166
Auraiya	0.8106	0.0599	0.1596	0.0484	0.0964	0.0445	0.0574
Azamgarh	1.2172	0.1046	0.2899	0.106	0.1536	0.075	0.1083
Baghpat	0.8814	0.075	0.2043	0.0738	0.1089	0.0542	0.0715
Bahraich	0.8543	0.0779	0.2165	0.0855	0.1022	0.06	0.0757
Ballia	0.9786	0.0757	0.2193	0.0748	0.1087	0.0687	0.0748
Balrampur	0.5858	0.0435	0.1099	0.0331	0.0689	0.0298	0.0404
Banda	0.8264	0.0744	0.209	0.0816	0.0993	0.058	0.0744
Bara Banki	1.1268	0.0852	0.2406	0.0744	0.1404	0.0655	0.0823
Bareilly	4.7384	0.4906	1.1535	0.4482	0.5541	0.3197	0.4221
Basti	0.3928	0.1358	0.1067	0.0447	0.0468	0.0282	0.0388
Bhadohi	0.7798	0.0603	0.1596	0.0505	0.0972	0.0411	0.0587
Bijnor	3.3044	0.2458	0.5853	0.175	0.3865	0.1546	0.2245
Budaun	2.1079	0.1665	0.4556	0.1546	0.2466	0.1304	0.1631
Bulandshahr	2.7995	0.2312	0.6101	0.2192	0.3226	0.1726	0.2209
Chandauli	0.7228	0.0634	0.182	0.0693	0.0874	0.0506	0.0666
Chitrakoot	0.3307	0.0266	0.0658	0.0213	0.0426	0.0152	0.0253

Deoria	0.9997	0.0806	0.2314	0.0822	0.1133	0.0702	0.08
Etah	0.824	0.0709	0.204	0.0756	0.1001	0.0571	0.071
Etawah	1.0988	0.1002	0.2753	0.1098	0.1279	0.078	0.0971
Faizabad	1.1098	0.0911	0.267	0.0887	0.1514	0.0657	0.0905
Farrukhabad	1.2484	0.1126	0.3112	0.1232	0.1449	0.0886	0.1107
Fatehpur	0.985	0.0855	0.2379	0.0911	0.1122	0.0699	0.0836
Firozabad	2.4156	0.2477	0.6338	0.2621	0.2781	0.1686	0.2293
Gautam Buddha Nagar	2.8787	0.4167	0.8648	0.3001	0.341	0.2092	0.2668
Ghaziabad	6.705	0.8464	1.701	0.6455	0.8179	0.4124	0.5324
Ghazipur	0.8631	0.0722	0.2072	0.075	0.1024	0.0598	0.0701
Gonda	0.6685	0.0603	0.1719	0.0667	0.0822	0.0465	0.062
Gorakhpur	2.4148	0.2329	0.6306	0.2649	0.2835	0.173	0.2307
Hamirpur	0.5888	0.0426	0.1124	0.0336	0.0677	0.0326	0.0413
Hapur	3.183	0.4018	0.8075	0.3064	0.3883	0.1958	0.2528
Hardoi	1.7656	0.1461	0.3846	0.1366	0.209	0.1055	0.1381
Hathras	1.0277	0.0861	0.2472	0.0905	0.1204	0.0719	0.0869
Jalaun	1.3322	0.1176	0.2909	0.1107	0.1607	0.0734	0.1123
Jaunpur	1.0553	0.0913	0.2582	0.0979	0.1232	0.0741	0.0916
Jhansi	2.5242	0.2269	0.6165	0.2419	0.2977	0.1708	0.2231
Kannauj	0.9975	0.0732	0.1829	0.0542	0.1163	0.0505	0.0673
Kanpur Dehat	0.5631	0.0412	0.1278	0.0399	0.0675	0.0384	0.044
Kanpur Nagar	9.8168	1.0426	2.0001	0.9014	1.2317	0.5422	0.6888
Kasganj	0.9137	0.074	0.2152	0.0756	0.1072	0.0631	0.0732

Kaushambi	0.3826	0.0329	0.1038	0.0358	0.0561	0.0246	0.0355
Kheri	1.4875	0.1215	0.3383	0.1185	0.1779	0.0952	0.1174
Kushinagar	0.5719	0.04	0.1236	0.0363	0.0666	0.0388	0.0395
Lalitpur	0.4935	0.0482	0.1315	0.0559	0.0585	0.0355	0.0501
Lucknow	9.9443	1.036	2.0062	0.9	1.2547	0.5551	0.6935
Mahoba	0.6649	0.0482	0.1206	0.0351	0.0769	0.0339	0.0436
Mahrajganj	0.4554	0.0323	0.1	0.0298	0.0539	0.0308	0.0321
Mainpuri	0.9024	0.0753	0.2143	0.0782	0.1043	0.0632	0.0736
Mathura	2.3379	0.2052	0.5527	0.2094	0.2826	0.1479	0.2031
Mau	1.5227	0.1325	0.372	0.1419	0.1764	0.1071	0.131
Meerut	5.8503	0.5378	1.1903	0.4876	0.7318	0.3078	0.4077
Mirzapur	1.0234	0.0937	0.2578	0.1039	0.1176	0.0729	0.0943
Moradabad	2.6189	0.2435	0.6596	0.2704	0.2986	0.1881	0.2377
Muzaffarnagar	2.7805	0.2319	0.6221	0.2248	0.3255	0.1748	0.2214
Pilibhit	1.1284	0.0956	0.2577	0.0929	0.1383	0.0686	0.0914
Pratapgarh	0.5871	0.0458	0.1198	0.0386	0.0728	0.0306	0.046
Prayagraj	4.7983	0.4348	0.9764	0.4281	0.606	0.2693	0.343
Rae Bareli	0.9187	0.0835	0.233	0.092	0.1096	0.0647	0.0832
Rampur	1.8272	0.1541	0.4317	0.1612	0.2056	0.1294	0.1501
Saharanpur	3.2419	0.2973	0.7793	0.3118	0.3821	0.2105	0.2861
Sambhal	2.027	0.1884	0.5105	0.2093	0.2311	0.1456	0.184
Sant Kabir Nagar	0.43	0.0311	0.0965	0.0293	0.052	0.029	0.0313
Shahjahanpur	1.8577	0.1601	0.4324	0.1634	0.2142	0.1234	0.1532

Shamli	1.0428	0.087	0.2333	0.0843	0.1221	0.0655	0.083
Shrawasti	0.1313	0.0095	0.0294	0.0088	0.016	0.0088	0.0092
Siddharthnagar	0.5374	0.0366	0.1126	0.0331	0.0591	0.0373	0.0383
Sitapur	1.7608	0.1428	0.3677	0.1279	0.2051	0.1018	0.133
Sonbhadra	1.0413	0.0748	0.2315	0.0705	0.123	0.0707	0.0773
Sultanpur	0.2583	0.0242	0.0687	0.0279	0.0319	0.0183	0.0266
Unnao	1.6771	0.1375	0.3766	0.1348	0.1953	0.1073	0.1394
Varanasi	5.0429	0.4286	1.3458	0.4565	0.7367	0.3202	0.44
Almora	0.2083	0.0143	0.1303	0.0212	0.0417	0.0175	0.0145
Bageshwar	0.027	0.0016	0.0151	0.0027	0.0045	0.0029	0.0023
Chamoli	0.2135	0.0122	0.1116	0.0162	0.0384	0.0206	0.0128
Champawat	0.1279	0.0081	0.0757	0.0123	0.0256	0.0121	0.009
Dehradun	3.2937	0.2211	1.7431	0.2931	0.5747	0.306	0.1919
Garhwal	0.4298	0.0223	0.2016	0.0258	0.07	0.0419	0.0218
Hardwar	2.4557	0.1613	1.3273	0.2156	0.4454	0.2317	0.1414
Nainital	1.3197	0.0854	0.6722	0.1099	0.2243	0.1219	0.075
Pithoragarh	0.2797	0.0159	0.1056	0.015	0.0493	0.0164	0.0138
Rudraprayag	0.0297	0.0018	0.0168	0.003	0.005	0.0031	0.0025
Tehri Garhwal	0.2591	0.0149	0.1376	0.0198	0.0484	0.0246	0.015
Udham Singh Nagar	2.1194	0.1344	1.1007	0.1731	0.3712	0.1996	0.117
Uttarkashi	0.085	0.0053	0.0502	0.0078	0.018	0.008	0.0055
Alipurduar	0.8156	0.036	0.256	0.1298	0.1657	0.0971	0.0416
Bankura	0.4447	0.0191	0.1327	0.066	0.0891	0.0506	0.0227

Birbhum	0.7456	0.0268	0.1954	0.0761	0.1658	0.0737	0.0303
Cooch Behar	0.4695	0.0165	0.1299	0.0506	0.1024	0.0519	0.0195
Dakshin Dinajpur	0.3442	0.0158	0.1044	0.0559	0.0654	0.0383	0.0183
Darjiling	0.5418	0.0219	0.1767	0.0813	0.1203	0.0706	0.027
Hooghly	3.0753	0.1383	0.9916	0.5096	0.6371	0.3741	0.1642
Howrah	4.5641	0.2094	1.3722	0.7253	0.9755	0.5353	0.2232
Jalpaiguri	1.1843	0.0523	0.3717	0.1885	0.2406	0.141	0.0605
Jhargram	0.2249	0.0099	0.067	0.0339	0.0455	0.0246	0.0113
Kalimpong	0.0993	0.004	0.0324	0.0149	0.0221	0.0129	0.0049
Kolkata	7.1366	0.3328	1.7505	1.1177	1.4381	0.6987	0.2879
Maldah	0.7909	0.0348	0.2563	0.1261	0.1781	0.0939	0.0417
Medinipur West	0.86	0.0378	0.2561	0.1295	0.174	0.0939	0.0432
Murshidabad	2.196	0.0829	0.6396	0.2718	0.4843	0.2544	0.0983
Nadia	2.1351	0.0913	0.6778	0.3269	0.4629	0.2508	0.1083
North Twenty Four Pargan*	8.0125	0.3884	2.6536	1.4902	1.4842	1.0176	0.453
Paschim Bardhaman	3.2638	0.1555	1.1009	0.6038	0.626	0.4235	0.1849
Purba Bardhaman	1.1059	0.047	0.3376	0.164	0.2295	0.1275	0.0547
Purba Medinipur	0.91	0.0375	0.2558	0.121	0.186	0.0942	0.0439
Puruliya	0.5262	0.022	0.1719	0.0834	0.1111	0.0701	0.029
South Twenty Four Pargan*	3.0086	0.1298	0.982	0.4848	0.6344	0.3807	0.1598
Uttar Dinajpur	0.5526	0.0237	0.1591	0.079	0.1088	0.0596	0.0268

Table 7: Fraction Weightage of Vehicle Categories on Different Road Types

	2W	LMV-P	4W	LMV-G	HDV-Truck	Buses	Others
Golden Quadrilateral	0	0	0	0	0.4	0	0.1
(National + state) Highway	0	0	0.17	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.2
District roads	0.3	0.15	0.23	0.375	0.1	0.4	0.7
City roads	0.7	0.85	0.60	0.325	0.1	0.2	0

Table 8: State emission comparison dataset

State_Name	TERI2016(Kt/yr)	Present study(kt/yr)
ANDAMAN & NICOBAR	0.0008	0.356797332
ANDHRA PRADESH	5.91	53.4828912
ARUNACHAL PRADESH	0.01	0.504225441
ASSAM	0.7	13.76278218
BIHAR	1.73	26.69012442
CHANDIGARH	0.0518	2.811862951
CHHATTISGARH	1.98	18.65602044
DADRA & NAGAR HAVE	0.0006	0.245837968
DAMAN & DIU	0.0004	0.09920464
DELHI	5.8	30.20396379
GOA	0.08	3.767341237
GUJARAT	31.76	82.15758404
HARYANA	1.14	39.40166484

HIMACHAL PRADESH	0.18	6.114837395
JAMMU & KASHMIR	0.29	6.697340679
JHARKHAND	1.21	18.57246127
KARNATAKA	13.62	64.66505965
KERALA	9.68	39.74808195
MADHYA PRADESH	4.89	45.66087596
MAHARASHTRA	77.13	111.2820602
MANIPUR	0.01	1.346899106
MEGHALAYA	0.11	1.506292972
NAGALAND	0.06	2.994512177
ODISHA	3.17	25.20916773
PUDUCHERRY	0.0207	0.349552278
PUNJAB	4.82	12.18864668
RAJASTHAN	12.58	54.72697082
TAMIL NADU	30.45	82.22988424
TELANGANA	2.82	21.57192287
TRIPURA	0.01	1.578318362
UTTAR PRADESH	32.9	102.0580638
UTTARAKHAND	0.19	9.067723286
WEST BENGAL	2.97	33.65566875

References: “Development of spatially resolved air pollution emission inventory of India, TERI

Table 9: City emission comparison dataset

City	Previous study (Tons/yr)	Present Study (Tons/Yr)
Agra ^[a]	893.45	1142.9
Amritsar ^[a]	610.6	919.3
Bengaluru ^[b]	4768.5	2718.6
Bhopal ^[a]	1008.9	2845
Bhubaneswar ^[a]	2340	1166.2
Chandigarh ^[a]	2305.8	4769.7
Chennai ^[a]	22101	13285.3
Coimbatore ^[a]	1931.7	4034.8
Dehradun ^[a]	204.6	525.1
Indore ^[a]	2689.95	2459.7
Jaipur ^[a]	3010	2539.7
Kanpur ^[a]	3074.95	2050.7
Kochi ^[a]	1491.45	1782.6
Ludhiana ^[c]	1339	823
Nagpur ^[a]	7313.9	7335.6
Patna ^[d]	1212	1047.5
Pune ^[a]	4141.8	4819.2
Ranchi ^[a]	1854.15	959.6
Varanasi ^[a]	992.2	2240.5
gaya ^[e]	1503	1541
Surat city ^[h]	4730	2913
Rajkot ^[g]	620	797.8

Lucknow ^[f]	6000	3571.2
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[a] Guttikunda et al., “Air pollution knowledge assessments (ApnA) for 20 Indian cities”, Urban climate

[b] TERI, 2010; “Air quality assessment, emission inventory and source apportionment study for bangalore city”

[c] PPCB,2020; “Source Apportionment study to prepare action plan to improve air quality of Ludhiana City”

[d] BPCB, “Comprehensive Clean Air Action Plan for the City of Patna”

[e] BPCB, “Comprehensive Clean Air Action Plan for the City of Gaya”

[f] urban emission.info

[g] Guttikunda and Jawahar; “Application of SIM-air modeling tools to assess air quality in Indian cities”, Atmospheric environment 62 (2012) 551-561.

[h] TERI, 2021; “Source apportionment study for the city of Surat, Gujarat